

What financial payment models are used to fund additional services in general practice settings, particularly to improve quality of care and patient outcomes, and support the transfer of services from hospital to community settings: A rapid evidence summary

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Abstract: In Wales, there is a clear policy ambition to strengthen community-based care and to shift services traditionally delivered in hospital settings into primary and community care. These reforms require the development of new payment mechanisms and administrative arrangements alongside the General Medical Services (GMS) contract mechanisms. This rapid evidence summary (RES) was conducted to inform these plans.

This RES aims to summarise evidence from the UK and other international health systems on financial models used to fund additional services in general practice. It is based on a limited search of key resources. Priority is given to studies representing robust evidence synthesis, and no quality appraisal or evidence synthesis was conducted.

Included evidence (organisational reports, reviews, evaluation reports and research publications) were published between 2011 to 2025. Evidence was described across four broad categories: models of care / service delivery structures; contracting and governance models; additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms; and incentive, quality, and performance frameworks. We describe the models of care within these categories and the evidence of effectiveness.

Findings for models of care / service delivery structures cover accountable care organisations (ACO, e.g. USA), multispecialty community providers (MCP, England), primary care home model (PCH), primary care networks (PCNs), and year of care models. Findings for contracting and governance models include Alliance contracting, prime contracting and outcome-based contracting. Findings for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms include additional roles reimbursement scheme (ARRS, England), additional capacity funding delivered via Health Boards in Wales, Bundled Payments (OECD countries), directed enhanced services (DES), and local enhanced services (LES). Evidence for incentive, quality and performance frameworks include quality and outcomes framework (QOF), quality assurance and improvement framework (replaced QOF in Wales in 2019), and other quality improvement schemes operating instead of or in addition to QOF.

Accountable care organisations may hold some promise, building upon primary care networks and year of care models, potentially using DES mechanisms. Broad models of outcome-based contracting may deliver some positive quality and cost outcomes. Role reimbursement schemes can enhance workforce, access, quality and delivery of services but attention required to supervision and sustainability. Local enhanced services offer flexible mechanisms to address identified local population health needs. Within core GMS, quality improvement schemes lead to very limited benefits, and the QOF improved some elements of quality, although sustained benefits are harder to demonstrate.

Further research is needed including on the effective transfer of services to primary and community care and on the impact of different financial models or payment schemes to fund additional services in general practice.

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What financial payment models are used to fund additional services in general practice settings, particularly to support the transfer of services from hospital to community settings? A rapid evidence summary

(Report number: RES0061. March 2026)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

What is a Rapid Evidence Summary?

Our Rapid Evidence Summaries (RES) are designed to provide a rapid response product. They are based on a limited search of key resources. Priority is given to studies representing robust evidence synthesis. No quality appraisal or evidence synthesis are conducted, and the summary should be interpreted with caution.

Who is this Rapid Evidence Summary for?

This RES has been prepared for Welsh Government to help inform the development of a new payment mechanism for services delivered in General Practice, supporting the policy aim of shifting care from hospital to community settings.

Background / Aim of Rapid Evidence Summary

The 2025-26 General Medical Services contract in Wales reinforces the shift toward community-based care by supporting the 'Community by Design' programme and expanding the range of services delivered outside secondary (hospital) care. These reforms require the development of new payment mechanisms and administrative arrangements alongside the Global Sum and Directed Supplementary Services mechanisms. To inform this work, this RES summarises evidence from the UK and other international health systems on financial models used to fund additional services in general practice.

Results

Recency of the evidence base

- Searches were conducted on bibliographic databases and relevant organisational websites, limited to English language publications from 2004 to February 2026. Included evidence was published between 2011 to 2025.

Extent of the evidence base

Evidence was organised and described across four broad categories: models of care / service delivery structures; contracting and governance models; additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms; and incentive, quality, and performance frameworks.

- Models of care / service delivery structures comprise organisational and delivery arrangements that define how primary care services are structured, coordinated, and delivered across providers or populations.
 - Accountable care organisations: **2** organisational reports and **3** reviews.
 - Multispecialty community providers: **2** organisational reports, **2** reviews and **3** evaluation reports.
 - Primary care home: **2** organisational reports and **1** evaluation report.
 - Primary care networks: **2** organisational and **4** evaluation reports and **3** primary research publications
 - Year of care approaches: **4** organisational reports and **3** evaluation reports.
- Contracting and governance models are formal contractual arrangements that determine accountability, risk-sharing, and responsibility for the delivery of services between commissioners and providers.
 - Alliance contracting, lead (prime) contracting and outcome-based contracting: **2** organisational reports, **2** reviews and **1** evaluation report.
- Additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms are payment mechanisms used to provide funding beyond core primary care contracts to support the delivery of additional services, roles, or activities.

- Additional roles reimbursement scheme (England): **3** organisational reports, **1** evaluation report and **6** primary research publications.
- Additional capacity funding (Wales): **3** organisational reports.
- Bundled payments: **3** organisational reports and **4** reviews.
- Directed enhanced services: **3** organisational reports and **1** primary research publication.
- Local enhanced services: **1** organisational report, **1** review and **1** primary research publication.
- Incentive, quality, and performance frameworks: frameworks that link additional payments to specified quality criteria, performance indicators, or assurance requirements.
 - Quality outcomes framework: **2** organisational reports and **9** reviews.
 - Quality assurance and improvement framework: **2** organisational reports.
 - Other quality improvement schemes: **1** review.

Key findings for models of care / service delivery structures

- Accountable care organisations ('ACO', USA) are funded through fee-for-service payments to provider networks through group contracts, alongside reinvestment of shared saving. They are associated with generally increased primary care visits alongside reductions in inpatient admissions and Emergency department visits, improvements in preventive care and chronic disease management, **with modest cost savings overall and increased quality of care**
- Multispecialty community providers (MCP, England) integrate primary and community-based care provision, potentially incorporating some hospital services (e.g. outpatient clinics or some diagnostic services), delivered through ACO contract packages, with GPs operating as owners or salaried staff. Limited implementation experience or evidence of improved outcomes, and **policy retreat**¹ noted.
- Primary care home created partnerships for multidisciplinary care delivery based on population needs assessment via blended payment mechanisms. Initial investment may be required for management support, coaching and clinical supervision during implementation. **Some improvements in service delivery with reduced costs** but cost-effectiveness uncertain.
- Primary care networks (PCNs) cover 30-50,000 population via Network Contract Directed Enhanced Services and a Network Agreement. Practices deliver their own services and collaborate to provide network services with payments linked to delivery of national network service specifications. Some evidence of improved collaboration, sustainability (financial & workforce, including recruitment in deprived areas) but with increased workload and dependence on power imbalances; **effectiveness evidence is limited and short term.**
- Year of care involved coordinated multidisciplinary working focused on long-term conditions, supported by a risk-adjusted capitation budget and a range of contracting approaches. Improved continuity and quality of experience for patients and staff; may be cost neutral or deliver savings, **giving value for money; however, health outcomes were not affected in the short term.**

Key findings for contracting and governance models

- Alliance contracting involves a group of providers contracting with commissioner to deliver services, jointly sharing risk and responsibility for delivery; upfront costs may be high; dependent on relational and leadership culture; **Evidence of improved quality or cost outcomes is limited.**
- Prime contracting involves a lead provider holding a contract and sub-contracting services for a defined population (e.g. older adults); complexity is high; commissioner oversight may be reduced; alignment of incentives across the sub-contractor chain is critical and a potential risk. **Evidence of improved quality or cost outcomes is limited.**
- Outcome-based contracting focuses on outcomes rather than processes, activities, or volumes, with both narrow (single provider) and broad (multidisciplinary) models; requires high upfront investment, including IT and monitoring. Payment is contingent on achieving specified outcomes, which may be iterative, with bonuses and/or penalties to support cost control and quality objectives. **Broad models: Positive quality and cost outcomes** in specific clinical conditions (e.g. acute myocardial infarction,

¹ Policy retreat refers to the scaling back or abandonment of a policy approach following initial implementation or exploration.

heart failure, pneumonia, hip and knee replacement, stroke, diabetes, coronary artery bypass graft surgery); narrow models: more mixed findings.

Key findings for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms

- Additional roles reimbursement scheme (ARRS, England), delivered via the network contract directed enhanced services provides reimbursement (mostly 70%) for employing specified additional multidisciplinary roles within PCNs. Some benefits were reported in workforce expansion, access and service delivery; however, **many PCNs lacked the organisational capacity and structures** to fully realise intended benefits, with concerns around supervision and sustainability.
- Additional capacity funding (Wales) delivered via Health Boards within general medical services (GMS), provides 50% reimbursement to enhance workforce capacity. **No evaluation evidence identified.**
- Bundled payments (OECD countries) are episode-based models for acute or elective care, or periodic models for long term conditions. They depend on clear definition of the contracting party (single or multiple collaborating/sub-contracting providers), with prospective or retrospective payment approaches often building on existing activity-based or fee-for-service systems, with an associated risk of gaming behaviour by providers. **Potential to reduce growth in medical spending**, with positive or no impact on quality of care. The Dutch model uses a year-of-care bundled payment for selected chronic conditions, showing some process improvements but no effect on clinical outcomes.
- Directed enhanced services (DES) operate beyond the GMS contract and include collaborative delivery through PCNs for nationally specified services. Some evidence indicates lower funding in deprived areas, but there **is no evidence from reviews on health outcomes.**
- Local enhanced services (LES) are a flexible mechanism for commissioning additional primary care services to expand preventive and clinical provision for local population health needs. **Evidence on effectiveness is limited.**

Key findings for incentive, quality and performance frameworks

- Quality and outcomes framework (QOF) provides standardised payments within GMS 'core business', adjusted for disease prevalence and practice list size, for chronic disease management and secondary prevention. Some evidence suggests reduced mortality, improved recording and reduced inequalities, with improvements in quality; however, wider care effects are mixed and **not sustained.**
- Quality assurance and improvement framework replaced QOF in Wales in 2019. **No formal evaluation evidence has been identified.**
- Other quality improvement schemes operate instead of or in addition to QOF. **Evidence of effectiveness or value is very limited.**

Policy and Practice Implications

- Accountable care organisations may hold some promise, building upon primary care network and year of care models, potentially using directed enhanced service mechanisms.
- 'Broad' models of outcome-based contracting may deliver some positive quality and cost outcomes.
- Role reimbursement schemes can enhance workforce, access, quality and delivery of services but attention required to supervision and sustainability.
- Local enhanced services offer flexible mechanism to address identified local population health needs
- Within core GMS, quality improvement schemes lead to very limited benefits, and the quality and outcomes framework improved some elements of quality, although sustained benefits harder to demonstrate.

Research Implications and Evidence Gaps

- Evidence is required on the effective transfer of services to primary and community care and on the impact of different financial models or payment schemes to fund additional services in general practice.
- Evidence is also required on the impacts of developments such as accountable care organisations and outcome-based contracting in the UK.

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Full Description
ACO	Accountable care organisation
ACP	Accountable care partnership
ACS	Accountable care systems
CCG	Clinical commissioning group
DES	Directed enhanced services
GMS	General medical services
GP	General practitioner
ICBs	Integrated care boards
LES	Local enhanced services
MCP	Multispecialty community providers
NHS	National Health Service
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCH	Primary care home
PCN	Primary care network
PMS	Personal medical services
QOF	Quality outcomes framework

Glossary

Accountable care

Is an approach to health and care in which different organisations work collaboratively to improve the health of their local population by joining up services and tackling the causes of ill health (Charles 2018).

Accountable care organisations

Accountable care organisations (ACOs) represent a more formalised model of accountable care. They may be established when NHS providers merge to form a single organisation, or when commissioners use competitive procurement processes to contract with organisations capable of delivering services to a defined population (Charles 2018).

Accountable care partnerships

Accountable care partnerships (ACPs) are alliances of NHS providers that agree to work collaboratively to deliver care, prioritising cooperation rather than competition. These partnerships typically include hospitals, community services, mental health services and general practice, and may also involve social care organisations and independent or third-sector providers (Charles 2018).

Accountable care systems

Accountable care systems (ACSs) have developed from sustainability and transformation plans/partnerships and take a system-level role in planning and commissioning care, as well as providing strategic leadership across their populations. They bring together NHS providers, commissioners and local authorities to work in partnership to improve health and care outcomes. In many cases, multiple ACPs operate within a single ACS footprint (Charles 2018).

Additional capacity funding

Additional capacity funding refers to funding made accessible to all practices in Wales providing general medical services (GMS), administered through Health Boards, based on evidence of additional hours worked. The scheme facilitates match funding of up to 50% for additional posts or additional hours worked by existing post-holders (Welsh Government 2022).

Additional roles reimbursement scheme

A nationwide scheme in England that provides funding to primary care networks (PCNs) to recruit additional staff into specified roles. The scheme set a recruitment target revised to 26,000 staff by 2024 and specifies that funded roles must be additional and not used to fill existing vacancies (Bramwell et al. 2024).

Alliance contracting

Alliance contracting involves an agreement between a group of providers and a commissioner to deliver services, in which all providers jointly share risk and responsibility for delivery (Addicott 2014).

Bundled payments

A payment model in which a single payment covers multiple services across part or all of a patient's care pathway, rather than paying separately for each service. Designed to encourage coordinated care, bundled payments may apply to specific conditions, time periods, or services, and may include outcome-based elements (Jones et al. 2024).

Directed enhanced services

Directed enhanced services (DES) are nationally commissioned enhanced services offered by NHS England to eligible GP contract-holders, providing additional funding for specified services beyond the core GP contract. Examples include out-of-hours provision, minor surgery, and services for individuals removed from practice lists due to acts or threats of violence (Addicott & Ham 2014).

Directed supplementary services

Directed Supplementary Services (DSS) are nationally specified additional services that general practices in Wales may opt to deliver. They are supported by separate funding and are designed to incentivise delivery of specific priority areas beyond core services (BMA Cymru Wales 2025).

Enhanced services

Enhanced services are specialist services provided by general medical services that are not covered under the core GP contract. In Wales, these are referred to as *Enhanced Medical Services* (Welsh Government 2023). In England, they include *Directed Enhanced Services (DES)* and *Local Enhanced Services (LES)* (Addicott & Ham 2014).

Enhanced medical services

In Wales, "enhanced medical services" are provided by GP practices in addition to their core contractual duties under the general medical services contract and are commissioned by local Health Boards. These include nationally-specified DES such as childhood immunisation programmes, influenza vaccination, minor surgery and other supplementary schemes (Welsh Government 2023).

General medical services

General Medical Services is a core GP contract agreed nationally that stipulates the essential services to be provided. These essential services are set in legislation and specify that general practices must provide services during core hours to manage their registered list of patients and temporary residents, including those who are ill with conditions from which recovery is generally expected, terminally ill, or suffering from chronic disease (Addicott & Ham 2014).

Global Sum

The Global Sum is the core capitation-based funding allocated to general practices for delivering essential primary care services. It is calculated based on the number and characteristics of registered patients and forms the main source of income for routine service provision (BMA Cymru Wales 2025).

Local enhanced services

Local enhanced services are enhanced services commissioned locally to address specific population needs and priorities. They support a range of locally agreed activities beyond the core GP contract, with commissioning responsibility delegated to clinical commissioning groups (CCG) on behalf of NHS England from April 2013. Examples include sexual health screening, smoking cessation programmes, blood pressure monitoring, and weight management (Addicott & Ham 2014).

Multispecialty community providers

Multispecialty community providers (MCPs) are positioned as a core organisational form for delivering accountable care within the NHS, aiming to improve outcomes and efficiency through greater integration between primary and secondary care, population-based accountability, and movement towards capitated or outcome-based funding arrangements (NAPC 2017).

Outcome-based contracting (or outcome-based payment mechanisms)

A payment mechanism in which some or all remuneration is contingent on the achievement of pre-specified outcomes rather than the delivery of defined processes or volumes of activity. Outcome-based payment mechanisms may operate within alliance or prime contracting arrangements (Sanderson et al. 2016, 2018).

Primary care home

An approach to strengthening and redesigning primary care that brings together integrated teams across primary, secondary and social care to deliver personalised, proactive and preventive care to a defined population (typically 30,000–50,000 people). It focuses on partnership working, improving population health outcomes, aligning clinical and financial drivers, and providing care to a registered local population (Dougall et al. 2019).

Primary care networks

Groups of neighbouring GP practices working together as a network to deliver services collaboratively for populations typically ranging from 30,000 to 50,000 patients, supported through the Network Contract DES (NHS England 2019a, Checkland et al. 2023b).

Prime contracting (prime provide contracting)

A contracting model in which a commissioner contracts with a single provider who delivers some services directly and coordinates and subcontracts other providers, holding overall accountability for service delivery and performance across a defined service, pathway or population (Addicott 2014).

Quality outcomes framework

The quality and outcomes framework (QOF) was introduced in 2004 as part of the revised General Medical Services contract and is a voluntary incentive scheme for GP practices, under which financial rewards are linked to achievement against specified indicators (Addicott & Ham 2014).

Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework

The Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework (QAIF) was introduced in Wales in 2019 as part of GMS contract reform, replacing the QOF. It set out contractual requirements and associated financial arrangements for quality assurance and quality improvement activities undertaken by general practices. From October 2022, elements of the QAIF, including clinical indicators, were incorporated into the core GMS contract in Wales as part of further contract reform, with quality improvement activity continuing under revised arrangements (British Medical Association 2022).

Risk- and gain-sharing

Risk- and gain-sharing refers to a management approach in which risks and rewards are shared among group members, with gains and losses distributed according to pre-agreed arrangements (Turner et al. 2018).

Year of Care

The Year of Care programme was a three-year national initiative led by Diabetes UK, NHS Diabetes, and The Health Foundation, supported by the Department of Health, exploring how personalised care planning could be implemented at scale for people with long-term conditions in primary care (Ahmad et al. 2014).

1. CONTEXT / BACKGROUND

In Wales, there is a clear policy ambition to strengthen community-based care and to shift services traditionally delivered in hospital settings into primary and community care. This direction is articulated through the *Community by Design* transformation programme, which aims to deliver integrated services closer to home, improve access, support prevention and population health management, and enhance system sustainability (NHS Wales 2026a).

Recent General Medical Services (GMS) contract reform in Wales reinforces this agenda. The 2025–26 GMS contract agreement provides significant new and recurrent investment in general practice and explicitly underpins the *Community by Design* programme (Miles 2025). Early priorities include expanding the range of services delivered in community settings, such as diagnostics and procedures that have historically been provided in secondary care (NHS Wales 2026b). As part of this reform, there is a requirement to design and implement new payment mechanisms and administrative arrangements within the Welsh GMS framework to support service delivery, including decisions about how payments are structured.

General practice funding operates through a core contract supplemented by additional payment mechanisms designed to support the delivery of services beyond essential requirements (BMA Cymru Wales 2025). Under the GMS contract, practices receive baseline funding through the global sum to deliver core (or “unified”) services, with additional funding streams layered on top to incentivise quality improvement and expanded service provision (Welsh Government 2025). These have included national incentive schemes such as the quality outcomes framework (QOF) which link a proportion of practice income to performance against specified quality indicators (Department of Health & Social Care 2024), and more recent quality improvement approaches such as the quality assurance and improvement framework (QAIF) introduced through contract reform in Wales (Welsh Government 2020). Primary care services may also be commissioned through Alternative Provider Medical Services (APMS) contracts, which allow services to be delivered by a wider range of providers under locally negotiated arrangements (Welsh Government 2024).

A further component of this model is funding for supplementary services, referred to in Wales as enhanced medical services, which enable practices to deliver additional activities such as minor surgery, care home services, and vaccination and immunisation programmes where appropriate for their patient population (Welsh Government 2023). These services attract additional payments and may be commissioned nationally as directed services or negotiated locally between health boards and local medical committees. In addition to these service-based payments, workforce-focused funding mechanisms have also been introduced, including additional capacity funding (Welsh Government 2022), which provides funding to support practices in increasing clinical capacity through additional staff or expanded working hours. Taken together, the funding model combines core capitation-based payments, incentive-linked quality payments, and service-specific funding to support flexibility, local responsiveness, and the delivery of care closer to home (BMA Cymru Wales 2025).

Against this backdrop, and to inform ongoing decisions about the design and use of payment mechanisms in Wales, there is value in examining how similar challenges have been approached elsewhere. England provides a particularly relevant comparator, having implemented and evaluated a range of financial and contractual mechanisms to support the delivery of additional services in primary and community settings. These mechanisms have been applied at multiple levels, including practice-level, network-level, and system-wide, and

include enhanced service arrangements, incentive-based payments (Baird et al. 2022), network funding, and large-scale service reform programmes such as the NHS Vanguard programme (Checkland et al. 2022). Evaluations of these approaches typically report on payment and contracting arrangements, alongside outcome data.

It is also important to understand what these payment models are intended to achieve, and whether outcomes and benefits associated with service transfer should be considered alongside the description of payment mechanisms. Outcomes of interest may include service access, patient experience, system flow, and the extent to which pressure on secondary care is reduced. In some cases, the primary objective may be the successful transfer of services rather than demonstrable improvements in patient outcomes or cost savings, recognising that maintaining outcomes while shifting care closer to home may itself represent a policy-relevant benefit.

In addition, international evidence from other health systems describes a range of payment models used to fund additional primary care services such as bundled payments for chronic disease management in the Netherlands (Rosen 2025b). This literature provides insight into how payment mechanisms have been structured, the purposes they were intended to serve, the contexts in which they have been applied, and the outcomes reported in relation to service delivery and system impact.

Together, evidence from England and other health systems internationally provides a useful body of learning to inform Welsh policy. This review therefore focuses on identifying and describing financial payment models used internationally to fund additional services within general practice settings, particularly where these models are intended to improve quality of care and patient outcomes and support the transfer of services from hospital to community settings and examines outcomes and system impacts in relation to these models.

2. RESEARCH QUESTION(S)

To structure the review question and guide eligibility criteria, the SPICE framework was used. SPICE—standing for Setting, Perspective, Intervention, Comparison, and Evaluation (Booth 2006). The table below outlines the scope of the review. A more detailed summary of the methods used for conducting the Rapid Evidence Summary are provided in Section 5.

Review question	
What financial payment models are used to fund additional services in general practice settings, particularly to improve quality of care and patient outcomes, and support the transfer of services from hospital to community settings?	
Setting	General practice settings in the UK delivering services under GMS or APMS. Comparable general practice contractual arrangements in other health systems
Perspective	General practice practitioners and organisations (e.g. GP practices, practice networks), commissioners or payers, and health system or policy stakeholders involved in the design, commissioning, or delivery of additional services within general practice.
Intervention (phenomenon)	Additional financial mechanisms, contractual arrangements, and delivery models used to support services beyond core GMS contracts, including comparable arrangements in other health systems

	<p>Models of care / service delivery structures^a</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accountable care organisations • Multispecialty community providers • Primary care home • Primary care networks • Year of care <p>Contracting and governance models^b</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alliance contracting • Lead (Prime) contracting • Outcome-based contracting <p>Additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms^c</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additional roles reimbursement scheme • Additional capacity funding • Bundled payments • Direct enhanced services • Local enhanced services <p>Incentive, quality, and performance frameworks^d</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality outcomes framework • Quality assurance and improvement framework • Other quality improvement schemes
Comparison	No explicit comparator required. Where reported, comparisons may include usual funding arrangements, alternative payment models, or pre- and post-implementation arrangements.
Evaluation	Outcomes examined or described in relation to payment models, including quality of care, patient outcomes or experience, service access, delivery of additional services, and the transfer of services from hospital to community settings, as well as system-level impacts where reported.
Other Study Considerations	
<p>Exclusions</p> <p>Integrated Neighbourhood Schemes; Integrated Care Systems Accountable Care Systems; Primary and Acute Care Systems Enhanced Health in Care Homes; Urgent and Emergency Care Acute Care Collaborative; Core GMS payment models (e.g. capitation-based global sum) Generic provider remuneration models, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salary • Fee-for-service • Bonus payments • Generic pay-for-performance • Capitation models (e.g. managed care, fund-holding) <p>Top-up payments</p>	

Key: APMS: Alternative Provider Medical Services; GMS: General medical services

Notes

^a Organisational and delivery arrangements that define how primary care services are structured, coordinated, and delivered across providers or populations.

^b Formal contractual arrangements that determine accountability, risk-sharing, and responsibility for the delivery of services between commissioners and providers.

^c Payment mechanisms used to provide funding beyond core primary care contracts to support the delivery of additional services, roles, or activities.

^d Frameworks that link additional payments to specified quality criteria, performance indicators, or assurance requirements

3. SUMMARY OF THE EVIDENCE BASE

3.1. Type and amount of evidence available

This section describes the types and volume of available evidence relating to organisational and system-level models of care, contracting arrangements, payment mechanisms, and incentive frameworks that shape how services beyond core primary care/general practice contracts are organised, funded, and delivered. Some of these models relate directly to financial payment or reimbursement mechanisms, while others provide the wider service delivery, governance, and accountability context within which such financial arrangements operate. Evidence was organised and described across four broad categories: models of care / service delivery structures; contracting and governance models; additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms; and incentive, quality, and performance frameworks.

A summary of the available evidence is presented in a tabular format based on each of the broad categories.

- Models of care / service delivery structures can be found across Table 1 to Table 4
- contracting and governance models across Table 5 to Table 7
- additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms across Table 8 to Table 11 and
- incentive, quality, and performance frameworks across Table 12 to Table 13.

3.1.1. Models of care / service delivery structures

Models of care / service delivery structures comprise organisational and delivery arrangements that define how primary care services are structured, coordinated, and delivered across providers or populations. These include accountable care organisations (ACOs), multispecialty community providers (MCPs), primary care home (PCH); primary care networks (PCNs), and year of care approaches (see Table 1 to Table 4)

Accountable care organisations

Evidence relating to ACOs comprised three reviews (Holm et al. 2024, Kaufman et al. 2019, Wilson et al. 2020) and two organisational reports (NAPC 2017, Shortell et al. 2014).

- A scoping review on the effectiveness of Medicaid ACOs within the US examining impacts on utilisation, quality, health outcomes, and costs, including 32 primary research studies published between 2012 and 2023 (Holm et al. 2024).
- A rapid review (including one systematic review and 59 primary studies published before 2019) examining how ACOs within the US are intended to support the Quadruple Aim—improving patient experience of care, enhancing population health, reducing per-capita healthcare costs, and ensuring positive provider experiences—and examining how and why these intended impacts are achieved through ACOs (Wilson et al. 2020).
- A systematic review of early evidence examining the impacts of ACOs within the US on utilisation, care processes, and outcomes, including 38 primary research studies and four federally funded evaluation reports published between 2010 and 2016 (Kaufman et al. 2019).
- A report by the National Association of Primary Care (2017) describing the development of accountable care-oriented models within the English NHS (MCPs and PCNs), situated within wider efforts to improve integration, population health, and financial accountability.
- A briefing by The King's Fund examining the development of accountable care organisations in the United States and emerging ACO-like approaches in England (Shortell et al. 2014).

Multispecialty community providers

Evidence relating to MCPs included two reviews (Sheaff et al. 2018, Turner et al. 2018), two organisational reports (NHS England 2016b, NHS England 2017a), three evaluation reports (Checkland et al. 2022, Wilson et al. 2019, Wilson et al. 2021).

- A national policy framework setting out the MCP care model, including its scope, organisational features, and intended role within NHS service reform (NHS England 2016b).
- National contractual guidance describing the proposed contractual models for MCPs, including participation, commissioning options, and the use of ACO contracts for partially integrated or fully integrated MCPs (NHS England 2017a).
- A realist synthesis of international evidence examining how MCPs can achieve their desired clinical and patient-reported outcomes searching for evidence up to December 2016 with no lower date limit and including research and evaluations from similar international care models, including ACOs and patient-centred medical homes (Sheaff et al. 2018),
- A realist synthesis of international evidence underpinning MCP and primary care-led integrated care models drawing on a wide range of international evidence, including research studies, evaluations, policy documents, and commentaries identified through searches conducted from January 2000 to December 2016 (Turner et al. 2018).
- A report of locally commissioned evaluations of NHS Vanguard new care models, synthesising findings from 46 local evaluation reports conducted across nine MCP Vanguard sites in England (Wilson et al. 2019; Wilson et al. 2021).
- A national mixed-methods evaluation report of the NHS Vanguard New Care Models Programme examining the implementation, outcomes, and system-level impacts of five Vanguard model types (including MCPs) across England synthesising qualitative case studies, quantitative analyses of service use and outcomes, and findings from locally commissioned evaluations conducted between 2015 and 2020 (Checkland et al. 2022),

Primary care home

Evidence relating to PCH included two organisational reports (Dougall et al 2019, National Association of Primary Care 2015) and one evaluation report (Kumpunen et al. 2017).

- A policy paper setting out the core characteristics and organisational model of the PCH (National Association of Primary Care 2015).
- An evaluation report by Nuffield Trust that uses mixed-methods research to explore the development, implementation and early impact of the PCH model across 13 out of 15 rapid test sites across England (Kumpunen et al. 2017).
- A mixed-methods research report by The King's Fund examining the factors that enabled and hindered the spread of the PCH concept across England (Dougall et al. 2019).

Primary care networks

Evidence relating to PCNs included two organisational reports (Fisher et al. 2019, NHS England 2019a); four evaluation reports (Beech et al. 2023, Checkland et al. 2023b², Swift. 2021 and Swift. 2023) and three primary research publications (Checkland et al. 2023a, Warwick-Giles et al. 2024, Smith et al. 2022).

² One of the evaluation reports Checkland et al. 2023b also generated two derivative primary research publications (Checkland et al. 2023a, Warwick-Giles et al. 2024)

- An evaluation report by the Health Foundation presenting a mixed methods study of primary care networks in socioeconomically deprived areas in England, combining policy analysis, workforce and funding data analysis, and qualitative interviews to assess whether PCN policy and resources adequately address health inequalities (Beech et al. 2023).
- An evaluation report presenting an examination of the development of PCNs as a governance mechanism within primary care in England (Checkland et al. 2023b).³ This evaluation report also has two derivative peer-reviewed publications:
 - A qualitative peer-reviewed publication based on Work package3 of the evaluation that reports case studies of seven PCNs in England examining how PCNs are constituted to meet their goals, the factors influencing their ability to deliver benefits, network and member levels and the emerging outcomes associated with PCN development (Checkland et al. 2023a).
 - A mixed-methods peer-reviewed publication based on WP3 and a re-analysis of WP4 examining how the design and introduction of PCNs influence their ability to tackle health inequalities (Warwick-Giles et al. 2024).
- A Health Foundation briefing analysing the introduction of PCNs in England, outlining policy origins in the NHS Long Term Plan and GP contract reform (Fisher et al. 2019).
- A NHS England guidance document setting out a five-year framework for GP contract reform, establishing PCNs, the Network Contract DES, and workforce expansion through the ARRS (NHS England 2019a).
- Two evaluation reports assessing PCNs progress two and three years post-establishment (Swift 2021, Swift 2023).
- A qualitative study examining early implementation of PCNs, identifying factors helping or hindering progress, how PCNs operate alongside existing collaborations and issues specific to rural networks (Smith et al. 2022).

Year of care

Evidence relating to Year of Care included four organisational reports (Ahmad et al. 2014, Department of Health 2012, NHS England 2016a, NHS England 2017b) and three evaluation reports (Year of Care 2011, Year of Care Partnership 2021, 2024).

- An evaluation report presenting the final findings of the Year of Care pilot programme tested for diabetes at three primary care trust sites (Year of Care 2011).
- A summary report of evaluations bringing together findings from Year of Care implementation projects conducted over the past 10 years (Year of Care Partnership 2021).
- A funding guidance document introducing a potential funding model involving a risk-adjusted capitation budget for providing Year of Care for people living with long-term conditions (Department of Health 2012).
- An implementation guidance handbook for Year of Care capturing learning from early implementation sites (NHS England 2017b).

³ The evaluation had four work packages (WP) involving document analysis and policymaker interviews (WP1), telephone surveys and interviews with PCN leaders and CCG members (WP2), longitudinal case study involving seven PCNs (WP3), and quantitative exploration of network development and outcomes (WP4).

- A personalised care and support planning handbook drawing on learning from the Year of Care programme to support delivery of personalised care and support planning (NHS England 2016a).
- A report commissioned by The Health Foundation contributing to the wider discussion on personalised care and self-management, including the Year of Care programme (Ahmad et al. 2014).
- An evaluation report of the Proactive Care approach applying the Year of Care model, describing implementation across two PCN sites (Carlisle Healthcare and Keswick & Solway), alongside development of the pilot programme and supporting resources (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

3.1.2. Contracting and governance models

Contracting and governance models are formal contractual arrangements that determine accountability, risk-sharing, and responsibility for the delivery of services between commissioners and providers, including alliance contracting, lead (prime) contracting, and outcome-based contracting (see Table 5 to Table 7).

Evidence relating to these three contracting models included two organisational reports (Addicott 2014, NHS England 2014); one evaluation report (Sanderson et al. 2019), two reviews presented across three publications⁴ (Sanderson et al. 2016, 2018; Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

- One literature review drawing on the wider international cross-sectoral literature to describe new contractual models, including **alliance, prime and outcome-based contracting** and their relevance to the English NHS. The review searched for evidence up to 2016 and included primary research studies, review articles and grey literature publications⁵ (Sanderson et al. 2016, 2018).
- A systematic review examining the characteristics and effectiveness of outcome-based payment models in OECD countries. The review searched from January 2000 to October 2016 and included 83 primary research studies, three research reports and two reviews describing 12 outcome-based payment models, primarily from the United States (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).
- An evaluation report examining the use of alliance agreements and a joint venture agreement with the aim to develop lead provider arrangements in the English NHS, together with the associated payment mechanisms, including outcome-based contracting across three in-depth case studies (Sanderson et al. 2019).
- An organisational report by the King's Fund describing the features of prime and alliance contracting and presenting five worked examples of these new models. The report differentiates between prime contractor and its variation prime provider contract (Addicott 2014).
- An organisational report supporting commissioners of health and care services in developing strategic and operational plans, including information on provider and alliance contracting (NHS England 2014).

⁴ The 2018 publication is a revised version of the 2016 Policy Research Unit report, based on the same literature review.

⁵ Reports detailing relevant policy initiatives and unpublished doctoral theses

3.1.3. Additional payments and reimbursement mechanisms

Additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms are payment mechanisms used to provide funding beyond core primary care contracts to support the delivery of additional services, roles, or activities, including additional roles reimbursement scheme (ARRS; England), additional capacity funding (Wales); bundled payments, directed enhanced services (DES) and local enhanced services (LES) (see Table 8 to Table 11).

Additional roles reimbursement scheme

Evidence related to ARRS comprised three organisational reports (MacConnachie 2024 NHS England 2019a, 2019b), one evaluation report (Baird et al. 2022); six primary research publications (Bramwell et al. 2024, Jones et al. 2024, McDermott et al. 2025, Nicodemo et al. 2025, Penfold et al. 2025, Queens Nursing Institute 2019).

- An evaluation report examining the implementation and integration of ARRS roles within PCNs in England, commissioned through the NIHR Policy Research Programme for the Department of Health and Social Care (Baird et al. 2022).
- A policy report analysing the impact, implementation and future development of the ARRS within PCNs in England (MacConnachie 2024).
- A NHS England guidance setting out a five-year framework for GP contract reform, establishing PCNs, the Network Contract DES, and workforce expansion through the ARRS (NHS England 2019a).
- A NHS England guidance document outlining how PCNs should implement and claim reimbursement through ARRSs (NHS England 2019b).
- A qualitative study examining how ARRS is being implemented within seven PCNs across England (Bramwell et al. 2024).
- A qualitative study exploring the challenges and enablers to implementing ARRS across three Integrated Care Systems in England (Jones et al. 2024).
- A qualitative realist evaluation examining how primary care networks and general practices make decisions about employing and deploying ARRS staff (McDermott et al. 2025).
- A quantitative study analysing England-wide quarterly general practice data (March 2018–March 2022) examining factors associated with the presence of ARRS roles and whether these are more common in well-staffed practices or those with GP shortages (Nicodemo et al. 2025).
- A quantitative study examining the commissioning of ARRS direct patient care roles and their association with patient experience and QOF achievement between 2020 and 2023 in England (Penfold et al. 2025).
- A quantitative study conducted by the Queens Nursing Institute examining how the introduction of the ARRS affected the General Practice Nursing workforce in England (Queens Nursing Institute 2019).

Additional capacity funding

Evidence relating to additional capacity funding comprised three organisational reports (Welsh Government 2022, 2025 and Miles 2025); however, no formal evaluation or primary research examining the impact of scheme was identified.

- A Welsh Government operational guidance note outlining the background and processes for the GMS Additional Capacity Funding scheme, setting out the recurrent £4m funding available for 2022/23 (Welsh Government 2022).

- A Welsh Government implementation guidance outlining how new GMS contractual changes should be delivered across Wales and sets out financial arrangements, including continuation of the £4m Additional Capacity Fund into 2024/25 and 2025/26 (Welsh Government 2025).
- A Welsh Government cabinet statement setting out the agreed GMS contract reform for 2024-25, announcing investment in general practice, confirming continuation of the £4m Additional Capacity Funding into 2025-26 and noting that forthcoming reviews will inform future contract negotiations (Miles 2025).

Bundled payments

Evidence relating to bundled payments included four reviews (Rosen 2025b, Simmons et al. 2014, Steenhuis et al. 2020, Struijs et al. 2020) and three organisational reports (Appleby et al. 2012, Lindner and Lorenzoni 2023, Siciliani et al. 2017).

- An organisational report from the King's Fund reviewing the English NHS experience of Payment by Results and international activity-based payment systems, outlining reform options including bundled payments (Appleby et al. 2012).
- An Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Health Working Paper reviewing the implementation and impact of value-based payment models across OECD countries, including episode-based bundled payments, and assessing their effects on spending, quality and care coordination (Lindner and Lorenzoni 2023).
- A literature review describing international examples of contracting and payment innovation in general practice, including the use of bundled payments for chronic disease management in the **Netherlands** (Rosen 2025b).
- A Health Foundation Working Paper analysing competition policy in five European countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Portugal), including the introduction of condition-specific bundled payments in the **Netherlands** for diabetes, COPD and vascular risk (Siciliani et al. 2017).
- A scoping review examining alternative payment arrangements including capitation and global budgets, pay for coordination, shared savings and shared risk, blended capitation, and bundled payments in relation to their international service delivery context, assessing the quality of chronic care associated with these models and disentangling the impact of payment reforms from co-occurring service delivery reforms (Simmons et al. 2014).
- A scoping review examining the key elements involved in the design and implementation of bundled payment contracts from a payer's perspective, searching for evidence up to March 2018 and including 147 articles comprising primary research studies, policy analyses, case studies, evaluation reports, and conceptual or descriptive papers from **OECD countries** (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- An evidence scan of primary research studies, reviews and grey literature providing an overview of bundled payment models in high-income countries, describing key design elements and reported effects on quality of care and medical spending. The scan identified 23 bundled payment initiatives across eight countries, of which 11 had publicly available evaluation (Struijs et al. 2020).

Directed enhanced services

Evidence related to DES comprised three organisational reports (NHS England 2019a, 2019c, 2022) and one primary research publication (L'Esperence 2021).

- An NHS England guidance document setting out a five-year framework for GP contract reform, establishing PCNs, the Network Contract DES, and workforce expansion through the ARRS (NHS England 2019a).
- An NHS England guidance document setting out the 2019/20 Network Contract DES, outlining its purpose, structure, eligibility and sign-up requirements for GP practices and the arrangements for establishing and operating PCNs (NHS England 2019c).
- An NHS England guidance document providing updated information on the 2022/23 Investment and Impact Fund within the National Contract DES, outlining its purpose, structure, domains and indicators, how performance is calculated and paid and how PCNs should monitor achievement (NHS England 2022).
- A quantitative study examining the range of DES funding activity and the equity of service provision across practices by analysing total DES funding per registered patient and assessing whether this voluntary payment mechanism is associated with variations in service provision by social deprivation and ethnic group (L'Esperence 2021).

Local enhanced services

Evidence relating to LES comprised one review (Kumar et al. 2014); one organisational report (NHS England 2023) and one primary research publication (Marks et al. 2011).

- A guidance document outlining how ICBs can commission LES through primary medical contracts (NHS England. 2023).
- A literature review examining whether LES in UK primary care improve clinical and progress outcomes and the factors influencing their impact which identified 14 studies covering 14 LES programmes across 10 disease areas (Kumar et al. 2014).
- A mixed-methods study examining how commissioners use LES and other incentive arrangements for preventive services, their perceived effectiveness and associated advantages and drawbacks (Marks et al. 2011).

3.1.4. Incentive, quality and performance frameworks

Incentive, quality, and performance frameworks: frameworks that link additional payments to specified quality criteria, performance indicators, or assurance requirements, including the quality outcomes framework (QOF), and quality assurance and improvement framework (QAIF) and other quality improvement schemes (QIS) (see Table 12 to Table 13).

Quality outcomes framework

Evidence relating to the QOF comprised nine reviews (Ahmed et al. 2021, Boeckxstaens et al. 2011, Forbes et al. 2016, 2017, Gillam et al. 2012, Ho et al. 2025, Holdroyd et al. 2025, Langdown & Peckham 2013, Srail et al. 2025) and two organisational reports (NHS England 2018; Nuffield Trust. 2014).

- A systematic review examining incentive schemes in UK general practice, including the QOF, focusing on quality of care, GP motivation and behaviour, and inequalities. The review searched for evidence published between 2009 and 2019 and 35 studies met the inclusion criteria (Ahmed et al. 2021).
- A systematic review addressing the equity impacts of the QOF in UK primary care, focusing on changes in achievement of incentivised indicators and inequalities by socioeconomic status, age, sex, and ethnicity. The review searched for evidence published from 2004 to 2009 and included 27 research reports (Boeckxstaens et al. 2011).

- A systematic review examining the impact of the QOF on care for long-term conditions in UK primary care, with attention to clinical processes, intermediate outcomes, and patient-centred aspects of care. Searches covered evidence published from 2004 to 2016 and included three systematic reviews and five primary research studies (Forbes et al. 2017).
- An evidence review commissioned by NHS England examining the impacts of the QOF in England on quality of primary care, emergency admissions, clinical processes and outcomes for long-term conditions, inequalities, and exception reporting⁶. The review searched for reviews published between 2011 to 2015 and for primary research studies published up to 2016 and included 40 research reports (Forbes et al. 2016).
- A systematic review investigating the introduction and withdrawal of the QOF financial incentives in UK primary care, focusing on quality of care, achievement of incentivised indicators, sustainability of effects, and post-withdrawal outcomes. The review searched for evidence published between 2004 and 2024 and included 30 research reports (Ho et al. 2025).
- A systematic review exploring associations between population and organisational characteristics of UK general practices and their performance on the QOF focusing on variation in achievement by workforce, list size, and deprivation. The review searched for evidence published between 2006 and 2022 and included 22 research reports (Srai et al. 2025).
- A systematic review of UK evidence synthesising findings on the effects of the QOF on health outcomes, non-incentivised care, and spillover effects beyond incentivised indicators in primary care. The review searched for evidence published from 2004 to 2012 and included 11 research reports (Langdown & Peckham 2013).
- A systematic review of UK studies assessing the impact of the QOF on the quality of primary medical care, including indicator achievement, clinical processes, inequalities, exception reporting, and professional behaviour. The review searched for evidence published from 2004 to 2011 and included 94 research reports (Gillam et al. 2012).
- An umbrella review synthesising 14 systematic reviews examining the impacts of primary care funding models, including the QOF, on health inequalities, access, continuity, and quality of care across high-income countries. The review searched for evidence published up to 2024 (Holdroyd et al. 2025).
- A national policy-commissioned review assessing the impacts of the QOF in England on quality and standardisation of care, professional workload, personalised care, and system-level outcomes (NHS England. 2018).
- A policy analysis by the Nuffield Trust drawing on published evaluations and reviews to discuss the role of payment mechanisms in the English NHS, including the QOF (Nuffield Trust 2014).

Quality assurance and improvement framework

The evidence relating to the QAIF comprised two organisational reports (Welsh Government 2020; 2021); however, no formal evaluation or primary research examining the impact of the framework was identified.

⁶ Exception reporting is the formal exclusion of specific patients from QOF performance indicators when applying the target would be inappropriate or unfeasible

- Two guidance documents setting out the structure, domains and contractual requirements of the Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework (QAIF) for the 2020/21 and 2021/22 GMS contracts (Welsh Government 2020, 2021).

Other quality improvement schemes

The evidence related to other QIS included one review (Bramwell et al. 2024).

- A literature review synthesising existing evidence on the effects of financially incentivised quality improvement activities in general medical practice on targeted clinical activities, non-targeted activities including potential spillover effects, overall quality of care, and practitioner and organisational outcomes, and identifying additional evidence relevant to NHS England policy development (Bramwell et al. 2024).

3.2. Key findings for models of care / service delivery structures

This section presents a summary of the key findings for accountable care organisations with US Medicare, accountable care-oriented models within the English NHS, multispecialty community providers, primary care networks, and year of care approaches. The findings are organised across the organisational and contractual context described; the identified contract holders; the financial mechanisms and/or incentives explicitly reported within contractual arrangements; the conditions or service areas covered; and the summary of review and/or evaluation findings, including reported evidence limitations.

3.2.1. Accountable care organisations with US Medicare

Organisational and contractual context

- Accountable care organisations are **voluntary networks** of physicians, hospitals, and other healthcare providers that jointly assume responsibility for the care of a defined population (Holm et al. 2024).
- In the US, ACOs were formally implemented in 2012 through Medicare following the Patient Protection and Affordable Care Act (Holm et al. 2024).
- Under this model, provider networks are accountable for coordinating care, improving population health, and addressing rising healthcare costs (Holm et al. 2024).
- The ACO approach has also attracted policy interest internationally, including in England and Canada, as a mechanism to support better management of patients with complex needs (Holm et al. 2024).

Contract holders

- In the US, ACOs are formed by groups of healthcare providers that collectively enter into contractual arrangements with Medicare and other public or private payers (Holm et al. 2024).
- These provider networks assume **accountability for the quality, cost, and outcomes** of care delivered to an agreed patient population over a defined period (Holm et al. 2024).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- ACOs use either **shared savings models**, in which a proportion of achieved savings is paid to providers who meet quality benchmarks, or **full-risk models**, which include financial bonuses or penalties linked to whether benchmarks are met or missed (Matulis & Lloyd 2018 as cited in Holm et al. 2024).
- ACOs are funded through **fee-for-service payments alongside reinvestment of shared savings** (Matulis & Lloyd 2028 as cited in Holm et al 2024).

Conditions covered

- ACOs are responsible for providing care to a defined patient population and are not limited to specific conditions (Holm et al. 2024).
- The model applies to the full range of care delivered to the population for which the ACO has assumed responsibility (Holm et al. 2024).

Summary of review findings

- The scoping review reported mixed evidence on the effects of Medicaid ACOs across healthcare utilisation, quality, health outcomes, and costs (Holm et al 2024).
 - The most consistent findings relate to utilisation, with several studies reporting **increased primary care visits alongside reductions in inpatient admissions** and inpatient stays.
 - Evidence on quality of care and health outcomes was more limited and variable, with many studies reporting small, null, or inconsistent effects.
 - Cost reductions were reported in only a small number of studies and were largely dependent on the length of attribution and the time elapsed since ACO implementation.
- Overall, the rapid review reported mixed evidence on the role of accountable care organisations in relation to the Quadruple Aim (Wilson et al. 2020).
 - Evidence showed positive trends across Quadruple Aim outcomes for ACOs compared with Medicare fee-for-service or group physician fee-for-service models.
 - ACOs were associated with **modest cost savings**, largely attributable to reductions in outpatient expenditure among medically complex patients and reductions in low-value service delivery.
 - ACO models **met the majority of quality measures** and generally performed better than fee-for-service comparators.
 - There was relatively limited evidence regarding the impact of ACOs on provider experience.
- The systematic review reported that evidence regarding the impact of ACOs on care processes and outcomes is mixed (Kaufman et al. 2018)
 - However, efficiency incentives within ACO contracts have not adversely affected common care quality measures or patient satisfaction.
 - Across payer groups, ACO implementation was most consistently associated with **reduced inpatient utilisation and emergency department visits**, and with **improvements in preventive care and chronic disease management**.

Evidence limitations

- Variation across Medicaid and Medicare ACO programmes: The scoping review by Holm et al. 2024 highlighted that Medicaid ACOs face distinct challenges compared with Medicare ACOs⁷, including variation across state Medicaid programmes, which may contribute to heterogeneity in findings.
- Heterogeneity in ACO evidence and study characteristics: The evidence base on ACOs is heterogeneous, with differences between studies in the payer programs, populations, and outcome measures evaluated (Holmes et al. 2024, Kaufman et al. 2019, Wilson et al. 2020).

⁷ Medicare is a federally administered programme primarily for older adults and people with disabilities, whereas Medicaid is a jointly funded federal–state programme for low-income populations, with eligibility and benefits varying across states

3.2.2. Accountable care-oriented models within the English NHS

This sub-section describes accountable care-oriented organisational models that have been discussed or developed within the English NHS. These models focus on population-based responsibility, integration across care settings, and collaboration between multiple provider organisations, and include the PCH, MCPs and accountable care systems (ACS) models.

Primary care home

- The PCH model is described as an organisational approach developed by the National Association of Primary Care. It brings together general practice with community, mental health, social care, and acute services to serve a defined population, typically at **neighbourhood level** (NAPC 2017).
- For further details on PCH see sections 3.1.1 and 3.2.4

Multispecialty community providers

- Multispecialty community providers are positioned as a core organisational form for delivering accountable care within the NHS, aiming to improve outcomes and efficiency through **greater integration between primary and secondary care**, population-based accountability, and movement towards capitated or outcome-based funding arrangements (NAPC 2017).
- For further detail on MCPs see section 3.1.1 and 3.2.3.

Accountable care style arrangements in the UK

- Accountable care organisations are most commonly described in relation to the US, with relevance to the UK often discussed through the concept of accountable care systems (ACSs)^{8,9}, which refer to arrangements in which groups of providers work together to deliver care for defined populations (NAPC 2017).
- In a UK context, ACO-style arrangements are described as mechanisms intended to support **closer alignment between commissioning and provision**, enabling groups of providers to take responsibility for outcomes and budgets for defined populations (NAPC 2017).
- It is also noted that direct transplantation of US ACO models into the NHS would require adaptation, given differences in governance arrangements and the mixed nature of the existing evidence base (NAPC 2017).

⁸ In England, the term ‘*accountable care*’ has been adopted and adapted to describe arrangements intended to support more collaborative working between organisations across the health and care system. These arrangements are commonly referred to as accountable care systems (ACSs), accountable care partnerships (ACPs), and accountable care organisations (ACOs). Although the terms ACP, ACO and ACS are sometimes used interchangeably, they represent distinct models with important differences (see Glossary for further explanation).

⁹ NHS England has renamed ACSs as *integrated care systems* to better reflect the work being undertaken in the ten areas of England operating in this way (Charles 2022).

3.2.3. Multispecialty community providers

This section describes the **NHS Vanguard¹⁰ New Care Models Programme**, with a specific focus on **MCPs** as one of the organisational models developed and implemented within the programme.

- Multispecialty Community Providers were one of the five New Care Models developed as part of the NHS Vanguard programme (NHS England 2016b), alongside Primary and Acute Care Systems (PACS), Enhanced Health in Care Homes (EHCH), Urgent and Emergency Care (UEC), and Acute Care Collaboratives (ACC).
- Fourteen sites agreed to become MCP vanguards, out of which 12 commissioned local evaluations (Wilson et al. 2021).
- The goal of MCP is **integration of primary and community-based care** to include much wider service provision, potentially incorporating hospital care, such as outpatient clinics or some diagnostic services (NHS England 2016b).

Organisational and contractual context

- Within the MCP programme, alliance agreement and ACO contract packages were used as contractual mechanisms through which primary care services could operate as MCPs.
- General Practitioners (GP) participation in MCPs beyond vanguards were expected to be via **ACO contracts** (NHS England 2017a).

Three contractual models were proposed for MCP sites:

- **Virtual MCPs**
In this model, primary care practices entered into an alliance agreement with commissioners and other providers to enable joint working at scale for specific services. Practices remained on existing contracts, such as General Medical Services (GMS), Personal Medical Services (PMS) or Alternative Provider Medical Services (APMS). The alliance agreement did not supersede these contracts, and an ACO contract was not granted (NHS England 2017a).
- **Partially integrated MCPs**
Under this model, an ACO contract was granted by commissioners for services within scope, while core general practice funding continued under GMS or PMS contracts. The contribution of primary care practices to the MCP was set out through an Integration Agreement, linking MCP services with primary medical services (NHS England 2017a).
- **Fully integrated MCPs**
In fully integrated MCPs, an ACO contract was granted covering both core general practice and other services in scope. Existing GMS or PMS contracts could be suspended, and **general practitioners could become owners** of the MCP organisation **and/or salaried** employees. This model required full-service integration under a single contractual arrangement (NHS England 2017a).

Contract holders

- Within MCP arrangements, accountable care organisation–style contracts may be held by a range of organisational forms (NHS England 2017a):

¹⁰ The Vanguard New Care Models Programme ran for three years aiming to develop novel models of care that crossed the boundaries of and connects primary care, community services and hospitals in England (Starling 2018).

- GP-owned organisations, including companies limited by shares or limited liability partnerships, with GPs as salaried employees, partners, or shareholders.
- Corporate joint ventures between GPs and Foundation Trusts.
- Existing NHS bodies, with GPs employed within the organisation.
- Host arrangements, in which one organisation holds the contract on behalf of others, with decisions made through a partner discussion forum that may include GP representation.

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Within MCP arrangements, a range of financial mechanisms and incentives was described as operating through MCP contractual frameworks (NHS England 2017a). These included:
 - Capitation, described as population-based budgets associated with MCP/ACO contractual arrangements, rather than core GMS funding.
 - Risk- and gain-sharing arrangements.
 - Incentive schemes, including the MCP Improvement Payment Scheme, described as replacing Quality Outcomes Framework (QOF) within MCP contractual arrangements.

Conditions covered

- MCPs were described as place-based models of care covering a whole registered population (NHS England 2016b).
- All conditions could be covered, dependent on services offered within each MCP (NHS England 2016b).

Summary of evaluation findings

- The national evaluation reported **modest reductions in the rate of growth of emergency admissions** in Vanguard sites compared with non-Vanguard sites, findings were reported at programme level and not disaggregated by Vanguard type, including MCPs (Checkland et al. 2022).
- Local MCP evaluations focused primarily on implementation and service change, with variable and limited quantitative outcome analysis, often constrained by data availability and lack of comparators (Wilson et al. 2019 2021).

Summary of review findings

- The realist synthesis by Sheaff et al. (2018) found **limited evidence** relating specifically to MCPs and therefore developed a revised logic model drawing on international evidence from comparable initiatives.
 - The revised logic model suggested that **multidisciplinary team working** was key for improved care organisation and safer care provision for people with long-term conditions.
 - **Better care coordination and increased involvement from patients**, alongside improved information systems were seen as key in improving care provision.
- The realist synthesis by Turner et al. (2018) developed multiple programme theories based on available evidence on how MCPs work and lead to better outcomes.
 - These programme theories suggest that the involvement of different healthcare professionals and service users (patients), individuals' understanding of the benefits of working together and having a trusting relationship, and training for integrated

working can lead to better behaviour outcomes for both service users and service providers.

Evidence limitations

- Quality and consistency of evidence: Local MCP evaluations were variable in quality, which limited the ability to assess outcomes consistently across sites (Checkland et al. 2022, Turner et al. 2018, Wilson et al. 2019, Wilson et al. 2021).
- Focus of reported findings: Many reported findings were process-focused, with outcomes often examined in relation to specific components (for example, individual incentives or capitation arrangements) rather than whole MCP contractual configurations (Turner et al. 2018).
- Attribution challenges: Attribution of outcomes to contractual forms or payment models was challenging, reflecting the complexity, heterogeneity, and evolving nature of MCP initiatives (Turner et al. 2018).
 - The realist synthesis by Turner et al. (2018) found **limited empirical evidence**, including for how contractual models and payment systems work.
 - The evidence included small-scale evaluations often comprising of less generalisable study designs, such as before and after studies with no control group, or case studies.
 - This led to moderate level of uncertainty in the conclusions of the review.
- Policy and implementation constraints: Evidence on ACO-style models in England is constrained by limited implementation and **subsequent policy retreat**¹¹, with accountable care replaced by looser integrated care arrangements (Checkland et al. 2022).
- Challenges to scale-up and sustainability: Evaluation of the Vanguard MCP pilots found that, while some elements of service change were retained or locally spread, there was no systematic wider implementation as originally envisaged and no simple or standardised approaches that could be readily scaled (Checkland et al. 2022).

3.2.4. Primary care home

The National Association of Primary Care (NAPC) developed the concept of PCH in 2015 to strengthen and redesign primary care (NAPC 2015, Dougall et al. 2019). A fully developed PCH brings together local services to encourage new ways of working based on the needs of its registered population, typically serving **between 30,000 and 50,000 people** (NAPC 2015, Kumpunen et al. 2017). Rather than a prototype for implementation, PCH is intended as a conceptual framework for aligning the aims and working practices of healthcare professional (Kumpunen et al. 2017). Although originally developed to support the design of MCP models, more recent reports categorise it as a type of PCN and note that it also informed the development of PCN policy (Dougall et al. 2019).

Organisational and contractual context

- The key to PCH is **multidisciplinary care delivery by creating partnerships** across primary, secondary, mental health, community, social care and voluntary sectors (Kumpunen et al. 2017, NAPC 2015).

¹¹ Policy retreat refers to the scaling back or abandonment of a policy approach following initial implementation or exploration.

- A PCH may employ 100-150 staff members and supports the cross-skilling and development of the wider multi-disciplinary team, including nurses, pharmacists and allied health professional (NAPC 2015).
- Staff distribution and service provision are based on **population needs assessment**. Providers may work together through networked arrangements but are not necessarily co-located. Networked arrangements may be supported through improved management of existing estates, use of technology and integrated IT systems (NAPC 2015).
- The development of Primary Care Homes and other multispecialty workforce models was facilitated by the NHS (Primary Care) Act 1997, which introduced greater flexibility in service delivery through mechanisms such as Personal Medical Services Plus arrangements (NAPC 2015).
- One proposed contractual model was an ACO, intended to support integrated working through a unified budget and shared outcome measure (NAPC 2015).
- Other **organisational arrangements depend** on the level of risk and reward clinicians are willing to take. These include:
 - 'Medical chambers' arrangements that provide shared equity for members while retaining existing contractual arrangements (NAPC 2015)
 - Company formation in which clinicians become Directors, such as a community interest company or a non-profit company limited by guarantee operating under social enterprise principles (NAPC 2015).
- **Initial investment may be required for management support, coaching and clinical supervision during implementation.** Workforce transformation funding and Health Education England training funds may support workforce development and placements within Primary Care Home settings (NAPC 2015).

Contract holders

- Depending on contractual arrangements, GPs and specialists may share equity stakes, with opportunities for other providers to participate (NAPC 2015).
- Initially the commissioner would be NHS England, although this arrangement may change over time (NAPC 2015).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

Blended payment mechanisms were suggested for Primary Care Homes, which included a mixture of approaches:

- Population-based capitated budgets calculated on the basis of the registered list and population needs, and responsibilities agreed within the contract. A recurring management allowance may also be required within the capitated budget to ensure business readiness and ongoing organisational stability (NAPC 2015).
- Risk sharing arrangements either with NHS England or full risk acceptance with appropriate insurance or via partnering with a commercial organisation (NAPC 2015).
- A risk premium intended to reduce the financial impact of high-cost patients. Under this approach, a maximum cost is levied against the Primary Care Home budget for any registered person's care commissioned from external service (NAPC 2015).
- Equity stakes or incentive payments for salaried or sub-contracted staff to support the delivery of high standards of care (NAPC 2015).
- Creation of a legal entity in which stakeholders are jointly incentivised (NAPC 2015).

- Responsibility for the capitated budget may be layered in stages, potentially progressing towards full financial responsibility for the registered population (NAPC 2015).

Conditions covered

- Focus on the health needs of specified subgroups of the local population, including complex or frail older people (Kumpunen et al. 2017)
- Provision of urgent, same-day and pre-bookable appointments for individuals on the registered list (NAPC 2015).
- Recognition that unregistered individuals living in the local area may also require care provision (NAPC 2015).
- Focus on groups of people sharing characteristics within a population rather than a specific disease (Kumpunen et al. 2017).
- Provision of proactive and preventive care for both healthy and chronically ill people (Kumpunen et al. 2017).

Summary of evaluation findings

- Improved multidisciplinary working and service development: Evaluation of 13 of 15 rapid test sites reported improved multidisciplinary team working and development of new care pathways and services (Kumpunen et al. 2017).
- **Improved service delivery** in selected sites: Three rapid test sites reported time savings in general practice through increased self-referrals to musculoskeletal services, improved prevention and population health approaches, and reduced hospital admissions associated with an acute response team for older people with frailty (Kumpunen et al. 2017).
- **Cost savings reported but cost-effectiveness uncertain:** Estimated savings ranged from £0.1 to £0.27 million, although cost-effectiveness could not be determined due to lack of systematic monitoring (Kumpunen et al. 2017).
- Improved patient satisfaction: Case study research across three sites reported improved patient satisfaction at one site serving approximately 44,000 patients (Dougall et al. 2019).
- Perceived improvements in patient health and wellbeing: Healthcare professionals reported improvements in patient health and wellbeing at one case study site (Dougall et al. 2019).

Evidence limitations

- No evidence reviews identified: No systematic or evidence reviews were identified for Primary Care Homes.
- Limited evidence base: Only two research and evaluation reports were identified in the grey literature, primarily describing the development and expansion of Primary Care Homes in England rather than their impact.
- Limited ability to demonstrate impact: Evidence suggests that demonstrating impact is constrained by staff capacity and existing information systems and processes for data collection (Dougall et al. 2019, Kumpunen et al. 2017).
- Outcome measures not aligned with service changes: Existing outcome measures do not always capture the impact of changes in service provision (Dougall et al. 2019).

3.2.5. Primary care networks

Primary care networks are groups of neighbouring GP practices working together as a network to deliver services collaboratively for populations typically ranging from 30,000 to 50,000 patients, supported through the **Network Contract DES** (NHS England 2019a, Checkland et al. 2023b).

Organisational and contractual context

- Primary care networks operate through the Network Contract DES (See section 3.4.5), which provides the contractual framework for collaborative working and delivery of specified services (Fisher et al. 2019, NHS England 2019a).
- The Network Contract DES also allows for Supplementary Network Services, enabling CCGs and PCNs to develop additional locally agreed services supported by local resources (NHS England 2019a).
- Each network must have a named accountable Clinical Director and a **Network Agreement** setting out the collaboration between its members (NHS England 2019a).
- The Network Agreement must be signed by all constituent GP practices and sets out how practices share responsibilities, resources and governance arrangements (NHS England 2019a).
- The Network Agreement also provides the formal basis for collaboration with other community-based organisations, including community health providers and other services involved in integrated care (NHS England 2019a).
- Practices participating in PCNs retain their individual core GP contracts and organisational independence while **collaborating to deliver network services** (Fisher et al 2019).

Contract holders

- Individual GP practices hold the core GP contract and participate collectively in the Network Contract DES through their PCN (Fisher et al. 2019; NHS England 2019).
- The Network Contract DES (for further detail see section 3.4.5) sets out the contractual arrangements for PCNs, including national service specifications and financial entitlements associated with network delivery (NHS England 2019).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Core network funding based on registered patient population to support establishment and operation of PCN. (NHS England 2019a).
- The ARRS (for further detail see section 3.4.1) provides reimbursement for employment of additional multidisciplinary staff, including roles such as clinical pharmacists, social prescribing link workers, physician associates, first contact physiotherapists and community paramedics (NHS England 2019a).
- **Payments linked to delivery of national network service specifications**, introduced progressively to support delivery of NHS Long Term Plan priorities (NHS England 2019a).
- Funding for network clinical leadership, reimbursing time for a clinical director responsible for coordinating network activities (NHS England 2019a).
- Network Participation Payments paid to GP practices participating in a PCN, linked to meeting the requirements of the Network Contract DES and collaborative delivery of network services (NHS England 2019a).

- Investment and Impact Fund performance payments linked to achievement of specified quality, access and service delivery indicators across PCN populations (NHS England 2019a).
- *Conditions covered*
- Primary care network service specifications focus on areas where networks can contribute to the 'triple aim' of improving health outcomes, improving quality of care for people with multiple conditions, and supporting sustainability of the NHS (NHS England 2019a).
- Areas highlighted include prevention and early detection of conditions such as stroke, heart disease and cancer, structured medication reviews, personalised care and support planning, care for care home residents, and reducing avoidable hospital admissions (NHS England 2019a).

Summary of evaluation findings

- **Improved collaboration** between practices: PCN improved collaboration across local general practices and other services (Beech et al. 2023).
- Sustainability: PCNs **may increase sustainability** by bringing in new funding and developing more efficient working practices, such as shared back-office support across services, or improved managerial capacities (Smith et al. 2022).
- Quality of prescribing: Employment of pharmacists through ARRS did not significantly improve quality of prescribing (Checkland et al. 2023b).
- Provision of additional services: three years on, PCNs reported to deliver additional services and developing services tailored to their populations needs (Swift 2023).
- Raised profile: Two years on from implementation of PCNs, their public profile increased, partially due to the vaccination programme during the COVID-19 pandemic (Swift 2021). PCNs were also found to increase awareness on health inequalities (Swift 2021).
- Management and leadership support: Effective management and leadership were highlighted as important, especially where there were no pre-existing relationships or tensions between partners (Checkland et al. 2023a, 2023b, Smith et al. 2022). Additional funding and managerial support were recommended (Checkland et al. 2023a, 2023b).
- Workforce improvements: Progress and early success in hiring was reported (Swift 2021, 2023, Smith et al. 2022).
- Increased workload: While improvements in workforce recruitment were reported, evidence from multiple evaluations suggest that **increased workload** through the development of PCNs was a challenge (Swift 2021, 2023, Smith et al. 2022).
- Workforce in deprived areas: PCNs in deprived areas had fewer full-time equivalent staff relative to population need than PCNs in more affluent areas (Beech et al. 2023). Administrative, nursing and non-ARRS staff was more likely to be recruited to less deprived areas, although **trends show that recruitment of ARRS staff and GPs improved in deprived areas** over time (Checkland et al. 2023b).
- Funding inequalities in deprived areas: Funding was reported not to be reflective of the additional work required in deprived areas and PCN-adjusted population funding was recommended (Beech et al. 2023). However, trends were identified that funding allocation improved over time (Warwick-Giles et al. 2024).

- **Compatibility with rural areas:** PCNs were considered less suited to rural contexts, where recruitment is more difficult, practices are geographically dispersed, and travel distances and limited public transport can reduce accessibility for patients and staff (Smith et al. 2022).
- **Pre-existing relationships:** Existing relationships between PCN partners could facilitate collaboration and recruitment (Checkland et al. 2023a, 2023b, Smith et al. 2022), while a lack of shared history could exacerbate inequalities (Checkland et al. 2023b). In some cases, prior relationships also created tensions where **power imbalances** between practices were perceived (Smith et al. 2022).
- **Inadequate infrastructure:** The Network Contract DES does not provide funding for estates or IT, leaving infrastructure insufficient to support increased staff and workload. Gaps were also reported in training and development, with many PCNs highlighting the need for additional funding and infrastructure support (Swift 2023).

Evidence limitations

- **Lack of evidence on effectiveness:** Multiple reports identified a lack of evidence on the effectiveness of PCNs (Checkland et al. 2023b, Smith et al. 2022), with limited data availability noted as a contributing reason (Checkland et al. 2023b).
- **Lack of long-term evaluations:** Most evaluations followed services for only 2–3 years due to project time limits, limiting evidence on longer-term outcomes and meaning findings may change over time (Checkland et al. 2023a, 2023b).
- **COVID-19 pandemic:** Most evaluations were conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic which may influence their findings (Checkland et al. 2023b).
- **Lack of evidence in rural areas:** Further research is needed in both urban and rural areas, particularly as existing evidence suggests the PCN model may be less suited to rural services (Smith et al. 2022).

3.2.6. Year of care

This sub-section describes the Year of Care programme and the Proactive Care approach which used the Year of Care model.

- **The Year of Care programme** was a three-year national initiative led by Diabetes UK, NHS Diabetes, and The Health Foundation, supported by the Department of Health, exploring how personalised care planning could be implemented at scale for people with long-term conditions in primary care (Ahmad et al. 2014).
 - A pilot of the Year of Care approach was conducted across three primary care trusts in England, Tower Hamlets, Calderdale and Kirklees, and North of Tyne, between 2006 and 2009, focusing on diabetes, with the initial evaluation undertaken from 2008 to 2011 (Year of Care 2011).
 - Learning from the Year of Care Programme, which extensively tested models of personalised care and support planning, informed the development of the House of Care as a whole-system framework¹²
- Proactive care is a primary care-led, personalised and preventative approach that uses **coordinated multidisciplinary working and care planning** to anticipate and address the needs of people living with long-term conditions and frailty.

¹² The House of Care is a whole-system framework for delivering personalised care and support planning for people with long-term conditions (Coulter et al. 2023, NHS England 2016a).

- A proactive care pilot used the Year of Care approach to personalised care and support planning for people with long-term conditions and frailty in two Primary Care Networks, Carlisle Healthcare and Keswick & Solway (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

Organisational and contractual context

The Department of Health (2012) proposed a **risk-adjusted capitation budget** to support the Year of Care funding model and outlined a **range of possible contracting** approaches for local implementation.

- Informal network approach with profit share: Providers collaborate without a formal contract, with participation (for example general practice participation) incentivised through shared savings from cost reductions (Department of Health 2012).
- Accountable Care Organisation: A payment and delivery model linking provider reimbursement to quality metrics and reductions in total population costs for a defined population, using mechanisms such as capitation, fee-for-service, or shared-savings arrangements (Department of Health 2012).
- Integrated care hubs (prime provider model): A central pathway organisation holds the budget for pathway-wide quality and productivity, with accountability for specialist provision outside hospitals, performance management of primary care, and the subcontracting and quality assurance of hospital services (Department of Health 2012).
- Alliance contracting: A collaborative contracting approach in which partners work openly and share risks, responsibilities, and goals, with an emphasis on achieving shared outcomes rather than organisational self-interest, in contrast to traditional contracting models (Department of Health 2012).
- Single integrated care organisation: Formal structural integration of care services into a single organisation, for example combining NHS Trust or Foundation Trust acute and community services with local authority management and shared budgets for intermediate and social care (Department of Health 2012).
- Joint venture with joint management board of providers: Multiple providers operate in partnership under a Joint Management Board, combining resources and/or expertise while retaining individual contractual obligations, with joint governance and accountability arrangements to achieve agreed outcomes and share risks and rewards (Department of Health 2012).
- Principal provider (contractor) and subcontracting model: A principal provider holds the main contract and subcontracts elements of care delivery to other providers within a care pathway (Department of Health 2012).
- Capitated outcomes-based contracts: A payment model in which providers receive a fixed amount per person, with additional incentives linked to the achievement of agreed outcomes (Department of Health 2012)

The proactive care pilot was implemented within existing primary care and community service structures, with organisational arrangements shaped by local workforce capacity, funding mechanisms, and multidisciplinary team configuration.

- Carlisle Healthcare PCN: Entered the pilot with an established co-located multi-disciplinary team and prior experience of the Year of Care approach, enabling delivery through a dedicated home-visiting team funded in part through unfilled GP vacancies (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

- Keswick & Solway PCN: Implemented the pilot using roles funded primarily through the ARRS, which shaped team composition and limited access to medical, nursing, and long-term condition expertise at the outset (Year of Care Partnership 2024).
- Funding considerations: The availability and flexibility of funding were identified as key factors influencing implementation and sustainability of proactive care models (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

Contract holders

- Year of care: Dependent on the contracting approach adopted locally, including GP practices, provider networks, lead (prime) providers, or integrated organisations, reflecting the flexibility of the Year of Care funding and contracting model (Department of Health 2012)
- Proactive care: The report describes delivery of the Proactive Care approach through PCNs and partner organisations, aligned with existing primary care and community service structures (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Risk adjusted capitation budget: A proposed funding model for Year of Care based on population risk profiling and grouping people according to need, with funding aligned to people's needs rather than individual conditions.
 - Set out as a concept based on risk profiling GP practice populations and needs-based classification using assessment systems (Department of Health 2012).
 - Implementation guidance described defining the patient cohort and included services and using historical costs to inform the value of a capitated budget (NHS England 2017b).
- Local enhanced service funding: Pilot sites involved in the initial implementation (2006–2009) funded additional Year of Care activities through enhanced services arrangements, including LES and Local Improvement Schemes (Year of Care 2011).
- 'Packages of care' payment approach (Tower Hamlets): The Tower Hamlets pilot site developed a locally tailored payment approach described as 'packages of care', structured around care planning and levels of complexity. Different payment levels were aggregated at network level and used to support individual practitioners or additional support services¹³ (Year of Care 2011).
- Integration into core contracts: The Year of Care project aimed for structured care planning to become routine practice and for this approach to be incorporated into future GMS contracts (Year of Care 2011).
- Additional local payments: The Year of Care final report identified the need for local additional payments to support implementation, including set-up costs, data monitoring and improvement, stratification by complexity and risk, and enhanced support for people requiring higher levels of care (Year of Care 2011).
- Use of existing funding mechanisms (Proactive care): The Proactive care pilot did not introduce a dedicated funding or payment model and was delivered using existing primary care and community funding arrangements, with workforce configuration and service delivery shaped by available funding, including reliance on schemes such as the ARRS (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

¹³ The final pilot report noted that, at the time of publication, national guidance on payment for GP provider activities was not yet clear (Year of Care 2011)

Conditions covered

- Following initial piloting in diabetes (Year of Care 2011), the Year of Care approach was subsequently applied across a wider **range of long-term conditions** (Year of Care Partnership 2021) and population groups, including¹⁴:
 - Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
 - Musculoskeletal conditions
 - Cardiovascular disease
 - Dementia
 - Frailty
 - People living with multiple long-term conditions (multimorbidity)
- Proactive care, which uses the Year of Care approach as its basis, focuses on people living with multiple long-term conditions and frailty (Year of Care Partnership 2024).

Summary of evaluation findings

From the pilot evaluation and subsequent summary reports, the following findings were reported (Year of Care 2011, NHS England 2016a):

- Adoption and reach: Care planning was adopted in the majority of pilot sites, with between 73% and 97% of practices implementing the approach; 76% of people with type II diabetes received at least one care planning consultation, and over 1,000 healthcare professionals were trained (NHS England 2016a, Year of Care 2011).
- Impact on people with long-term conditions: Improved experience of care, greater involvement in decision-making, better understanding of conditions, recognition of self-management, tailored support to build confidence and skills, **improved continuity** of care, and better access to information and local support (NHS England 2016a, Year of Care 2011)
- Impact on healthcare professionals: More satisfying consultations, improved knowledge and skills, **higher job satisfaction, enhanced teamwork**, better organisation of care, and more appropriate use of medicines (NHS England 2016a, Year of Care 2011).
- Impact on practices and systems: **Improved productivity**, with care planning described as **cost-neutral or cost-saving in some settings**, alongside improved organisation and teamwork (NHS England 2016a, Year of Care 2011).
- Impact on commissioners: Greater **value for money**, commissioning informed by clinical and population-level data, services better aligned with patient and clinician needs, improved understanding of pathways and costs, and alignment with wider system priorities, including quality improvement and reduced acute care use.
- Clinical outcomes: Changes in **clinical indicators were not immediate**, with evidence suggesting that two to three years may be required before measurable changes are observed.

The Year of Care Partnership (2021) report described further condition-specific benefits associated with the application of the Year of Care approach:

- Diabetes: Sustained positive changes in diabetes clinical data at pilot sites.
- Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: Lower rates of emergency admissions and A&E attendance in a pilot which incorporated keyworkers and self-management activities.

¹⁴ Primary research evidence on the application of the Year of Care approach to progressive neurological conditions, including progressive supranuclear palsy, Parkinson's disease, multiple sclerosis, and motor neurone disease, is reported by Peel et al. (2012).

- Musculoskeletal conditions: Most participants (97%) reported feeling able to talk about their issues during care planning consultations and all participants reported that they would recommend care planning to others. Reductions in opioid prescribing for pain management were reported, alongside increased use of self-management approaches.
- Frailty: Falls discussions were incorporated into care planning with older adults, leading to identification of more people at risk of falling. Participating practices reported changes to service offers, including medication review, self-management support, and strength and balance classes.
- Dementia: Practitioners reported access to dementia-specific toolkits and training that had not previously been available.

Evidence limitations

The Year of Care 2011 evaluation and NHS England 2016a summary both acknowledge that:

- The programme was implemented and evaluated in real-world settings.
- There was no formal comparator or experimental design.
- Evidence is largely descriptive and formative.

Further methodological considerations have been raised in later critical analyses¹⁵.

3.3. Key findings for contracting and governance models

This section describes new contracting and governance models, including alliance contracting, prime contracting, and outcome-based contracting. The findings are organised across the organisational and contractual context described; the identified contract holders; the financial mechanisms and/or incentives explicitly reported within contractual arrangements; the conditions or service areas covered; and the summary of review and/or evaluation findings, including reported evidence limitations.

3.3.1. Alliance contracting

Alliance contracting¹⁶ involves an agreement between a group of providers and a commissioner to deliver services, in which all providers **jointly share risk and responsibility for delivery** (Addicott 2014).

Organisational and contractual context

- Alliance contracting relies heavily on relational norms (e.g. trust, flexibility, reciprocity) because contracts cannot be fully specified in advance. Success factors are largely **relational, including leadership culture**, senior management support and dedicated resource (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- A pre-alliance phase is required to agree contractual terms and build trust between partners through dedicated joint activity (Sanderson et al. 2018).
 - **Upfront costs may be high** during this period (Addicott 2014, Sanderson et al. 2018), and overestimation of costs involved with the contractual model at the start has also been reported (Sanderson et al. 2018).
 - Some contractual and operational issues are only resolved during implementation (Sanderson et al. 2018)

¹⁵ Subsequent critical analysis highlighted methodological limitations of the Year of Care evidence base, including lack of comparative testing, reliance on self-reported outcomes, attribution challenges, and uncertainty regarding unintended consequences and value for money (Roberts et al. 2019).

¹⁶ Alliance contracting is also referred to as 'alliance partnering', 'pure alliance', or 'project alliance' (Sanderson et al. 2018).

- Alliance contracting may develop a dedicated governance structure, including a co-located integrated project management team or a leadership board with agreed membership and terms of reference (Addicott 2014, Sanderson et al. 2016).
- Opportunistic behaviours, such as gaming¹⁷ which may include cherry picking easier clients, may be reduced via alliance contracting due to its reliance on relationship based contractual agreements and risk sharing (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- While alliance contracting can strengthen partnership working and shared risk management, collective risk-sharing may create challenges for public sector accountability, integrity and transparency, particularly where parties are held accountable for failures they did not directly cause. Clear allocation of specific risks to designated partners may mitigate this issue (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Procurement could be a potential issue with alliance contracting, as partners may not be chosen through a competitive process (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Certain type of alliance contracting may not be compatible with Standard NHS contracts, such as where multiple alliance partners work under a single commissioning contract (Addicott 2014, NHS England 2014). However, key elements of alliance contracting could be adapted with the use of a single or multiple NHS Standard Contracts (NHS England 2014).

Contract holders

- In alliance contracting, a single contract may involve multiple providers with shared accountability (Sanderson et al. 2018).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Alliance-style arrangements involve risk-sharing and aligned financial incentives between partners (Addicott 2014).
- Existing payment mechanisms may create misaligned incentives and require alignment across providers to support integration (Addicott 2014).
- Case study sites used multiple financial mechanisms, including multilateral risk-sharing agreements, outcome-based payments and capitated models (Sanderson et al. 2019).

Conditions covered

- Specific populations including older people or disease groups, such as mental health (Addicott 2014).
- In three case studies, populations and conditions covered were older people (aged over 65 years) and people with severe mental health problems (Sanderson et al. 2019).
- Alliance models are typically framed at pathway or system level rather than around single discrete conditions (Sanderson et al. 2018, NHS England 2014).

Summary of evaluation findings

- Evidence remains limited. A literature review identifies potential benefits (e.g. improved integration, innovation and stronger inter-organisational relationships), but direct **empirical evidence of improved quality or cost outcomes is weak** (Sanderson et al. 2018).

¹⁷ Gaming refers to strategic behaviour by providers to maximise financial or performance gains without necessarily improving underlying service quality (Sanderson et al. 2018).

- UK case studies show mixed findings: Financial incentives and risk-sharing mechanisms had limited influence in some contexts, and pre-existing provider tensions were not resolved by contractual form alone (Sanderson et al. 2019).
- Service reconfiguration and cost impact: Of three UK case studies, only one progressed to service reconfiguration and reported cost savings (Sanderson et al. 2019).

Evidence limitations

- Theoretical and empirical limitations: Alliance contracting is undertheorized and lacks empirical evidence¹⁸ (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Measurement and attribution challenges: The limited evidence may reflect difficulties in attributing and measuring outcomes. The complexity of alliance arrangements and the influence of contextual factors make evaluation challenging (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Cross-sector evidence base: The evidence presented by Sanderson et al. (2018) mainly comes from sectors other than health, such as construction, public services, aerospace, defence, information and communication technology.

3.3.2. Lead (prime) contracting

In prime contracting, a commissioner awards a single contract to a lead provider, also known as prime contractor or integrator, who manages/sub-contracts other providers to deliver specific services (Addicott 2014, Sanderson et al. 2018). Prime contracting also has a variation called Prime provider contract (Addicott 2014). In this variation the prime provider not only sub-contracts other providers to perform services but also delivers some or all care specified in the prime contract (Addicott 2014).

Organisational and contractual context

- Prime contracting shares some relational features with alliance contracting, including reliance on trust, flexibility, solidarity and reciprocity (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Contract negotiating can be time and resource intensive (Sanderson et al. 2016, 2018).
- Although ex ante transaction costs (costs arising from negotiating, specifying and drafting contracts) may be reduced for commissioners, through delegation of sub-contracting to the prime contractor, overall **contractual complexity** remains (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Prime contracting may involve dedicated governance arrangements, including co-located integrated project management teams (Sanderson et al. 2016).
- Delegation to a prime contractor may create principal–agent risks, including opportunistic behaviour within the supply chain (e.g. cherry picking), particularly where oversight is reduced. These risks may be mitigated through regulatory oversight and carefully aligned incentive structures (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Delegation to a prime contractor may **reduce commissioner oversight** and expertise, limiting the ability to monitor performance. This may be mitigated if commissioners retain a stewardship role and build contractual safeguards allowing intervention (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Selection of prime contractors may not require full competitive procurement, although commissioners must ensure appropriate assurance that a suitable lead provider has been chosen (Sanderson et al. 2018).

¹⁸ Empirical evidence refers to systematically collected and analysed data evaluating the real-world impact of alliance contracting on outcomes, costs, or service performance.

- Delivery risks may shift from commissioners to prime contractors, who manage these through sub-contracting and supply chain accountability (Addicott 2014, Sanderson et al. 2016). However, relationships may become strained if risks and costs are disproportionately passed to sub-contractors (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Prime contracting may be compatible with NHS Standard Contracts, particularly as processes related to sub-contracting was strengthened in 2014/2015 to support new models of contracting (NHS England 2014).

Contract holders

- A commissioner awards a single contract to a prime contractor, who coordinates and subcontracts other providers with overall accountability for service delivery (Addicott 2014, Sanderson et al. 2018).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Prime contracting may involve a capitated budget for a defined population or care pathway, with a proportion contingent on achieving specified outcomes. Concerns exist regarding how such models manage comorbidities or activity outside the defined scope (Addicott 2014).
- Financial and performance risks may transfer from commissioners to the prime contractor, who manages these through supply chain contracts (Sanderson et al. 2016, 2018).
- **Incentive alignment across the supply chain is critical**, as misaligned payment mechanisms may undermine intended behavioural effects (Addicott 2014, Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Evidence suggests that inconsistencies exist in payment mechanisms and incentivisation that needs to be aligned across providers (Addicott 2014).
- NHS payment rules allow local variations to support outcome-linked and capitated contracting models (NHS England 2014).

Conditions covered

- Prime contracting has been applied to **defined populations and care pathways**, including older people and service areas such as cancer and musculoskeletal care (Addicott 2014).

Summary of evaluation findings

- Evidence remains limited: A literature review identifies potential benefits (e.g. improved service coordination and sharing of good practice), but direct **empirical evidence of improved quality or cost outcomes is weak** (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Hierarchical supply chain arrangements may generate relational tensions (Sanderson et al. 2018).

Evidence limitations

- Empirical limitations: Prime contracting is supported by limited empirical evidence, and robust evaluations of its impact on cost and quality are scarce (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Cross-sector evidence: The evidence presented by Sanderson et al. (2018) mainly comes from sectors other than health, such as construction, public services, aerospace, defence, information and communication technology.

3.3.3. Outcome-based contracting

Outcome-based contracting (or outcome-based payment models) refers to a payment mechanism in which some or all remuneration is contingent on the achievement of pre-specified outcomes **rather than the delivery of defined processes, activities, or volumes** of care. Such arrangements may operate within broader contractual models, including alliance or prime contracting (Sanderson et al. 2016, 2018).

Organisational and contractual context

- Negotiating and specifying outcomes in outcome-based contracts may require significant **upfront effort, including investment** in information systems, data collection, analysis, and monitoring arrangements (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- These ex-ante transaction costs (e.g. negotiating, specifying and drafting contracts) may be substantial, although potential efficiency gains over time may offset these costs (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Evidence on processes for setting outcomes is limited; however, the literature suggests **outcome specification should be iterative** and may extend beyond the initial contract specification stage (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Outcome-based contracts involve significant transfer of financial risk to providers, as **payment is contingent on achieving specified outcomes** (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- Outcome-based contracts may create risks of opportunism and gaming (e.g. cherry-picking easier clients), including where outcome-based payment mechanisms are combined with prime contracting arrangements (Sanderson et al. 2018).
- A systematic review of outcome-based payment models identifies two broad categories: **narrow and broad models** (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).
 - Narrow outcome-based payment models: Narrow models provide explicit financial incentives for objectively measured quality improvement. Providers receive bonuses or penalties depending on achieved outcomes. These models typically target a single provider type and/or specific clinical areas. These include primary care physicians and hospitals or conditions, such as myocardial infarction. The UK's QOF is considered a narrow model of outcome-based payment (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).
 - Broad outcome-based payment models: Broad models combine global budgets and shared savings arrangements with explicit financial incentives linked to quality indicator scores. They generally involve multidisciplinary provider groups delivering care across a defined population (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

Contract holders

- Contract holders vary depending on the model design.
 - In narrow models, the contract holder is typically a single provider type, such as primary care physicians or hospitals.
 - In broad models, the contract holder is more likely to be a multidisciplinary provider group responsible for delivering care across a defined population (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Narrow models use explicit financial incentives linked to performance on predefined quality indicators. These typically involve **bonuses and/or penalties** based on achievement of outcome (and often process) targets. Payments are usually additive to existing reimbursement structures rather than replacing them (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

- Broad models combine global budgets or population-based payments with shared savings and/or shared risk arrangements. These models also include explicit financial incentives tied to quality indicator performance, meaning that payment is contingent both on **cost control and achievement of quality outcome** (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

Conditions covered

- Outcome-based payment models may apply either to **specific clinical conditions or to defined populations**. Some models operate at the level of whole general practice populations (e.g. all patients registered within a practice), while others focus on specific diseases or procedure (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).
- Clinical areas in which outcome-based payment models have been implemented include acute myocardial infarction, heart failure, pneumonia, hip and knee replacement, stroke, diabetes, and coronary artery bypass graft surgery (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

Summary of review findings

- **Narrow models: mixed** quality impact and limited cost evidence: Out of nine narrow models evaluated, five demonstrated positive changes in quality, while the remainder showed mixed or negative effects. Healthcare utilisation and costs were seen unfavourable or were not measured (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).
- **Broad models: positive quality and cost outcomes:** Although only three broad models were evaluated, these demonstrated positive effects on both quality of care and healthcare costs (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

Evidence limitations

- Limited number of evaluated models: Of the 12 outcome-based payment models identified in the systematic review by Vlaanderen et al. (2019), only four had more than three studies investigating their effectiveness. Sanderson et al. (2018) similarly highlight the limited empirical evidence available in this area.
- Limited ability to draw firm cause-and-effect conclusions. Most studies compare results before and after implementation or between different groups, rather than using more rigorous trial designs. This means it is difficult to be certain that observed changes were caused by the payment model itself (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).
- Restrictive definition may limit generalisability: The definition of outcome-based payment models used by Vlaanderen et al. (2019) applies a specific threshold for linking payment to outcomes, which may exclude other relevant models and affect the generalisability of the findings.
- Predominance of USA-based evidence. Most of the identified evidence originates from the USA, which may limit interpretation and transferability of findings to other healthcare systems operating under different funding and regulatory arrangements (Vlaanderen et al. 2019).

3.4. Key findings for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms

This section presents a summary of the key findings for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms including the ARRS (England) additional capacity funding (Wales), bundled payments (OECD countries), bundled payments (Netherlands), DES and LES. The key findings are organised across the organisational and contractual context described; the identified contract holders; the financial mechanisms and/or incentives explicitly reported within contractual arrangements; the conditions or service areas covered;

and the summary of review and/or evaluation findings, including reported evidence limitations.

3.4.1. Additional roles reimbursement scheme (England)

A nationwide scheme in England that provides funding to PCNs to recruit additional staff into specified roles.

Organisational context

- The ARRS operates **through the Network Contract DES** to support expansion of the primary care workforce within PCNs (Fisher et al. 2019, NHS England 2019a).
- The scheme enables PCNs to recruit additional staff working across member practices, supporting the development of multidisciplinary teams operating at network level to deliver services across the PCN population (Fisher et al. 2019, NHS England 2019a).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- The scheme provides **reimbursement funding linked to the employment of specified additional roles within PCNs** (NHS England 2019a).
- Supported roles include clinical pharmacists (from 2019), social prescribing link workers (from 2019), physician associates (from 2020), first contact physiotherapists (from 2020) and community paramedics (from 2021) (Fisher et al. 2019, NHS England 2019b).
- The ARRS forms part of the planned expansion of the primary care workforce, supporting recruitment of 26,000 additional staff across PCNs by 2023/24 (Baird et al. 2022, NHS England 2019b).
- Reimburses **70% of salary costs for most** additional roles, and 100% for social prescribing link workers, with the remaining costs met by member practices within the PCN (Fisher et al. 2019).
- National investment in ARRS was planned to increase from £110 million in 2019/20 to £891 million by 2023/24 to support expansion of the primary care workforce (Fisher et al. 2019).

Conditions covered

- The scheme is not linked to specific clinical conditions but aims to increase workforce capacity within primary care networks by funding additional multidisciplinary roles to support the delivery of general practice and primary care services.

Summary of evaluation findings

The independent evaluation (Baird et al. 2022) that examined the implementation and integration of selected ARRS-funded roles within PCNs in England (pharmacists, first contact physiotherapists, social prescribing link workers and paramedics) reported the following:

- Accelerated workforce expansion: ARRS enabled rapid recruitment of additional multidisciplinary staff into general practice (Baird et al. 2022).
- Development of multidisciplinary teams: ARRS roles contributed to the growth of multidisciplinary teams, though effective team based working across PCNs was often limited by weak PCN identity and inconsistent integration structures (Baird et al. 2022).
- Variable implementation: Integration of roles varied across PCNs due to differences in organisational readiness and local implementation approaches (Baird et al. 2022).

- Role clarity challenges: Limited clarity about the purpose and deployment of some roles affected how staff were integrated across practices (Baird et al. 2022).
- Operational barriers: Implementation challenges included limited leadership and organisational development capacity, variable supervision arrangements, and infrastructure constraints such as estate space (Baird et al. 2022).
- Sustainability concerns: Uncertainty about longer-term funding and workforce planning raised questions about sustainability of ARRS roles (Baird et al. 2022).
- Staff wellbeing challenges: ARRS staff frequently experienced reduced autonomy, belonging and contribution due to fragmented deployment, inconsistent induction and limited support (Baird et al. 2022).
- Overall conclusion: **Many PCNs lacked the organisational capacity, shared strategy and support structures required to fully realise the intended benefits** of ARRS roles (Baird et al. 2022).

The policy report that examined progress and experiences of the ARRS within PCN in England (MacConnachie 2024) reported the following:

- Workforce expansion: ARRS has supported rapid recruitment of additional patient-facing staff in primary care, contributing to increased appointment capacity and diversification of the workforce (MacConnachie 2024).
- **Improved access and service delivery:** Additional roles have enabled new services and clinics in primary care and allowed patients to access different practitioners directly without GP referral (MacConnachie 2024).
- Support for multidisciplinary and integrated cross-sector working: ARRS roles have supported development of multidisciplinary teams and collaboration across services, including links with community and voluntary sector organisations (MacConnachie 2024).
- Operational and infrastructure challenges: Implementation has been constrained by workforce shortages, limited estate space, digital infrastructure limitations, and the need for supervision and training (MacConnachie 2024).
- System-wide workforce pressures: Recruiting staff into ARRS roles may increase competition for workforce across other parts of the health system (MacConnachie 2024).
- **Future sustainability considerations:** Continued success will require greater flexibility in role selection, improved support for supervision and training, infrastructure investment, and longer-term funding commitments (MacConnachie 2024).

The findings from the three qualitative studies (Bramwell et al. 2024, Jones et al. 2024, McDermott et al. 2025) reported the following:

- Variation in implementation and perceived benefits: Implementation of the ARRS varied across PCNs, with broadly similar experiences and shared challenges, while the scheme broadened expertise and services in primary care and staff generally felt valued (Bramwell et al. 2024; Jones et al. 2024).
- Contextual and operational constraints: The introduction of ARRS roles was affected by wider contextual factors and operational constraints (Bramwell et al. 2024, Jones et al. 2024).
- Perceived benefits of ARRS roles: ARRS roles were perceived to broaden expertise and services in primary care, improve patient care, and offer potential GP time savings (Bramwell et al. 2024, Jones et al. 2024).

- Impact on GP workload and access to care: The scheme did not consistently reduce GP workload but enhanced access to different types of care (Jones et al. 2024).
- Implementation challenges and contextual constraints: Implementation of ARRS roles was affected by wider contextual and operational constraints, including COVID-19 disruption, infrastructure and space limitations, scheme inflexibility, and the need for staff supervision and support (Bramwell et al. 2024).
- Role clarity, supervision and workforce integration: Further challenges included unclear role boundaries, **variable supervision arrangements**, workforce integration constraints, and limited career progression opportunities for some roles (Jones et al. 2024).

The three quantitative studies (Nicodemo et al. 2024, Penfold et al. 2025, Queens Nursing Institute 2019) reported the following:

- Workforce distribution and practice characteristics: ARRS roles were **more commonly commissioned or present in larger practices, areas with greater GP supply** and in practices with more nurses or overseas-trained GPs (Penfold et al. 2025, Nicodemo et al. 2024).
- Variation in workforce deployment: Evidence on workforce distribution was mixed, with some evidence suggesting ARRS roles were commissioned in areas with higher GP supply, while other findings suggest deployment in practices with GP shortages (Penfold et al. 2025, Nicodemo et al. 2024).
- PCN organisational structure and role commissioning: Single-practice PCNs commissioned more direct patient care ARRS roles per population than multi-practice PCNs (Penfold et al. 2025).
- Patient experience outcomes: ARRS roles were associated with small improvements in aspects of patient experience, including satisfaction and perceived access (Penfold et al. 2025, Nicodemo et al. 2024).
- Prescribing patterns: ARRS staffing was associated with lower overall prescribing and slightly lower prescribing for mental health conditions (Nicodemo et al. 2024).
- Quality of care indicators: No association was identified between ARRS staffing and QOF achievement (Penfold et al. 2025).
- Workforce change and professional concerns: The introduction of ARRS roles represented a significant workforce change, marked by limited consultation with general practice nurses and concerns about inequitable pay and development opportunities (Queens Nursing Institute 2019).
- Impact on nursing workload and responsibilities: Redistributing work to ARRS roles affected nursing workload and professional responsibilities, particularly when roles worked outside scope or required additional follow-up and supervision (Queens Nursing Institute 2019).
- Drivers of implementation: Implementation of ARRS roles appeared to be driven by funding availability rather than workforce demand (Queens Nursing Institute 2019).

Evidence limitations

- The evidence base is largely observational and further evaluation of the scheme is warranted (Penfold et al. 2025, Nicodemo et al. 2024).

3.4.2. Additional capacity funding (Wales)

Additional capacity funding refers to funding made accessible to all practices in Wales providing GMS, administered through Health Boards, based on evidence of additional hours worked

Organisational and contractual context

- The Additional Capacity Fund is a Welsh Government funding initiative introduced as part of wider General Medical Services (GMS) contractual arrangements to support increased workforce capacity in general practice (Welsh Government 2022, Welsh Government 2025).
- The scheme provides recurrent funding to enable practices to increase workforce capacity through additional posts or additional working hours (Welsh Government 2022, Miles 2025).

Contract holders

- Funding is made available **within General Medical Services** and accessible to practices **via health boards** (Welsh Government 2022).
- GP practices apply for funding through local health board processes in line with Welsh Government operational guidance (Welsh Government 2022).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- The scheme operates on a **50% match-funding basis**, with Welsh Government funding covering up to half of the cost of additional workforce capacity and practices providing the remaining contribution (Welsh Government 2022).
- Funding can be used to support recruitment of additional staff or additional hours worked by existing staff (Welsh Government 2022).
- Welsh Government committed £4 million of recurrent funding for the scheme, with continuation of this funding confirmed for 2025-26 (Welsh Government 2022; Miles 2025).

Conditions covered

- The scheme is not linked to specific clinical conditions but is intended to increase workforce capacity within general practice to support delivery of primary care services (Welsh Government 2022).

Summary of evaluation findings

- No formal evaluation or primary research examining the impact of the framework was identified.

3.4.3. Bundled payments (OECD countries)

The following sub-section summarises evidence on bundled payment contracts reported primarily in OECD countries. It draws on a scoping review by Steenhuis et al. (2020), an international evidence scan of bundled payment initiatives by Struijs et al. (2020), and policy analyses by Appleby et al. (2012) and Lindner and Lorenzoni (2023). Evidence relating specifically to the Netherlands is reported separately in the section 3.4.4.

Organisational and contractual context

- Bundled payment models have been introduced in a number of health systems as part of wider payment reforms aimed at improving care coordination across providers within defined care pathways and supporting cost containment (Appleby et al. 2012, Lindner & Lorenzoni 2023).
- Bundled payment models were described as being designed and implemented across pre-contractual and post-contractual procurement phases (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Bundled payments were implemented as **episode-based models for acute or elective care activities, or as periodic models for people with chronic conditions** (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Variations in design and implementation were described across studies operating under different national regulatory frameworks and single-payer or multi-payer health systems (Steenhuis et al. 2020, Appleby et al. 2012).
- The design of bundled payment contracts varies substantially across countries, including differences in the scope of services covered, contracting arrangements and mechanisms for allocating financial risk between payers and providers (Lindner & Lorenzoni 2023).

Contract holders

- The **definition of the contracting party was identified as a key design feature** of bundled payment models (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Bundled payment contracts were held by:
 - a **single provider** organisation (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
 - **multiple collaborating provider** organisations (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
 - a new or existing third legal entity acting as the contracting party (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- In some models, the contracting party received and distributed bundled payments among providers (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Some arrangements involved no direct interaction between the payer and subcontracted provider organisations (Steenhuis et al. 2020).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Bundled payment models included shared-savings and shared-risk arrangements between payers and providers (Appleby et al. 2012, Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Bundled payment models used either:
 - A prospective payment strategy, where the bundled payment is determined in advance of care delivery (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
 - A retrospective payment strategy, where payments are calculated after care delivery based on submitted claims (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Allocation of payments and savings or losses among providers was specified within bundled payment arrangements (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Fee-for-service payments continued alongside bundled payments in several models.
- Bundled payment models **often build on existing activity-based or fee-for-service** payment systems, which are used as the basis for setting bundle prices or budgets (Appleby et al. 2012).
- Conflicting financial incentives within provider organisations were described, including those arising from:
 - Employer–employee contracts (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
 - Gain-sharing arrangements (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Potential behavioural responses to financial incentives

- Gaming was described as behaviour in which a care professional deliberately influences care processes to maximise personal financial benefit within a bundled payment arrangement (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- **Gaming could occur** before patient inclusion (e.g. “cherry picking” or “lemon dropping”) or during care delivery and monitoring (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Across studies, gaming was identified as a potential barrier to effective implementation of bundled payment contracts (Steenhuis et al. 2020).

Conditions covered

- Bundled payments have been implemented across a range of clinical areas including both episodic care activities and chronic disease management programmes (Steenhuis et al. 2020, Struijs et al. 2020).
 - Hip replacement
 - Knee replacement
 - Diabetes
 - Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Summary of evaluation findings

- Bundled payment initiatives have stimulated **improved care coordination, enhanced the usefulness of collected quality data, and strengthened clinical engagement and relationships between payers and providers.**

Summary of review findings

An international evidence scan identified 23 bundled payment initiatives across eight countries, of which 11 had publicly available evaluations (Struijs et al. 2020).

- Mixed evidence on spending: Twenty of the 32 studies assessing expenditure reported modest savings or reductions in spending growth, while two studies reported increased spending in the early years of implementation (Struijs et al. 2020).
- Mixed evidence on quality of care: Eighteen of the 32 studies assessing quality reported improvements in quality of care, while the remaining studies reported no measurable difference (Struijs et al. 2020).
- Overall conclusion: The evidence suggests bundled payment models have the **potential to reduce medical spending growth while having either a positive impact or no impact on quality of care** (Struijs et al. 2020).

Evidence limitations

- Limited availability of evaluation evidence: Of the 23 bundled payment initiatives identified across eight countries, only 11 had publicly available evaluations assessing their effects (Struijs et al. 2020).
- Heterogeneous evidence base: The included literature comprised a mix of primary research studies, policy analyses, case studies, evaluation reports, and conceptual or descriptive papers, limiting comparability across studies (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Evidence on the effectiveness of bundled payment models remains limited and heterogeneous across health systems, with variation in implementation, evaluation methods and outcome measures (Lindner & Lorenzoni 2023).
- Inconsistent reporting of contract design: Key bundled payment design elements such as risk sharing arrangements, payment distribution mechanisms, and governance structures were not consistently described across studies (Steenhuis et al. 2020).

- Limited empirical evaluation: Many papers focused on describing bundled payment contracts rather than evaluating their implementation or effects (Steenhuis et al. 2020).
- Geographical concentration of evidence: Approximately two-thirds of included studies were conducted in the United States, which may limit generalisability to other health system contexts (Steenhuis et al. 2020).

3.4.4. Bundled payments (Netherlands)

This sub-section summarises an international example of contracting for general practice services in the **Netherlands** (Appleby et al. 2012, Rosen 2025b, Siciliani et al. 2017, Simmons et al. 2024). It describes the use of bundled payment contracts between health insurance companies and care groups and summarises findings on their design, implementation and impact. Evaluations of the Netherlands' year-of-care bundled payment initiative have been considered particularly relevant for comparison with the NHS due to similarities in health system organisation (Appleby et al. 2012).

Organisational and contractual context

- Bundled payment contracts for chronic disease management in the Netherlands operate through contractual arrangements between health insurance companies and large operational support organisations, known as care groups, which organise care across participating providers (Rosen 2025b).
- The model was introduced nationally in 2010 as part of national policy to improve the quality of chronic disease management in general practice and support integrated care pathways between general practitioners and other providers (Siciliani et al. 2017, Rosen 2025b).
- The **Dutch model uses a year-of-care bundled payment covering the management of selected chronic conditions**, rather than payments for individual services (de Bakker et al. 2012 as cited in Appleby et al. 2012).

Contract holders

- Contracts are held by Dutch health insurance companies and care groups, with care groups negotiating bundled payment prices directly with insurers (Rosen 2025b, Siciliani et al. 2017).
- Payments are made to care groups, which distribute payments to participating providers delivering care within the bundle and support GP practices and other providers to meet contract requirements, including providing operational and organisational development support (Siciliani et al. 2017, Rosen 2025b).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- The contracts use bundled payments for specified chronic disease services (Rosen 2025b).
- Payments are made to care groups, which distribute payments to participating providers and support GP practices and other providers to meet contract requirements, including providing operational and organisational development support (Siciliani et al. 2017, Rosen 2025b).

Conditions covered

- Chronic disease management programmes including diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and vascular risk management (Siciliani et al. 2017, Rosen 2025b).
- Frail elderly patients with complex care needs (Simmon et al. 2024).

Summary of evaluation findings

- An evaluation conducted one year after the introduction of bundled payments reported (Struijs et al. 2010 as cited in Rosen 2025b).
 - Perceived improvements in care processes, including more standardised care delivery, improved training, better use of electronic medical records, increased attendance at multidisciplinary team meetings, improved protocol compliance, and greater transparency of care (Rosen 2025b).
 - **No significant changes were observed at one year in clinical outcomes or service use** (Rosen 2025b).
 - The price paid per care bundle varied substantially between insurers (Rosen 2025b).
- A further economic evaluation (Karimi et al. 2021 as cited in Rosen 2025b) conducted five years after implementation reported:
 - Increases in overall costs for patients included in bundled payments, particularly for those with multimorbidity, alongside improvements in care processes and intermediate outcomes (Rosen 2025b).
 - Caregivers perceived the care group's market power as distorting their relationship and highlighted potential GP conflicts of interest arising from ownership of the care group while also providing care (Rosen 2025b).
 - Some also reported reduced patient choice due to practices using preferred providers, such as dieticians (Rosen 2025b).
- Administrative and implementation challenges: Implementation has been associated with administrative burden and variation in costs and performance between care groups (Struijs & Baan 2011, de Bakker et al. 2012 as cited in Appleby et al. 2012).
- Concerns have been raised regarding market power of larger care groups, potential double funding through existing payment systems, and the risk of selecting less complex patients (Struijs & Baan 2011, de Bakker et al. 2012 as cited in Appleby et al. 2012).
- Market structure and financial risks: Concerns have been raised regarding the market power of larger care groups, potential double funding through existing payment systems, and the risk of selecting less complex patients (Struijs & Baan 2011, de Bakker et al. 2012 as cited in Appleby et al. 2012).
- Improvements in care coordination: Early evaluations reported improvements in provider collaboration, care coordination and compliance with clinical guidelines (Struijs & Baan 2011, de Bakker et al. 2012 as cited in Appleby et al. 2012)
- Limited patient-level impact: Early evaluations also reported that these changes were not yet visible to patients (Struijs & Baan 2011, de Bakker et al. 2012 as cited in Appleby et al. 2012).

Summary of review findings

- A scoping review by Simmons et al. (2024) identified one study examining bundled payment models among frail elderly patients with complex care needs.
 - Person-centred care: Improvements in person-centredness. (Hoedemakers et al. 2022 as cited in Simmons et al. 2024).
 - Autonomy and treatment burden: Reduced autonomy and increased medication burden (Hoedemakers et al. 2022 as cited in Simmons et al. 2024).

Evidence limitations

- Limited evaluation evidence: The available evidence is based on a small number of evaluations of the Dutch bundled payment model.
- Short-term evaluation periods: Some evaluations were conducted relatively early after implementation, limiting the ability to assess longer-term effects.
- Variation in implementation: Differences in how care groups organise and deliver services may limit the comparability of findings across settings.
- Limited patient-reported outcomes: Much of the available evaluation evidence focuses on care processes and organisational changes rather than patient-reported outcomes or experiences.

3.4.5. Directed enhanced services

Directed enhanced services are nationally commissioned enhanced services offered by NHS England to eligible GP contract-holders, providing additional funding for specified services beyond the core GP contract.

Historically, DES were introduced as part of the 2004 GMS contract as nationally offered schemes enabling practices to deliver additional services beyond the core contract (Rosen 2025a). More recently, the introduction of the Network Contract DES through the 2019 GP contract reforms expanded this mechanism to **support collaborative delivery of services through PCNs** (NHS England 2019a; NHS England 2019b).

Organisational and contractual context

- Directed enhanced services provide contractual arrangements through which general practices deliver services beyond the core GP contract and form part of the national GP contract framework for delivering specified additional services (NHS England 2019a; NHS England 2019b).
- Participation in DES Services is voluntary, with practices choosing whether to deliver the specified services in return for associated payments (NHS England 2019a).
- The Network Contract DES is a specific DES introduced through the 2019 GP contract reforms, providing the contractual framework through which groups of general practices collaborate as PCNs to deliver nationally specified services (NHS England 2019a; NHS England 2019b; NHS England 2022).

Contract holders

- Payments are linked to delivery of specified services beyond the core GP contract (NHS England 2019a; NHS England 2019b).
- Under the Network Contract DES, funding supports delivery of **nationally specified** services through Primary Care Networks (NHS England 2019a; NHS England 2022).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Payments are linked to delivery of specified services beyond the core contract.
- Payments may also be linked to achievement of defined indicators or service specifications.

Conditions covered

- Historically, DES have supported delivery of a range of nationally specified services through general practice, including vaccination and immunisation programmes, cervical screening, extended access services and health checks for people with learning disabilities (L'Esperance et al. 2021).

- Some schemes have also focused on management of long-term conditions and proactive care for patients at higher risk of hospital admission (L'Esperance et al. 2021).
- More recently, the Network Contract DES specifies nationally defined service areas delivered through Primary Care Networks, including structured medication reviews, enhanced health in care homes, anticipatory care, personalised care and cardiovascular disease prevention (NHS England 2022).
- The Network Contract DES specifies nationally defined service areas delivered through PCNs, including structured medication reviews, enhanced health in care homes, anticipatory care, personalised care and cardiovascular disease prevention (NHS England 2022).

Summary of evaluations

- A cross-sectional analysis of English general practices found that participation in DES was widespread for some schemes (particularly immunisation programmes) but varied across different DES schemes (L'Esperance et al. 2021).
- The study also reported variation in DES funding and service provision across practices, with slightly **lower funding observed in more socioeconomically deprived areas** and higher funding associated with practices with greater clinical workforce capacity (L'Esperance et al. 2021).

Evidence limitations

- **No evidence reviews** identified: No systematic or evidence reviews were identified for DES.
- Limited outcome evaluation: The identified study examined participation and funding patterns rather than evaluating impacts on patient outcomes, service quality or system costs (L'Esperance et al. 2021)

3.4.6. Local enhanced services

Local enhanced services are enhanced services commissioned locally to address specific population needs and priorities.

Organisational and contractual context

- Local enhanced services are locally commissioned services outside national general practice contracts that support provision of services beyond core GMS requirements and may be arranged using the GP contract or the NHS Standard Contract (NHS England 2023).
- Local enhanced services are **commissioned by local NHS organisations to address locally identified population health needs** and priorities (NHS England 2023).
- The design, scope and delivery of LES varies between local areas depending on local commissioning priorities and service needs (NHS England 2023, Kumar et al. 2014).

Contract holders

- Local enhanced services are commissioned by local NHS organisations, with arrangements made either through GP contracts or through NHS Standard Contracts depending on the commissioning approach (NHS England 2023).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Payments for LES are linked to the delivery of specified services or activities defined within local service specifications (Kumar et al. 2014).

- Payment structures, service specifications and incentive arrangements vary across local areas depending on commissioning priorities (NHS England 2023, Kumar et al. 2014)
- Some LES include start-up or retainer payments and may also include closing fees as part of their financial structure (Kumar et al. 2014).

Conditions covered

- Local enhanced services are not linked to nationally specified clinical conditions but are used to commission services addressing locally identified population health needs (NHS England 2023, Kumar et al. 2014).
- Examples of services commissioned through LES include sexual health services, smoking cessation support, alcohol interventions, cardiovascular disease prevention, weight management, diabetes-related services and substance misuse services (Marks et al. 2011).
- Local enhanced services have also been used to commission vaccination programmes including HPV catch-up vaccination, MMR catch-up vaccination, hepatitis vaccinations and additional influenza vaccinations for at-risk groups (Marks et al. 2011).
- The specific services commissioned through LES vary across local areas depending on population health needs and commissioning priorities (NHS England 2023, Kumar et al. 2014).

Summary of evaluation findings

- Early evaluations found that LES were **used by commissioners to expand preventive and clinical services** delivered within general practice (Marks et al. 2011).
- Local enhanced services were commonly used to incentivise delivery of preventive services within primary care settings (Marks et al. 2011).
- The range and structure of services commissioned through LES varied across local areas, reflecting local commissioning priorities and service gaps (Marks et al. 2011).

Summary of review findings

- Reviews suggest that LES provide a **flexible mechanism for commissioning additional primary care services** tailored to local population needs (Kumar et al. 2014).
- However, the locally determined nature of LES results in substantial variation in service design, delivery and funding arrangements across areas (Kumar et al. 2014).

Evidence limitations

- Evidence on the effectiveness of LES is limited and often based on locally conducted evaluations or descriptive studies (Kumar et al. 2014).
- Variation in service design and delivery across local areas makes comparison of outcomes and impacts difficult (Kumar et al. 2014).

3.5. Key findings for incentive, quality and performance frameworks

This section presents a summary of the key findings for incentive, quality and performance frameworks including QOF, QAIF and other quality improvement schemes. The key findings are organised across the organisational and contractual context described; the identified contract holders; the financial mechanisms and/or incentives explicitly reported within contractual arrangements; the conditions or service areas covered; and the summary of review and/or evaluation findings, including reported evidence limitations.

3.5.1. Quality & outcomes framework (QOF)

The QOF is a voluntary pay-for-performance scheme introduced in 2004 as part of wider GP contract reforms, originally comprising 147 indicators across four domains. The QOF forms a defined element of GMS and personal medical services (PMS) funding with over 95% of practices participating (NHS England 2018).

Organisational and contractual context

- The QOF was introduced to improve quality in primary care, **standardise chronic disease management and secondary prevention**, and reduce avoidable hospital admissions. It also contributed to changes in practice organisation, use of information systems and multidisciplinary team roles within general practice (Nuffield Trust 2014).
- The QOF operates as a national quality performance framework for general practice, using a structured set of indicators that measure clinical care, public health activities and organisational processes (Nuffield Trust 2014).
- Indicators are evidence-based and developed through a process led by the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE), which recommends indicators for inclusion in the framework (NHS England 2018).
- GP practices earn points for completing specified activities or achieving defined outcomes within QOF indicators. **Payments are adjusted for disease prevalence and practice list size** and are made through in-year aspiration payments followed by a year-end balancing payment (NHS England 2018).
- Indicator achievement is calculated after excluding patients recorded as meeting defined exception reporting criteria (NHS England 2018).
- Following successive reforms, the QOF framework comprises 77 indicators focused mainly on clinical and public health areas and accounts for around 8% of GP practice income, equating to approximately £685–£691 million per year, compared with 15–20% of income at its introduction (NHS England 2018).
- In England, GP funding combines weighted capitation (the largest share) with QOF pay-for-performance payments, enhanced services funding, dispensing payments and some fee-for-service elements (Nuffield Trust 2014).

Contract holders

- The QOF forms **part of the GMS and PMS contractual framework** and under which contracts are held by general practices rather than individual GPs (Nuffield Trust 2014). (Nuffield Trust 2014).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Under the QOF, practices earn points for achieving specified clinical and organisational indicators, with payments linked to the proportion of eligible patients for whom the indicator is achieved (NHS England 2018).
- Indicators typically include lower and upper achievement thresholds, with no points awarded below the lower threshold and full points awarded once the upper threshold is reached (NHS England 2018).
- QOF payments are partly made through in-year “aspiration payments”, with a balancing payment made at the end of the financial year based on final achievement levels (NHS England 2018).
- Achievement calculations generally exclude patients meeting defined exception reporting criteria from the indicator denominator (NHS England 2018).

- The framework includes a maximum number of available points (559 in 2018/2019), with the value of each point adjusted according to practice list size and disease prevalence (NHS England 2018).
- Payments are made to practices rather than individual clinicians, meaning financial benefits primarily accrue to GP partners rather than salaried staff (Nuffield Trust 2014).

Conditions covered

- QOF indicators cover a wide range of clinical areas including cardiovascular and metabolic conditions, respiratory diseases, mental health conditions, preventive health indicators (such as smoking status and obesity) and care for people with learning disabilities (NHS England 2018).

Summary of review findings

- **Reduced mortality, improved recording and inequalities, but mixed wider care effects:** QOF was associated with reduced mortality in some studies, improved data recording and reductions in sociodemographic inequalities. However, it was also linked to decreased quality in non-incentivised activities, poorer patient experience associated with 'tick-box' approaches, increased pressure to meet non-specific targets, mixed evidence regarding competition, and limited evidence on non-financial incentives in primary care (Ahmed et al. 2021).
- Overall quality improved, with variation in benefit across groups: QOF introduction was associated with **overall improvements in quality scores**; older patients and males generally benefited more, total QOF scores did not vary by ethnicity, and small residual differences related to deprivation persisted, favouring less deprived groups; none of the included studies assessed equity in access to care (Boeckxstaens et al. 2011).
- Modest early improvements in incentivised care with limited wider impact: QOF was associated with modest improvements in incentivised activities, particularly in the early years, and may have encouraged practices to maintain performance. It also improved computerisation and recording of care delivery, and supported nurse-led multidisciplinary management of chronic disease. However, indicators showed **limited alignment with wider primary care priorities** and may have diverted attention from patients with complex needs, with no clear population level benefit and health outcome effects described as modest and short lived (Forbes et al. 2016).
- Modest early gains with **narrowing deprivation gaps but reduced continuity:** Quality of care for incentivised conditions improved more rapidly in the first year before returning to prior trends, with modest cost-effective reductions in mortality and hospital admissions in some domains and narrowing differences between deprived and non-deprived areas. However, achievement for non-incentivised conditions was lower and worsened over time, and both clinicians and patients reported reduced continuity and person centredness of care, with overall impacts on costs, professional behaviour and patient experience remaining uncertain (Gillam et al. 2012).
- Short term improvements **not sustained** and reversed after withdrawal: QOF incentives consistently improved recorded quality at one year beyond pre incentivisation trends, with largest gains in complex process indicators and those that had previously performed poorly. By three years, however, improvements were inconsistent and not clearly above trend and gains appeared to reverse following withdrawal, with reductions in recorded quality at one and three years (Ho et al. 2025).
- Mixed and inconsistent effects on health inequalities: QOF was associated with some narrowing of socioeconomic and age-related inequalities, particularly in England. However, temporary widening of deprivation gaps was also observed and socioeconomic inequalities in Scotland did not narrow and in some cases widened. Sex based

inequalities persisted or widened in some settings, and exception reporting was more common among older, deprived and multimorbid patients; there was no consistent pattern of change in ethnic inequalities and no consistent evidence of sustained reductions in health inequalities (Holdroyd et al. 2025).

- **Initial health gains not sustained and limited overall impact:** QOF initially improved health outcomes for a limited number of conditions, but effects subsequently returned to pre-existing trends. There was limited impact on non-incentivised activities with adverse effects for some sub population groups, and overall impact on improving health outcomes was constrained by the focus on process-based indicators and ceiling thresholds (Langdown & Peckham 2013).
- **Practice and population characteristics associated with systematic performance differences:** QOF performance was negatively associated with socioeconomic deprivation, higher proportions of patients aged over 65 years, larger list size, higher mean GP age and APMS contracts, while group practice status, higher FTE GP numbers and training practice status were frequently associated with better performance. Associations for most other characteristics were inconsistent, and the evidence base was largely cross sectional and based on early QOF data (Srai et al. 2025).

Evidence limitations

Across the QOF evidence base, the overall limitations are consistent and recurrent across reviews.

- **Predominantly observational designs:** Most included studies were cross sectional, ecological, or before and after analyses without robust comparators, limiting causal inference.
- **Attribution challenges:** Improvements in outcomes cannot be confidently attributed to QOF due to concurrent policy changes, secular trends, and wider system reforms.
- **Short term follow up:** Many studies focused on early years of QOF, with limited long-term evaluation of sustainability.
- **Reliance on recorded data:** Outcomes are often based on recorded quality indicators rather than independently verified clinical outcomes, raising the possibility that improvements reflect documentation rather than true care changes.
- **Limited patient centred outcomes:** Few studies assessed holistic care, integration, continuity, patient experience, or access, and none of the equity focused reviews assessed equity in access to care.
- **Indicator scope limitations:** Evidence is concentrated on incentivised conditions, with weaker evidence on non-incentivised activities and potential spillover effects.
- **Heterogeneity of measures:** Variation in indicators, populations, subgroups, and country context makes synthesis difficult and findings inconsistent.
- **Equity evidence inconsistent:** Effects on socioeconomic, ethnic, sex and age inequalities vary by setting and indicator, with no consistent sustained reduction in inequalities.
- **Early QOF bias:** Many analyses use data from the early years of QOF, limiting understanding of later iterations and reforms.
- **Withdrawal evidence limited:** Evidence on the effects of indicator withdrawal exists but is less extensive and largely focused on recorded quality.

3.5.2. Quality assurance and improvement framework

The QAIF was introduced in Wales in 2019, replacing the QOF, which had been in place since its introduction as part of the new GMS contract in 2004.

Organisational and contractual context

- The QAIF forms part of the GP contract and aims to embed quality assurance and quality improvement activities within general practice with many QI activities delivered at cluster or GP collaborative level (Welsh Government 2021).

Contract holders

- Financial incentives provided through QAIF points linked to achievement of indicators and completion of quality improvement projects, with points assigned across domains such as clinical indicators, quality improvement, access standards and collaborative working (Welsh Government 2021).

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Financial incentives provided through QAIF points linked to achievement of indicators and completion of quality improvement projects, with points assigned across domains such as clinical indicators, quality improvement, access standards and collaborative working (Welsh Government 2021).

Conditions covered

- Clinical indicators cover areas including influenza vaccination, dementia care review, diabetes management, COPD review, mental health monitoring and palliative care multidisciplinary review (Welsh Government 2021).
- Quality improvement projects address areas including prescribing safety, atrial fibrillation management, antimicrobial stewardship for urinary tract infection, advance care planning, activity and clinical data quality, and inhaler prescribing (Welsh Government 2021).
- In 2020–21, a COVID-19 learning quality improvement project focused on urgent care planning across clusters was introduced (Welsh Government 2020).

Summary of evaluation findings

- **No formal evaluation** or primary research examining the impact of the framework was identified

3.5.3. Other quality improvement schemes

Quality improvement activity in general practice is described as a systematic approach to improving quality of care comprising a set of principles and methods, often operationalised through activities such as Plan–Do–Study–Act (PDSA) cycles, audit and feedback, learning events, and collaborative working (Bramwell et al. 2023).

The narrative review by Bramwell et al. (2023) identified six financially incentivised quality improvement interventions in primary care, five of which had been formally evaluated.

- Somerset Practice Quality Scheme (England, 2015–2017)
- Staffordshire Quality Improvement Framework (Stoke-on-Trent, UK, 2009–2015)
- North West England Scheme (East Lancashire, 2016–2018)
- Australian Primary Care Collaboratives Program (Australia, 2004–2011)
- Swedish Quality Improvement Project (Stockholm, 2016–2017)

Organisational and contractual context

- Somerset Practice Quality Scheme
Countywide alternative contractual arrangement to QOF, in which practices opted out but received the same QOF-equivalent payment, supported by the CCG and requiring participation in a Quality Improvement Network.
- Staffordshire Quality Improvement Framework
Local framework operating alongside QOF, incorporating locally agreed standards, educational programmes, learning events and practice visits.
- North West England Scheme
Local quality improvement initiative implemented in addition to QOF within a defined geographical area, with capitation-based payment for protocol-driven identification and management of patients.
- Australian Primary Care Collaboratives Program
National collaborative programme structured around quality improvement collaborative methodology, with central programme management and workshop-based learning and protected time for planning quality incentives.
- Swedish Quality Improvement Project
Regional primary care initiative requiring submission of quality improvement reports to the healthcare administration system, with optional training provision.

Contract holders

- Across the reviewed interventions, participation and payment were described as occurring at the level of general practices.

Embedded financial mechanisms and/or incentives

- Somerset Practice Quality Scheme
Same payment to practices as would have been received through QOF achievement in 2012/13.
- Staffordshire Quality Improvement Framework
Up to £6 per registered patient based on level of achievement assessed by a panel of stakeholders including patients.
- North West England Scheme
Payment on capitation basis for patients identified and managed according to protocol.
- Australian Primary Care Collaboratives Program
Funding for programme managers, protected clinical time for planning and learning, and additional financial incentives for practices (not clearly specified how administered).
- Swedish Quality Improvement Project
€0.5 per patient per year to practices that provided reports of QI activities.

Conditions covered

- Somerset Practice Quality Scheme
Multimorbidity and person-centred coordinated care; included health coaching, multidisciplinary support for frailty, social prescribing and self-management support.
- Staffordshire Quality Improvement Framework
Long-term conditions, including cardiovascular disease and stroke.
- North West England Scheme
Hypertension and atrial fibrillation.

- Australian Primary Care Collaboratives Program
Primarily chronic disease management, including diabetes and cardiovascular disease.
- Swedish Quality Improvement Project
Locally determined quality improvement projects reported to the healthcare administration system.

Summary of review findings

The literature review by Bramwell et al. 2023 reviewed the international published literature on the processes and outcomes of financially incentivised quality improvement activity in primary care and identified five evaluated interventions. The key findings from these evaluations are summarised below.

- **Very limited evidence of effectiveness:** Very limited robust evidence that financially incentivising QI improves patient care, organisational performance, or system-level outcomes.
- Practitioner engagement and acceptability: Modest evidence that financially incentivised QI is valued by practitioners, with high levels of scheme uptake
- **Value for investment: Very limited evidence** that financially incentivised QI represents better value than alternative approaches to improving care.
- Findings from the largest programme: Evaluation of the Australian Primary Care Collaborative Program (2004–2011) showed promising engagement from primary care and some improvement in selected clinical measures.
- Role of system support: Evaluated schemes commonly incorporated elements of system support and flexibility, including feedback mechanisms, opportunities for reflection, and in some cases protected time for planning and implementing QI activities.
- Contextual enablers of effective QI: Effective QI appears to depend heavily on contextual enablers such as leadership, professional ownership, protected time, and system support

Evidence limitations

The literature review by Bramwell et al. 2023 identified several important limitations within the existing evidence base on financially incentivised quality improvement in primary care.

- Limited evidence of effectiveness: Very limited robust evidence that financially incentivised QI improves patient care, organisational performance, or system-level outcomes.
- Methodological limitations: Many evaluations were small-scale, short-term, uncontrolled, or limited in design, restricting causal inference.
- Narrow outcome assessment: Most studies focused on limited clinical indicators and did not comprehensively assess patient, professional, organisational, or system-level outcomes.
- Limited long-term evidence: Insufficient follow-up to determine sustainability of effects.
- Limited economic evaluation: Little evidence that incentivised QI represents better value than alternative approaches.
- Measurement challenges: Difficulties in measuring overall quality of primary care, including lack of agreed, multidimensional outcome measures.

- Attribution challenges: Observed changes cannot easily be attributed to financial incentives alone, given the influence of contextual enablers such as leadership, professional ownership, protected time, and system support.

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Kumar et al. 2014. Do local enhanced services in primary care improve outcomes? Results from a literature review. *Quality in Primary Care* 22(3): 157-169

<https://doi.org/10.4172/1479-1064.1000652>

Marks et al. 2011. Incentivizing preventive services in primary care: perspectives on Local Enhanced Services. *Journal of Public Health*. 33(4):556-564

<https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdr016>

4.4. Incentive, quality, and performance frameworks

4.4.1. Quality outcomes framework

Key organisational documents

NHS England 2018. Report of the review of the quality and outcomes framework in England. NHS England, London. Available at:

<https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/quality-outcome-framework-report-of-the-review.pdf> [Accessed: 11/02/2026].

Nuffield Trust 2014. The NHS payment system: evolving policy and emerging evidence: Research report. Nuffield Trust, London. Available at:

<https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/research/the-nhs-payment-system-evolving-policy-and-emerging-evidence> [Accessed: 11/02/2026].

Key resources for evaluation of impact

Ahmed et al. 2021. What drives general practitioners in the UK to improve the quality of care? A systematic literature review. *BMJ Open Quality*. 10e.00127.

<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-001127>

Boeckxstaens et al. 2011. The equity dimension in evaluations of the quality and outcomes framework: a systematic review. *BMC Health Services Research*. 11:209

<https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-11-209>

Forbes et al. 2016. Review of the quality and outcomes framework in England: final report. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System, London. Available at:

<https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/review-of-qof-21st-december-2016.pdf> [Accessed: 11/02/2026].

Forbes et al. 2017. The role of the quality and outcomes framework in the care of long-term conditions: a systematic review. *British Journal of General Practice*. 67(664):e775-e784.

<https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp17X693077>

Gillam et al. 2012. Pay-for-performance in the United Kingdom: impact of the quality and outcomes framework: a systematic review. *Annals of Family Medicine*. 10(5):461-468.

<https://doi.org/10.1370/afm.1377>

Ho et al. 2025. Effect of UK quality and outcomes framework pay-for-performance programme on quality of primary care: systematic review with quantitative synthesis. *BMJ*. 389:e083424
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-083424>

Holdroyd et al. 2025. The impact of primary care funding on health inequalities: an umbrella review. *Primary Health Care Research and Development*. 26(e24):1-10.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/S146342362500012X>

Langdown & Peckham 2013. The use of financial incentives to help improve health outcomes: is the quality and outcomes framework fit for purpose? A systematic review. *Journal of Public Health*. 36(2):251-258.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/ftd077>

Srai et al. 2025. General practice characteristics associated with pay-for-performance in the UK: a systematic review. *BJGP Open*. 9(2)
<https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGPO.2024.0174>

4.4.2. Quality assurance and incentive framework

Key organisational documents

Welsh Government 2020. Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework: supplementary guidance for the GMS contract Wales 2020/21. Welsh Government, Cardiff. Available at: <https://www.bma.org.uk/media/3339/wales-gov-quality-and-improvement-framework-2020-21.pdf> [Accessed 11/03/2026]

Welsh Government 2021. Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework: Guidance for the GMS contract Wales 2021/22. Welsh Government, Cardiff. Available at: <https://sbuhb.nhs.wales/about-us/key-documents-folder/performance-and-finance-committee-papers/performance-and-finance-committee-march-2023/32-app-1-qaif-guidancepdf/> (Accessed 24/02/2026).

4.4.3. Other quality improvement schemes

Key resources for evaluation of impact

Bramwell et al. 2023. 'Pay for Quality Improvement' schemes: financially incentivising quality improvement activity in primary care. Available from: Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System. London.
<https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/pay-for-quality-improvement%E2%80%99-schemes-literature-review.pdf> [Accessed 24/02/2026]

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Table 1: Summary of included evidence from reviews for models of care / service delivery structures

Resource	Citation	Recency (Search dates)	Evidence Type*	Status**	Findings	Comments
Accountable care organisations						
Database search	<p>Holm et al. 2024</p> <p>The impact of Medicaid accountable care organizations on health care utilization, quality measures, health outcomes and costs from 2012 to 2023: A Scoping Review. Medical Care Research and Review. 81(5):355-369</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1177/10775587241241984</p>	1st, Jan 2012 to Nov 15th 2023	Scoping review	Published	The findings of this review indicate mixed evidence on the effectiveness of Medicaid ACOs. Reported improvements included increased use of primary care services and reductions in hospital admissions and inpatient stays. Evidence of cost savings was limited to a small number of studies and appeared to be influenced by the duration of beneficiary attribution and the time elapsed since ACO implementation.	This scoping review assesses the impacts of Medicaid ACOs implemented after the Affordable Care Act on health care utilization, quality measures, health outcomes, and costs, drawing on studies published between 2012 and 2023. The authors conducted the review in response to the considerable variation in design, practice and evidence across Medicaid ACO programs. The authors commented that the heterogeneity in study designs and comparison populations limits the ability to draw conclusions about Medicaid ACOs as a whole.
Database search	<p>Kaufman et al. 2019</p> <p>Impact of accountable care organizations on utilization, care, and outcomes: a systematic review. Medical Care Research and Review. 76(3):255-290.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1177/1077558717745916</p>	2010 to Nov 5th 2016	Systematic Review	Published	<p>The 42 included articles examined ACO contracts involving Medicare (n=24), Medicaid (n 5), commercial payers (n=11), and multiple payer types (n=2).</p> <p>Across payer groups, the most consistent associations with ACO implementation were reductions in inpatient utilisation and emergency department visits, alongside improvements in preventive care and chronic disease management.</p>	This review sought to assess the quality and strength of evidence regarding the association between public and private accountable care organizations and changes in healthcare utilization, processes of care, and health outcomes. It examined ACOs across payer types and evaluated whether these models were associated with improvements in care delivery and clinical outcomes, with particular attention to methodological rigour

					<p>The seven studies assessing patient experience or clinical outcomes found no evidence that ACOs adversely affect care; however, further monitoring of patient care and outcomes is recommended.</p>	<p>and consistency of findings across studies.</p> <p>No prospective trials have evaluated ACOs, and we were unable to synthesize the results of observational studies into a meta-analysis due to the differences between studies in the payer programs, populations, and outcome measures evaluated</p>
Database search	<p>Wilson et al. 2020</p> <p>The impacts of accountable care organizations on patient experience, health outcomes and costs: a rapid review. <i>Journal of Health Services Research and Policy</i>.25(2):130-138</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1177/1355819620913141</p>	Inception to June 2019	Rapid review	Published	<p>The reviewed studies suggest that ACOs are associated with cost reductions without evidence of reduced quality.</p> <p>Positive trends were reported across most quadruple-aim domains compared with fee-for-service models.</p> <p>Cost savings were generally modest and primarily driven by reduced outpatient spending among medically complex patients and decreases in low-value care.</p> <p>ACOs met most quality measures and often outperformed fee-for-service comparators, while evidence on provider experience was limited.</p> <p>Qualitative evidence highlighted enabling mechanisms such as additional care-coordination staff and shared electronic health record systems.</p>	<p>This rapid review sought to identify the impacts of accountable care organisations on the quadruple aim—improving patient experience, enhancing population health outcomes, reducing per capita healthcare costs, and supporting positive provider experience. In addition, it aimed to determine how and why such impacts were achieved, by synthesising both quantitative evaluations and qualitative evidence regarding mechanisms, implementation factors, and enabling conditions</p> <p>The authors reported that limited availability of data across the study questions and the Quadruple Aim outcomes constrained the reliability of the findings, highlighting the need for ongoing monitoring and further research.</p>

Multispecialty community providers						
Advance Google Search	<p>Sheaff et al. 2018</p> <p>From programme theory to logic models for multispecialty community providers: a realist evidence synthesis. <i>Health and Social Care Delivery Research</i> 6(24).</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3310/hsdr06240</p>	Inception to 5 th December 2016	Realist synthesis	Published	<p>As MCPs are a new model with limited direct evidence, expectations about how they may operate are informed by evidence from comparable international initiatives.</p> <p>MDTs are likely to be the central mechanism by which MCPs work, provided that the MDTs include the relevant professions (hence, organisations) and, for care planning, the individual patients.</p> <p>These teams bring people from different services and professions together to co-ordinate their work better for each patient, and give patients and carers more of a voice. Information technology is also needed so that each team can see the most recent information about what care each patient needs.</p>	<p>This realist synthesis sought to elicit and test initial programme theories underpinning MCPs, by analysing policy-makers' assumptions and synthesising international secondary evidence to determine which mechanisms were supported by evidence, under what conditions, and for which populations. The review aimed to refine these assumptions into a more evidence-based logic model explaining how MCPs might improve care coordination, patient experience, population health, and cost-effectiveness.</p> <p>The review developed multiple context-mechanism-outcome configurations (middle-range theories) on whether MCPs work, in what circumstances and how. However, some of these middle-range theories are based on indirect evidence, which may influence interpretation. Indirect evidence was included from ACO and patient-centred medical homes.</p>
Advance Google Search	<p>Turner et al. 2018</p> <p>The international knowledge base for new care models relevant to primary care-led integrated models: a realist synthesis. <i>Health and</i></p>	January 2000 to December 2016	Realist synthesis	Published	<p>Findings suggest that integrated care models that work well are tailored to local needs and constantly evolving. They are also dependent on good connections between local people, communities and health-care staff, especially those that allow learning</p>	<p>This realist synthesis sought to articulate and test the underlying programme theories of MCP models, by synthesising international theoretical, empirical and practice-based evidence to explain how mechanisms operating in different contexts contribute to</p>

	<p><i>Social Care Delivery Research 6(25).</i></p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3310/hsdr06250</p>				<p>from one another. In an MCP, there should be:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. opportunities for all the different staff and service users to be involved 2. a shared view of the benefits of working together, with trust for one another and the organisations that they represent 3. training to support integrated working <p>Findings suggest that, when these three aspects come together, staff and service users can change their behaviours to benefit both themselves and the system.</p>	<p>improvements in population health, cost-effectiveness, patient experience and staff experience. The synthesis focused specifically on the 14 MCP vanguards in England, which were designed to provide comprehensive, integrated care outside a hospital setting.</p> <p>The evidence base included limited empirical evidence; there is a limited number of small-scale evaluations comprising uncontrolled before and after studies or single-case studies. The realist synthesis contains a number of commentaries drawing on experiential evidence.</p> <p>The limitations of the evidence base related to the long-term impacts of enhanced primary care teams delivering care closer to home; the heterogeneity of contracting models and variable reporting; and the use of before-and-after methods prone to bias. Thus, there is a moderate level of uncertainty around the conclusions.</p>
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Key

ACO: Accountable care organisations; MCP: Multispecialty providers; MDT: Multidisciplinary team

Table 2: Summary of key organisational documents for models of care / service delivery structures

Citation	Content Summary
Accountable care organisations	
<p>National Association of Primary Care 2017</p> <p>Providing accountable care. Comparing the delivery of primary care in the UK and USA through Accountable Care Systems and Organisations. https://napc.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Providing_Accountable_Care.pdf</p>	<p>This document is an organisational report produced by the National Association of Primary Care that describes accountable care as a concept and explores how it is being interpreted and developed across the US and English health systems. It outlines a range of accountable care-oriented organisational models that focus on population-based responsibility, integration across care settings, and collaboration between multiple provider organisations, including the PCH, MCPs, and ACSs. The report draws on discussions from a UK-US symposium and is intended to share perspectives and learning rather than to formally evaluate effectiveness.</p>
<p>Shortell et al. 2014</p> <p>Accountable care organisations in the United States and England: Testing, evaluating and learning what works. The Kings Fund, London. https://assets.kingsfund.org.uk/f/256914/x/74b750cdcd/accountable_care_organisations_us_and_england_2014.pdf</p>	<p>This briefing document provides an overview of ACOs in the US and examines their relevance to the development of more integrated and accountable models of care in England. It describes the origins and defining features of ACOs, outlines the different organisational forms that have emerged in the US, and discusses how these models are tested, evaluated and adapted over time. The report also explores early evidence on performance and draws out lessons for policy and system leaders, with particular attention to the implications of the ACO approach for integrated care initiatives within the English NHS</p>
Multispecialty community providers	
<p>NHS England 2016b</p> <p>The multispecialty community provider (MCP) emerging care model and contract framework. https://www.abhi.org.uk/media/1208/mcp-care-model-frmwrk.pdf</p>	<p>This national policy framework defines what being a MCP means by assembling features from the 14 MCP vanguards into a common framework. The framework document describes the MCP model, its aim, development, and design of contractual arrangements. This framework was not intended to be a definitive national policy, as it was expected at the time of the publication that changes would be made as more evidence emerged from the Vanguard New Care Models Programme and from wider implementation.</p>
<p>NHS England 2017a</p>	<p>This national contractual guidance focuses on GP participation in a MCP. There are different ways for GPs to participate in a MCP, which</p>

<p>GP participation in a Multispecialty Community Provider NHS England: Accountable Care Organisation (ACO) Contract package - supporting document. NHS England. https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/12/1693_DraftMCP-5_A.pdf</p>	<p>could range from maintaining current practice arrangements to suspending existing contracts and working as an employee directly for the new organisations. The model has been designed to maximise the options available, and it is possible for different practices to relate to an MCP in different ways. The options are virtual, partially integrated or fully integrated MCP. The use of ACO contracts is described for partially and fully integrated MCPs.</p>
<p>Primary care home</p>	
<p>Dougall et al. 2019 Insights from the spread of the primary care home. The King's Fund, London. https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/insight-and-analysis/reports/insights-primary-care-home</p>	<p>This research report by The King's Fund aimed to explore the factors that enabled and hindered the spread of the PCH model across England (Dougall et al. 2019). The research used mixed methods including literature review, qualitative interviews with members of the National Association of Primary Care and early adopters of the PCH model, development of case studies, and reflections with internal and external stakeholders. The case study sites were: Granta Medical Practices in Cambridge, St Austell, and Newport Pagnell Medical Centre.</p>
<p>National Association of Primary Care 2025 The Primary Care Home. National Association of Primary Care, London. https://napc.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/PCH-2015.pdf</p>	<p>A policy paper setting out the core characteristics and organisational model of the PCH. PCH was developed to strengthen and redesign primary care by bringing together local service to encourage new ways of working based on the needs of the population. The paper contains information on proposed contractual models, financial mechanisms, governance structures, and potential outcome metrics.</p>
<p>Primary care networks</p>	
<p>Fisher et al. 2019 Briefing: Understanding primary care networks – context, benefits and risks. The Health Foundation; London. https://www.health.org.uk/sites/default/files/upload/publications/2019/Understanding%20primary%20care%20networks.pdf</p>	<p>A Health Foundation briefing describing the introduction of PCNs in England, outlining their policy origins in the NHS Long Term Plan and GP contract reforms, and explaining the Network Contract DES, funding arrangements and workforce expansion through the ARRS, alongside discussion of potential benefits and risks.</p>
<p>NHS England 2019a Investment and evolution: a five-year framework for GP contract reform to implement The NHS Long Term Plan, NHS England, London.</p>	<p>This NHS England guidance document sets out a five-year framework for GP contract reform to implement the NHS Long Term Plan. The document introduces PCNs as groups of neighbouring general</p>

<p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/gp-contract-2019.pdf</p>	<p>practices working together to deliver services to defined populations. It establishes the Network Contract DES as the contractual mechanism through which practices collaborate within PCNs and deliver specified services. The framework also introduces the ARRS to support the recruitment of additional staff, including roles such as clinical pharmacists, social prescribing link workers, physician associates, first contact physiotherapists and community paramedics. In addition, the framework outlines requirements for PCN governance, network agreements and delivery of national service specifications through the Network Contract DES.</p>
<p>Year of care</p>	
<p>Ahmad et al. 2014 Person-centred care: from ideas to action. Bringing together the evidence on shared decision making and self-management support. Health Foundation, London. https://www.health.org.uk/sites/default/files/PersonCentredCareFromIdeasToAction.pdf</p>	<p>This report seeks to bring together the evidence on shared decision making and self-management support from 11 national implementation programmes, including evaluations from the Year of Care. It also draws on in-depth interviews with programme leads, and information from a seminar with health care professionals, researchers, policy makers and educators. The report concludes that the evidence base for self-management support and shared decision making is expanding, but remains mixed, with variable quality and gaps in the knowledge base.</p>
<p>Department of Health 2012 QIPP Long-Term Conditions: Supporting the local implementation of the year of care funding model for people with long-term conditions. Department of Health, London. https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/215060/dh_133652.pdf</p>	<p>This funding guidance document introduces the Year of Care funding model and is aimed at health and social care commissioners and providers who are implementing integrated long-term conditions care services to improve outcomes and experience for people. The financial model described is an annual risk adjusted capitation budget which is based on levels of need. The model aims to improve outcomes and deliver a more effective use of resources by focussing providers on moving away from episodic, activity driven funding flows towards person centred care irrespective of organisational boundaries. The guidance also describes implications for commissioning, contracting, and service delivery arrangements associated with implementing the model.</p>
<p>NHS England 2016a Personalised care and support planning handbook: The journey to person-centred care. NHS England, London.</p>	<p>This handbook introduces personalised care and support planning. It contains and links to practical guidance, case studies and theory on how to introduce personalised care and support planning. The handbook pulls together learning from several organisations and</p>

https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/core-info-care-support-planning-1.pdf	<p>programmes that have been working on personalised care and support planning, support for self-management, and person-centred care, including National Voices, Royal College of General Practitioners, and in particular, draws on learning from the Year of Care Programme.</p>
<p>NHS England 2017b The Long Term Conditions Year of Care Commissioning Programme Implementation Handbook. NHS England, London. https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2017/02/ltc-yoc-handbook.pdf</p>	<p>This implementation guidance handbook captures learning from early implementation sites of the Year of Care programme. The handbook covers key factors and stages of implementation, including leadership and cross-system collaboration, co-production and engagement with patients, whole-population analysis to target resources effectively, tasks associated with service change, calculation of capitated budgets. The handbook also presents findings from evaluations conducted at early implementation sites.</p>

Key

ARRS: Additional Roles Reimbursement Scheme; ACO: accountable care organisations; ACS: accountable care systems; DES: Directed enhanced service; MCP: multispecialty community providers; NHS: National Health Service; PCH: primary care home; PCN: Primary Care Network

Table 3: Summary of included evidence from evaluations for models of care / service delivery structures

Citation	Content summary
Multispecialty community providers	
<p>Checkland et al. 2022</p> <p>National Evaluation of the Vanguard New Care Models Programme, Final Report. University of Manchester, Manchester https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/national-evaluation-of-the-vanguard-new-care-models-programme-final-report-submitted.pdf</p>	<p>This report presents the final findings of the National Evaluation of the Vanguard New Care Models Programme. While evaluations of individual local Vanguard sites have been published, this report provides the only comprehensive assessment of the programme as a whole.</p> <p>Several New Care Model types were initially proposed and were subsequently refined into five models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. Primary and Acute Care Systems ii. Multispecialty Community Providers iii. Enhanced Health in Care Homes iv. Urgent and Emergency Care v. Acute Care Collaboratives
<p>Wilson et al. 2019</p> <p>Investigating locally commissioned evaluations of the NHS Vanguard Programme. University of Manchester, Manchester. https://research.manchester.ac.uk/files/118897237/Investigating_Locally_Commissioned_Evaluations_of_the_Vanguard_Programme_Final_Report.pdf</p> <p>Wilson et al. 2021</p> <p>Investigating the nature and quality of locally commissioned evaluations of the NHS Vanguard programme: an evidence synthesis. Health Research Policy and Systems 19(1) https://doi.org/10.1186/s12961-021-00711-3</p>	<p>This report (and its derivative publication) synthesises the locally commissioned evaluations conducted as part of the Vanguard New Care Models Programme. The report assessed the nature and quality of these evaluations, including details of the evaluators, questions, methodological approaches and limitations in design and/or reporting.</p> <p>A total of 115¹⁹ separate reports relating to the locally commissioned evaluations were identified, out of which 46 reports related to nine MCP Vanguards. Most evaluations were both resource and time limited (12 months) and employed mixed methods. Evaluations largely focused on describing the implementation context and capturing stakeholder reflections on and experience of the development and implementation of the Vanguard.</p> <p>Additionally, the report investigated evaluation leads' experiences of the evaluation process and of the Vanguard programme overall.</p>

¹⁹ 108 were identified in Wilson et al. 2019, although methods seem to be the same

Primary care home	
<p>Kumpunen et al. 2017</p> <p>Primary Care Home: Evaluating a new model of primary care. Nuffield Trust, London.</p> <p>https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/sites/default/files/2017-08/pch-report-final.pdf</p>	<p>This evaluation report by Nuffield Trust aimed to explore the development, implementation and early impact of the Primary Care Home model across 13 out of 15 rapid test sites across England. Mixed-methods were used to evaluate the sites including review of the logic model of 13 rapid test sites, qualitative interviews with clinical and managerial leads and frontline staff, questionnaires and co-creation of ongoing monitoring and evaluation approaches. Three rapid tests sites were also explored more in-depth, and these were: Healthy East Grinstead Partnership, St Austell Healthcare, and Thanet Health Community Interest Company.</p>
Primary care networks	
<p>Beech et al. 2023</p> <p>Doing more for less? A mixed methods analysis of the experience of primary care networks in socioeconomically deprived areas. The Health Foundation, London.</p> <p>https://www.health.org.uk/reports-and-analysis/reports/doing-more-for-less</p>	<p>A Health Foundation report drawing on a rapid literature review, policy analysis, quantitative workforce and funding data, and qualitative interviews to analyse whether national primary care network policy and resource allocation have mitigated or widened inequalities between more and less deprived areas, and to examine the experience of operating PCNs in areas of high socioeconomic deprivation in England. The rapid literature review was conducted to inform the policy analysis and interview framework, rather than to generate standalone synthesised findings.</p>
<p>Checkland et al. 2023b</p> <p>Primary Care Networks: exploring primary care commissioning, contracting, and provision. Final report.</p> <p>Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System. London.</p> <p>https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/final-report-prucomm-primary-care-networks-full-version-post-peer-review.pdf</p>	<p>The purpose of this report was to examine the development of PCNs and to explore their role as a governance mechanism within primary care service provision. It aimed to understand the policy objectives underpinning changes to primary care commissioning and contracting, how networks were formed and operated in practice, and how contractual, payment, and support arrangements were implemented at local level. The report also sought to examine how practices collaborated within neighbourhoods, including workforce arrangements and network-level incentives, and how PCNs engaged with wider local health and care systems, including community, voluntary, and system-level partners.</p>
<p>Swift 2021</p> <p>Primary care networks - Two years on. NHS Confederation, London.</p> <p>https://www.nhsconfed.org/system/files/2021-08/Primary-care-networks-two-years-on-01.pdf</p>	<p>This report considers the progress of PCNs two years on from their creation, exploring the challenges encountered and the opportunities ahead as PCNs move toward greater system working. The evaluation was based on engagement sessions hosted by PCNs and a survey of over 150 clinical directors and</p>

	managers of PCNs. The report offers guidance for PCN development and improvement for the Network Contract DES.
<p>Swift 2023</p> <p>Primary care networks - Three years on. NHS Confederation, London. https://www.nhsconfed.org/system/files/2023-02/Primary-care-networks-Three-years-on_0.pdf</p>	The purpose of this report was to assess progress of PCNs from establishment to three years on, exploring any challenges and successes. The evaluation was based on ongoing engagement with approximately 200 clinical directors and managers of PCNs alongside wider primary care organisations, for example GP federations. The report aims to outline what contributes to a strong PCN and sets out recommendations for Integrated Care Systems and policymakers, including priorities for the 2023-2024 PCN contract.
Year of Care	
<p>Year of Care 2011</p> <p>Report of findings from the pilot programme. Year of care. http://www.networks.nhs.uk/nhs-networks/national-pbc-clinical-leaders-network/documents/YOC_Report.pdf</p>	This is the final report of the Year of Care pilot project. It describes the background, aims and objectives, parallel evaluations, the way the programme was delivered and its impact. The Year of Care Programme has demonstrated how to deliver personalised care in routine practice for people with long term conditions, using diabetes as an exemplar. Year of Care worked with three pilot primary care trusts: Tower Hamlets, Calderdale and Kirklees, and North of Tyne.
<p>Year of Care Partnership 2021</p> <p>The impact of implementing the Year of Care approach to personalised care and support planning. https://www.yearofcare.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/7.-The-impact-of-implementing-the-YOC-PCSP-approach-V1.1-final-Jul-21.pdf</p>	This summary report of evaluations outlines some of the quantitative and qualitative findings and feedback Year of Care have gathered over the past decade. This includes evidence on patient experience, healthcare professionals' views, changes in care processes and coordination, and clinical outcomes. Clinical areas included diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, musculoskeletal conditions, frailty, and dementia.
<p>Year of Care Partnership 2024</p> <p>Implementing Proactive Care Using the Year of Care Approach to Personalised Care and Support Planning. https://www.yearofcare.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Proactive-Care-Pilot-Programme-report-V1.0-final-May-2024.pdf</p>	This evaluation report presents two primary care networks (Carlisle Healthcare and Keswick & Solway) in North Cumbria who implemented the Proactive Care which is based on Year of Care approach. The report details how the process was developed, provides examples of supporting resources and emphasises the role of digital systems in identifying people and delivering high quality care. The evaluation drew on data from surveys and workshops but did not include measures of impact; staff nevertheless reported perceived benefits of working in this way.

Key

PCN: primary care networks; QOF: quality outcomes framework.

Table 4: Summary of primary research for models of care / service delivery structures

Citation	Aspect of Question explored	Study type	Methods	Focus
Primary care networks				
<p>Checkland et al. 2023a</p> <p>Primary care networks as a means of supporting primary care: findings from qualitative case study-based evaluation in the English NHS. <i>BMJ Open</i>. 2023 Nov 21;13(11):e075111.</p> <p>https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/13/11/e075111</p>	<p>How PCNs in England are constituted to meet their defined goals and what factors affect their ability to deliver benefits</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Case studies (7 PCNs in England)</p> <p>Interviews (n=91)</p> <p>Observations (87 hours)</p>	<p>Explores PCNs as a means of supporting primary care, how they are constituted to meet their defined goals, the factors affecting their ability to deliver benefits at community, network and member levels, and the outcomes of outputs associated with PCNs so far.</p>
<p>Smith et al. 2022</p> <p>Early evidence of the development of primary care networks in England: a rapid evaluation study. <i>Health and Social Care Delivery Research</i> 10(27): 1-108</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3310/GBUO3259</p>	<p>Early implementation of primary care networks (PCNs) focusing on what has helped or hindered progress, how PCNs operate in relation to pre-existing collaborations and issues for rural networks.</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Four work packages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A rapid evidence assessment • Stakeholder workshop (academics, policy experts, PPI) • Case studies across four sites using interviews, observation of meetings, a survey and documentary analysis <p>Analysis synthesis to develop recommendations</p>	<p>This evaluation study was to produce early evidence on the development and interpretation of PCNs in England to inform policy to include the context and rationale for collaboration, early learning from establishing PCNs, barriers and facilitators, how PCNs relate to previous GP collaborations, differences between rural and urban settings and the likely progress in light of COVID-19.</p>
<p>Warwick-Giles et al. 2024</p> <p>Exploring whether primary care networks can contribute to the national goal of reducing health</p>	<p>How the design and introduction of PCNs influence their ability to tackle health inequalities</p>	<p>Mixed methods</p>	<p>Quantitative data</p> <p>Linear regression analysis of allocated PCN funding in relation to income deprivation</p>	<p>This study assessed whether PCN funding mechanisms support efforts to reduce health</p>

<p>inequalities: a mixed methods study. <i>British Journal of General Practice</i> 74(742): e290-e299 https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGP.2023.0258</p>			<p>scores (using national datasets).</p> <p>Qualitative data: Interviews (n=91) with GPs, Commissioners, ARRS staff and NHS managers</p> <p>Observations: 87 hours of PCN meeting observations across seven PCN sites</p>	<p>inequalities. It also sought to understand how PCN characteristics, internal relationships, organisational maturity, staffing models, and local context affect their ability to address inequalities.</p>
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Key

ARRS: Additional Roles Reimbursement Scheme; GP: General Practitioner; NHS: National Health Service; PCN: Primary Care Networks

Table 5: Summary of included evidence from reviews for contracting and governance models

Resource	Citation	Recency (Search dates)	Evidence Type*	Status**	Findings	Comments
Organisational search	<p>Sanderson et al. 2016</p> <p>Alliance contracting, prime contracting and outcome based contracting: What can the NHS learn from elsewhere? A literature review. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System. London.</p> <p>https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/new-contractual-models-literature-review-final-july-2016.pdf</p>	<p>No date restrictions</p> <p>Publications up to 2015</p> <p>Type of evidence included: primary quantitative and qualitative research, reviews, theoretical literature, grey literature (policy initiatives, unpublished doctoral theses).</p>	Literature review	Published	<p><u>Contracting approaches</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alliance contracting • Prime contracting • Outcome based contracting <p>66 documents were included in the final review. While there is a lack of empirical evidence, the existing literature suggests that alliance contracting may help increase service integration, it could also help reduce capital costs, increase innovation, improve relationships between contractual partners, and result in non-cost outcomes, such as enhanced reputation and competitive advantage. Alliance contracting may also improve care quality.</p> <p>Prime contracting may help with sharing good practice among sub-contractors and prime leaders, and may improve service coordination. However, tension and lack of trust could arise between prime and sub-contractors. Prime contracting may reduce costs, particularly for the commissioners and it may improve care quality.</p>	<p>The report draws on the wider literature describing new contractual models (alliance, prime and outcome-based contracting). It covers topics, including contract negotiation, risk management, advantages and disadvantages of different contracting mechanisms; it does not undertake a formal evaluation or comparative assessment of outcomes.</p> <p>The literature was gathered from sectors such as construction, public services, aerospace, defence, information and communication technology, and health and welfare services.</p> <p>Literature relating to 'pay for performance' in health care; ACO, was not included.</p> <p>This review suggests that alliance contracting, prime contracting and outcome-based contracting are undertheorized areas. Much of the literature is normative in basis, does not consider issues from a theoretical perspective, and does not give empirical evidence.</p>
Database search	<p>Sanderson et al. 2018</p> <p>New models of contracting in the public sector: a review of alliance contracting, prime contracting and outcome-based contracting literature. <i>Social Policy & Administration</i> 52 (5):1060-1083.</p>					

	https://doi.org/10.1111/spol.12322					
Back chaining	Vlaanderen et al. 2019 Design and effects of outcome-based payment models in healthcare: a systematic review. <i>The European Journal of Health Economics</i> 20:217–232. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10198-018-0989-8	January 2000 to October 2016	Systematic review	Published	The included 88 articles (75 quantitative studies, 8 qualitative studies, 3 research reports, and 2 reviews) described 12 outcome-based payment models implemented in US, UK and South Korea. Models were divided into 2 groups based on differences in design features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrow outcome-based payment models²⁰: Most (5/9) of the narrow models showed positive effects on quality; the others had mixed (2) or negative (2) effects. The effects of narrow models on healthcare utilization or costs, however, were unfavourable (3) or unknown (6). • Broad outcome-based payment models²¹: All broad models (3) showed positive effects on quality of care, while reducing healthcare cost growth. <p>Although strong empirical evidence on the effects of outcome-based payment models on healthcare quality, utilisation, and costs remains limited, current findings suggest that broader models may be preferable to narrower models.</p>	This review analyses the characteristics and effectiveness of outcome-based payment models implemented in OECD countries, examining their impact on quality of care, healthcare utilisation and healthcare costs. Limitations: Most included studies were quasi experimental, with few true experimental designs. The small number of studies for some models (8 models had at most 3 studies) limits the strength of evidence on quality and cost outcomes. The review's definition of outcome-based payment models and selected outcomes may restrict generalisability. Effects are likely influenced by contextual factors, including broader policy environments and geography.

Key

ACO: Accountable care organisations

²⁰ Narrow outcome-based payment models provide explicit financial incentives linked to objectively measured quality indicators, with bonuses or penalties tied to performance. They typically target a specific provider group (e.g., hospitals or primary care physicians) and/or specific clinical areas (e.g., acute myocardial infarction care).

²¹ Broad outcome-based payment models combine global budgets and shared savings with explicit financial incentives linked to quality indicators. They typically target multidisciplinary provider groups delivering a range of services to a defined patient population.

Table 6: Summary of key organisational documents for contracting and governance models

Citation	Content Summary
<p>Addicott 2014</p> <p>Commissioning and contracting for integrated care. The Kings Fund, London.</p> <p>https://assets.kingsfund.org.uk/f/256914/x/7e19e421bd/commissioning_and_contracting_for_integrated_care_2014.pdf</p>	<p>This organisational report describes two new contracting models that aim to support a more integrated care: prime contract and alliance contract. Additionally, a variation of prime contracting, called prime provider contract, is introduced. These new contracting models were implemented at five sites, and their cases were also presented. Two sites used prime contracting (Staffordshire, Bedfordshire), one prime provider contract (Cambridgeshire), one alliance contract (Lambeth) and a mixture of alliance and prime provider contracts (Salford).</p>
<p>NHS England 2014</p> <p>Commissioning for Effective Service Transformation: What we have learnt. NHS England, London.</p> <p>https://www.improconsult.co.uk/uploads/7/2/5/9/72595103/serv-trans-guide.pdf</p>	<p>This organisational report is aimed at commissioners of health and care services to support them in the creation of strategic and operational plans. It provides information on clinical leadership, co-production, local service provision, design of future services, delivering improved outcomes, active management, and selection of commissioning mechanisms. Commissioning mechanisms described include prime provider and alliance contracting.</p>

Table 7: Summary of included evidence from evaluations for contracting and governance models

Citation	Content summary
<p>Sanderson et al. 2019</p> <p>New models of contracting in the NHS. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System, London.</p> <p>https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/new-models-of-contracting-final-report-1-.pdf</p>	<p>This evaluation report aimed to explore why NHS commissioners are choosing new models of contracting, the characteristics of these models, how they are used in practice, and the impact they are having. The research included three case studies, out of which two aimed to implement alliance contracts, and one a joint venture agreement with the goal to develop a lead provider model. The project used qualitative semi-structured interviews with leads for the contractual arrangements, and documentary analysis. Data was collected in two stages from October 2016 - June 2017 and April 2018 – July 2018.</p>

Key

NHS: National Health Service

Table 8: Summary of included evidence from reviews for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms

Resource	Citation	Recency (Search dates)	Evidence Type*	Status**	Findings	Comments
Bundled payments						
Organisational search	Rosen 2025b What can we learn from international examples of contracting for general practice services? In 'The evolution of GP contracting: learning from history and other countries. Article series, Nuffield Trust' https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/news-item/what-can-we-learn-from-international-examples-of-contracting-for-general-practice-services	1947 to present (2024?) and subsequently limited to 2000	Literature review	Published as Blog	Netherlands – chronic disease management via care groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bundled payments for chronic disease management • Contracts between insurance companies and large operational support organisations (“care groups”) 	International examples are discussed descriptively and comparatively; no formal evaluation or synthesis of outcomes is undertaken
Database Search.	Simmons et al. 2014. Disentangling the impact of alternative payment models and associated delivery models on quality of chronic care: a scoping review. <i>Health Policy</i> 143:105034 https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healthpol.2024.105034	2013-2022	Scoping Review	Published	The study identified 34 relevant articles across five types of payment models (capitation/global budget, pay for co-ordination, shared savings/shared risk, blended capitation and bundled payments). United States (n = 25) Canada (n = 3) China (n = 2) Germany (n = 2) Netherlands (n = 2)	This scoping review sought to link alternative payment arrangements including capitation and global budgets, pay for coordination, shared savings and shared risk, blended capitation and bundled payments to their service delivery context, assess the quality of chronic care associated with these models, and disentangle the impact of payment reforms from co-occurring service delivery reforms

					<p>Only one included study examined bundled payments, the Care Chain Frail Elderly programme in the Netherlands, and this assessed patient reported outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The CCFE study reported that the programme did not improve the health of older people. • The programme was positively evaluated by patients. • According to providers, it showed sustained improvements in patient centredness and enjoyment of life. 	<p>The authors repeatedly note that payment reforms and service delivery reforms are usually introduced at the same time, making it difficult to tell which part of the change led to the outcome. They note that there was very limited evidence available to distinguish the two.</p> <p>The certainty of evidence across the review was generally low.</p> <p>The bundled payment article was rated low.</p>
Database Search.	<p>Steenhuis et al. 2020. Unravelling the complexity in the design and implementation of bundled payments: a scoping review of key elements from a payer's perspective. <i>The Millbank Quarterly</i> 98(1):197-222</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0009.12438</p>	Inception – March 2018	Scoping Review	Published	<p>The study reviewed 147 articles (primary research studied, policy analyses, case studies, evaluation reports and conceptual and descriptive papers) and identified 53 elements that were included in the framework.</p> <p>The elements spanned all pre and post contractual procurement phases and included specification of care services and costs, small heterogenous patient populations, allocation of payments and savings/losses, patient identification, alignment of the care delivery model with the payment model and limited effects on quality and costs in early pilots.</p> <p>The authors concluded that bundled payment contracts introduce an alternative set of financial incentives that affect the entire health care system and demand a different type of collaboration among organisations.</p>	<p>This scoping review sought to identify and structure the key elements in the design and implementation of bundled payment contracts across OECD countries</p> <p>The complexities of bundled payments were found to show up everywhere in the contracting lifecycle.</p> <p>The framework provides a structured overview of the principal elements and gives insights into the sources of complexity.</p> <p>The authors note several limitations including the possibility of missing elements, potential reporting bias towards successful implementations, the influence of their bundled payment definition and that findings reflect a payer's only perspective.</p>

<p>Database Search</p>	<p>Struijs et al. 2020. Bundled payment models around the world: how they work and what their impact has been. The Commonwealth Fund, New York. https://www.commonwealthfund.org/publications/2020/apr/bundled-payment-models-around-world-how-they-work-their-impact</p>	<p>Not reported</p>	<p>Evidence Scan</p>	<p>Published</p>	<p>The authors identified 23 bundled-payment initiatives across eight countries (United States, Taiwan, England, the Netherlands, Portugal, Denmark, New Zealand and Sweden). Of these, 11 initiatives had publicly available published evaluations</p> <p>Within the evidence scan, 35 evaluation studies were retrieved in total, all related to these 11 evaluated initiatives. Among these studies, 32 reported effects on quality of care and 32 reported effects on medical spending.</p> <p>Of the spending studies, 20/32 reported modest savings or slower spending growth, while 2/32 found increased spending in the early years.</p> <p>Of the quality studies, 18/32 reported improvements, 12/32 found no difference and 2/32 reported negative effects.</p> <p>Cost and quality results were generally positive irrespective of country, procedure or condition.</p> <p>Bundled payment models have the potential to reduce medical spending growth while having either a positive impact or no impact on quality of care.</p> <p>Evidence suggests bundled-payment models can reduce low-value care, strengthen provider collaboration and improve care coordination.</p>	<p>An evidence scan of primary research studies and reviews, alongside grey literature, providing an overview of current bundled-payment models in high-income countries and describing their key design elements and reported effects on quality of care and medical spending.</p> <p>All studies were observational rather than controlled experiments.</p> <p>The authors noted design weaknesses that limit certainty about cause and effect, and that voluntary participation may have introduced selection bias.</p> <p>Twelve additional initiatives were identified but had no publicly available evaluation. Patient experience was rarely assessed. Reporting of key payment design features was also limited, with risk-sharing arrangements, risk adjustment methods and payment distribution often poorly described or only briefly outlined.</p>
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					Implementation challenges included privacy constraints, difficulty defining quality criteria, identifying eligible patients, provider income concerns and possible limits on patient choice.	
Local enhanced services						
Database search	Kumar et al. 2014 Do local enhanced services in primary care improve outcomes? Results from a literature review. <i>Quality in Primary Care</i> 22(3): 157-169 https://doi.org/10.4172/1479-1064.1000652	Searches were conducted in May to June 2013.	Literature review	Published	14 studies were identified representing 14 selected LES programmes. The 14 LES programmes relate to 10 different disease areas. 13 LES were associated with some improvement in outcomes, including increased diagnosis, reductions in emergency admissions and increased referrals. Payments for successful outcomes are common to most LES specifications. Some LES include an initial start-up payment or closing fee. Examples in the review include retainer/start up fees and indicator-based payments. The authors identify three key factors influencing outcomes: the presence of a supporting national framework, existing service provision and the size of the financial incentive.	A literature review that examines whether LES in UK primary care improve clinical and process related outcomes and identifies common factors influencing their impact. The authors note several limitations including poorly reported outcomes for some LES, low practice participation and low patient uptake in some services.

Key

CCFE: Care Chain Frail Elderly Programme; LES: Local Enhanced Services; OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

Table 9: Summary of key organisational documents for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms

Citation	Content Summary
Additional roles reimbursement scheme	
<p>MacConnachie et al. 2024</p> <p>Assessing the impact and success of the additional roles reimbursement scheme. NHS Confederation, London.</p> <p>https://www.nhsconfed.org/publications/assessing-impact-and-success-additional-roles-reimbursement-scheme</p>	<p>This policy report reviews progress against the ARRS scheme’s original aims and draws on insights from PCN members, case studies and national workforce data to examine how ARRS roles have shaped access, workforce capacity and multidisciplinary working. It also outlines practical, financial and infrastructure factors influencing implementation and sets out recommendations for how the scheme could be developed beyond 2025.</p>
<p>NHS England 2019a</p> <p>Investment and evolution: a five-year framework for GP contract reform to implement The NHS Long Term Plan, NHS England, London.</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/gp-contract-2019.pdf</p>	<p>This NHS England guidance document sets out a five-year framework for GP contract reform to implement the NHS Long Term Plan. The document introduces PCNs as groups of neighbouring general practices working together to deliver services to defined populations. It establishes the Network Contract DES as the contractual mechanism through which practices collaborate within PCNs and deliver specified services. The framework also introduces the ARRS to support the recruitment of additional staff, including roles such as clinical pharmacists, social prescribing link workers, physician associates, first contact physiotherapists and community paramedics. In addition, the framework outlines requirements for PCN governance, network agreements and delivery of national service specifications through the Network Contract DES.</p>
<p>NHS England 2019b</p> <p>Network contract directed enhanced service: additional roles reimbursement scheme guidance. NHS England, London.</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/publication/network-contract-directed-enhanced-service-additional-roles-reimbursement-scheme-guidance/</p>	<p>This contractual guidance document outlines the scheme’s purpose, the workforce baseline set in 2019 and the rules for claiming reimbursement for five additional staff roles. The guidance describes how baselines are established, how claims are submitted and the requirement that only staff beyond 2019 can be funded through the scheme. It also summarises the funding arrangement entitlements and responsibilities for both commissioners and PCNs under the Network Contract DES.</p>
Additional capacity funding	
<p>Welsh Government 2025</p> <p>Implementation guidance for providers of General Medical Services.</p>	<p>This implementation guidance aims to ensure a consistent Wales-wide understanding of how the new GMS contractual changes should be delivered</p>

<p>https://www.gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2025-04/implementation-guidance-for-providers-of-general-medical-services_1.pdf</p>	<p>following agreement between Welsh Government, NHS Wales and GPC Wales.</p> <p>Within the financial section of the guidance, the document outlines that total investment into GMS services for 2024/25 includes the current year's Additional Capacity Fund allocation of £4m and a commitment to continue this funding through 2025/26 as part of the overall settlement. The document notes that a short life working group will address the Additional Capacity Fund and options for the future.</p>
<p>Miles 2025</p> <p>Written Statement: General Medical Services contract reform for 2024-25. Welsh Government.</p> <p>https://www.gov.wales/written-statement-general-medical-services-contract-reform-2024-25</p>	<p>This publication is a written Cabinet statement issued by the Cabinet secretary for Health and Social Care, outlining the agreed GMS contract reform for 2024-2025. Its purpose is to announce the investment being made into general practice for 2024-25 and to set out the key elements of the contract agreement reached between Welsh Government, NHS Wales and GPC Wales.</p> <p>The Statement confirms the total £4m investment of Additional Capacity funding for 2024-25 with a commitment to continue this funding at the same level for 2025-26 as part of the overall settlement. It confirms that there will be substantive reviews of the Additional Capacity fund with recommendations informing future contract negotiations.</p>
<p>Welsh Government. 2022</p> <p>Guidance for the GMS contract additional capacity 2022/23</p> <p>https://www.gov.wales/sites/default/files/publications/2025-07/gms-contract-additional-capacity-2022-2023-guidance.pdf</p>	<p>This operational Welsh Government guidance note provides a short background to the funding provided to support additional capacity funding in the previous financial year and outlines the scheme processes for 2022/23. From April 2022 additional capacity funding of £4m, recurrent for three years, was made available and this two-page guidance note briefly sets out how this can be used and eligibility requirements</p>
<p>Bundled payments</p>	
<p>Appleby et al. 2012</p> <p>Payment by Results. How can payment systems help to deliver better care? The Kings Fund, London.</p> <p>https://assets.kingsfund.org.uk/f/256914/x/a024b91a9b/payment_by_results_report_november_2012.pdf</p>	<p>An organisational report from The King's Fund reviewing the English NHS experience of Payment by Results and international activity-based payment systems, identifying key lessons, assessing whether Payment by Results is fit for current and future challenges, and outlining reform options including bundled, pathway, and year-of-care payments to support integrated care</p>

<p>Lindner & Lorenzoni 2023</p> <p>Innovative providers' payment models for promoting value-based health systems: Start small, prove value, and scale up. OECD Health Working Papers No. 154. OECD Publishing, Paris.</p> <p>https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/innovative-providers-payment-models-for-promoting-value-based-health-systems_627fe490-en.html</p>	<p>An OECD Health working paper examining value-based provider payment models implemented across several OECD countries, describing how bundled payments across acute episodes, chronic conditions and the continuum of care are designed to promote efficiency, improved health outcomes and enhanced patient experience, reviewing the publicly available evidence on their impact on value, and outlining key intervention points for policymakers in the design and implementation of these models to support effective adoption and scaling.</p>
<p>Siciliani et al. 2017</p> <p>Competition policy in five European countries: what can be learned for Health policy in England? The Health Foundation.</p> <p>https://www.health.org.uk/reports-and-analysis/working-papers/competition-policy-in-five-european-countries</p>	<p>This Health Foundation working paper analyses policies affecting competition in primary and secondary care across five European countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Portugal) and draws lessons for health policy in England. It reviews six dimensions of competition (patient choice, hospital payment and quality, hospital mergers, involvement of private providers, GP choice and competition, selective contracting for chronic conditions) drawing on international case studies and empirical evidence. The paper also examines the introduction of bundled payments in the Netherlands for chronic conditions (including diabetes, COPD and vascular risk), where insurers contract with care groups to deliver coordinated care, representing a form of competition "for the market" designed to improve integration and reduce fragmentation of services.</p>
<p>Direct enhanced services</p>	
<p>NHS England 2019a</p> <p>Investment and evolution: a five-year framework for GP contract reform to implement The NHS Long Term Plan, NHS England, London.</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/gp-contract-2019.pdf</p>	<p>This NHS England guidance document sets out a five-year framework for GP contract reform to implement the NHS Long Term Plan. The document introduces PCNs as groups of neighbouring general practices working together to deliver services to defined populations. It establishes the Network Contract DES as the contractual mechanism through which practices collaborate within PCNs and deliver specified services. The framework also introduces the ARRS to support the recruitment of additional staff, including roles such as clinical pharmacists, social prescribing link workers, physician associates, first contact physiotherapists and community paramedics. In addition, the framework outlines requirements for PCN governance, network agreements and delivery of national service specifications through the Network Contract DES.</p>
<p>NHS England 2019c</p>	<p>This guidance document sets out the 2019/20 Network Contract DES, outlining the purpose and structure of the DES, the eligibility and sign-up process for GP practices and the requirements for establishing and operating PCNs. It</p>

<p>Network Contract Directed Enhanced Service: contract specification 2019/20. NHS England, London</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/network-contract-des-specification-2019-20-v1.pdf</p>	<p>describes expectations for PCN arrangements, including the Network Agreement, leadership, workforce and additional roles, data sharing, patient engagement and extended hours access and details the associated financial entitlements, payment conditions and reimbursement processes. The document also explains the monitoring arrangements and administrative provisions related to PCN membership changes, payments and compliance.</p>
<p>NHS England 2022</p> <p>Network Contracted Directed Enhanced Service: investment and impact fund 2022/23: updated guidance. NHS England, London.</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/publication/network-contract-directed-enhanced-service-investment-and-impact-fund-2022-23-updated-guidance/</p>	<p>This guidance document provides updated guidance for the 2022/23 Investment and Impact Fund within the Network Contract DES, setting out the schemes purpose, structure, domains and indicators, how performance is calculated and paid and how PCNs should monitor achievement. It details live, deferred and retired indicators (with their rationales, numerators/denominators, thresholds, points, exclusions and data sources), explains prevalence and list-size adjustments and indicator standardisation and summarises in-year changes to indicators.</p>
<p>Local enhanced services</p>	
<p>NHS England 2023</p> <p>Local enhanced service commissioning through GP contracts. NHS England, London.</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/publication/local-enhanced-service-commissioning-through-gp-contracts/</p>	<p>This guidance document sets out how ICBs can commission local enhanced services through primary medical contracts, explains the background to previous arrangements and outlines new delegation changes giving ICBs responsibility for decisions on local enhanced services and local incentive schemes. It describes how ICBs may commission these services either through NHS standard contracts or variation of GP contracts and details the considerations and rules that apply when arranging such services with providers.</p>

Key

ARRS: Additional Roles Reimbursement Scheme; COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; DES: directed enhanced services; GMS: General Medical Services; GP: general practitioners; GPC: General Practitioners Committee; ICB: integrated care boards NHS: National Health Service; OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development); PCN: primary care network

Table 10: Summary of included evidence from evaluations for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms

Additional roles reimbursement scheme	
<p>Baird et al. 2022</p> <p>Integrating additional roles into primary care networks. The Kings Fund, London.</p> <p>https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/insight-and-analysis/reports/integrating-additional-roles-into-primary-care-networks</p>	<p>This evaluation examines how the ARRS reimbursement model influences recruitment and employment arrangements for additional roles in general practice. The study focuses on four ARRS-funded roles (pharmacists, physiotherapists, social prescribing link workers and paramedics) and draws on a review of relevant literature, analysis of workforce data, and interviews and focus groups with ARRS staff and stakeholders. It describes organisational factors affecting the integration of these roles within primary care networks and discusses implications for implementation and longer-term workforce sustainability.</p>

Key

ARRS: Additional roles reimbursement scheme

Table 11: Summary of primary research for additional payment and reimbursement mechanisms

Citation	Aspect of Question explored	Study type	Methods	Focus
Additional roles reimbursement scheme				
<p>Bramwell et al. 2024</p> <p>Implementing the additional roles reimbursement scheme in seven English Primary Care Networks: a qualitative study. <i>British Journal of General Practice</i>. 74(742):e323-e329. https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGP.2023.0216</p>	<p>How ARRSs are being implemented within seven PCNs across England</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Longitudinal qualitative case study Interviews and meeting-observation data collected between 2020 and 2022</p>	<p>Explores how PCNs organise, recruit and integrate ARRS funded roles in general practice and describes how ARRS reimbursement rules and funding constraints shape local employment decisions and operational challenges</p>
<p>Jones et al. 2024</p> <p>Challenges and enablers to implementation of the additional roles reimbursement scheme in primary care: a qualitative study. <i>British Journal of General Practice</i>. 74(742):e315-e322. https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGP.2023.0433</p>	<p>Challenges and enablers to implementing ARRS across three Integrated Care Systems in England</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Interviews with ARRS healthcare professionals and key stakeholders</p>	<p>Explores how Primary Care Networks recruit, organise and support ARRS roles and how the structure of the ARRS funding model influences processes such as role deployment, supervision, training pathways and integration across practice</p>
<p>McDermott et al. 2025</p> <p>Employment and deployment of additional staff roles in general practice: a realist evaluation of what works for whom, how, and why. <i>British Journal of General Practice</i>. 75(752):e153-e158. https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGP.2024.0562</p>	<p>How PCNs and general practices make decisions about employing and deploying ARRS staff</p>	<p>Qualitative</p>	<p>Realist evaluation Case study design across four PCN's in England and conducted semi-structured interviews with clinical directors, GP's, practice managers and ARRS staff</p>	<p>Explores how staffing choices shape the way ARRS roles are organised and implemented within general practice</p>
<p>Nicodemo et al. 2025.</p> <p>Effect of Additional Roles Reimbursement Scheme roles on prescription patterns and patient satisfaction in England: a retrospective</p>	<p>To determine the association between ARRS staff and prescription rates and patient satisfaction.</p>	<p>Quantitative</p>	<p>Retrospective data from more than 6000 general practices.</p>	<p>Analyses the effects of ARRS staff on prescription rates and patient satisfaction.</p>

panel data analysis. <i>British Journal of General Practice</i> 2025; 75 (750): e28-e34. https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGP.2024.0196			Data sources were from the general workforce minimum dataset and NHS digital datasets about primary care practice activity from 2018-2022.	
Penfold et al. 2025 Additional Roles Reimbursement Scheme uptake, patient satisfaction, and QOF achievement: an ecological study from 2020–2023. <i>British Journal of General Practice</i> . 75(750):e35-e42 https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGP.2024.0083	The commissioning of ARRS direct patient care roles and their association with patient experience	Quantitative	Linked PCN and general workforce data, GP patient survey responses and QOF results from 2020 to 2023.	Describes patterns in ARRS workforce uptake and analysed statistical associations with patient reported access, satisfaction and clinical effectiveness
Queens Nursing Institute 2019 ARRS workforce impact survey: the impact of the introduction of the additional roles reimbursement scheme (ARRS) on the general practice nursing workforce in England. https://qicn.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/ARRS-Workforce-Impact-Survey-2024.pdf	How the introduction of the ARRS affected the General Practice Nursing workforce in England	Quantitative Workforce impact assessment study	Cross sectional survey	Explores perceived changes in workload, role boundaries, supervision demands and workforce experiences following the introduction of ARRS roles
Directed enhanced services				
L'Esperence et al. 2021 The provision of additional services in primary care: a cross-sectional study of incentivized additional services, social deprivation, and ethnic group. <i>BJGP Open</i> . 2021 Jan 5(1): p.bjgpopen20X101141 https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgpopen20X101141	Examines the range of DES funding activity and equity of service provision across practice	Quantitative	Cross sectional survey	Explores how DES funding is distributed across general practices by measuring total funding per registered patient and assessing whether this voluntary payment mechanism is associated with variations in

				service provision by social deprivation and ethnic group.
Local enhanced services				
Marks et al. 2011 Incentivizing preventive services in primary care: perspectives on Local Enhanced Services. <i>Journal of Public Health</i> . 33(4):556-564 https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdr016	How contractual flexibility is used, through LES for preventative services and its perceived effectiveness	Mixed methods	Semi-structured interviews at 10 case study sites LES documentary analysis from 3 sites. Cross sectional survey	Explores commissioners' use of LES and other incentive arrangements, their perceived effectiveness, associated advantages and drawbacks, and how LES are deployed to support preventive activity in primary care

Key

ARRS: Additional Roles Reimbursement Scheme; DES: Directed Enhanced Services; GP: General Practitioner; LES: Local Enhanced Services; PCN: Primary Care Networks; QOF: Quality Outcomes Framework

Table 12: Summary of included evidence from reviews for incentive, quality, and performance frameworks

Resource	Citation	Recency (Search dates)	Evidence Type*	Status**	Findings	Comments
Quality outcomes framework						
Database search	Ahmed et al. 2021 What drives general practitioners in the UK to improve the quality of care? A systematic literature review. BMJ Open Quality. 10e00127. https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjog-2020-001127	2009 to 2019	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced mortality rates (in some studies) • Better data recording and documentation • Improved sociodemographic inequalities • Increased awareness and attention to previously neglected areas of care • Improved performance on incentivised indicators • Improved patient satisfaction and accessibility (in some contexts) <p>Unintended effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased quality of care in non-incentivised activities • Poor patient experiences • Increased pressure to meet targets • Risk of target-driven or 'box-ticking' care • Concerns about impersonalisation of care <p>Unintended effects (withdrawal QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced performance on previously incentivised activities, with some indicators returning towards pre-incentive levels <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence on patient experience was mixed, with improved satisfaction scores reported in some studies alongside 	The review explored how different types of incentives influenced: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical effectiveness • Patient experience • Organisational performance • GP behaviour • Health inequalities

					<p>concerns about relational and holistic aspects of care</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uncertain or variable long-term impact on clinical outcomes • Context-dependent effects across different settings and implementation models • Local competition between GP practices was associated with some improvements in quality indicators, though evidence was limited and mixed 	
Database search	<p>Boeckxstaens et al. 2011</p> <p>The equity dimension in evaluations of the quality and outcomes framework: a systematic review. BMC Health Services Research. 11:209</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-11-209</p>	January 2004 to November 2009	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall quality scores generally improved • Older patients benefited more than younger patients • Male patients benefited more than female patients • Variations in exception reporting²² is low (i.e there was little difference between practices (or over time) in how often patients were excluded from performance indicators) <p>Unintended effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small but significant differences related to deprivation were observed (favouring less deprived groups) <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total QOF scores did not vary according to ethnicity 	<p>The review aimed to examine how the introduction of QOF affected equity in treatment and treatment outcomes across population subgroups, and to assess whether exception reporting contributed to inequity</p> <p>None of the included studies assessed equity in access to care</p>

²² Exception reporting is the formal exclusion of specific patients from QOF performance indicators when applying the target would be inappropriate or unfeasible

Database search	Forbes et al. 2016 Review of the quality and outcomes framework in England: final report. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System. London. https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/review-of-qof-21st-december-2016.pdf	Systematic reviews: January 2004 to May 2016 Primary evidence: 2012 to 2016	Evidence Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practices may be encouraged to maintain their performance on incentivised areas • Modest improvements in incentivised activities were observed, particularly in the early years • Contributed to improved computerisation and recording of care delivery • Supported nurse-led multidisciplinary management of chronic disease <p>Unintended effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited alignment between indicators and priority areas identified in the Five-Year Forward View • Potential diversion of attention from broader primary care priorities and patients with complex needs <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current evidence does not show a clear population-level benefit • Effects on health outcomes appear modest and short-lived 	<p>This report reviews evidence on whether QOF improves the quality of primary care and health outcomes, including whether it changes practitioner behaviour, sustains improvements or affects outcomes after indicators are withdrawn.</p> <p>Evidence from one study suggests that performance was largely maintained following withdrawal of most QOF indicators, with only small declines observed in certain areas (e.g. influenza immunisation for asthma). No substantial reduction in performance was observed in the first year after withdrawal.</p>
Database search	Forbes et al. 2017 The role of the quality and outcomes framework in the care of long-term conditions: a systematic review. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System, London.	2004 to May 2016	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Associated with modest slowing in the rise of emergency admissions and consultation rates for severe mental illness • Associated with modest improvements in incentivised diabetes process and intermediate outcome indicators <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No clear evidence of impact on mortality 	<p>This systematic review examined evidence on whether QOF improves the quality of care and outcomes for people with long-term conditions, including its effects on processes of care, clinical outcomes, service use, holistic and integrated care, self-care and patient experience.</p>

	https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp17X693077				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No clear evidence that QOF improved integration or coordination of care, holistic care, self-care, or patient experience 	
Database search	<p>Gillam et al. 2012 Pay-for-performance in the United Kingdom: impact of the quality and outcomes framework: a systematic review. <i>Annals of Family Medicine</i>. 10(5):461-468.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1370/afm.1377</p>	January 2004 to July 2011	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modest cost-effective reductions in mortality and hospital admissions Reduced differences in performance between deprived and non-deprived areas Improved data recording and teamwork, with nurses gaining specialist skills <p>Unintended effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decline in continuity of care and satisfaction with continuity, attributed to more structured, protocol-driven care and greater task delegation within practices Conditions that were not incentivised under QOF showed poorer performance over time. Reported decline in continuity of care, attributed to more structured, protocol-driven care and greater task delegation within practices. <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality of care for incentivised conditions improved at a rapidly during the first year of the framework then returned to prior rates Limited evidence on the impact on costs, professional behaviour Little change in other patient experience domains 	This systematic review examines the evidence on how QOF has affected the quality of UK primary medical care since its introduction, reviewing the impact of pay-for-performance incentives on clinical quality, costs, professional behaviours, patient experience and equity.

Database search	<p>Ho et al. 2025</p> <p>Effect of UK quality and outcomes framework pay-for-performance programme on quality of primary care: systematic review with quantitative synthesis. BMJ. 389:e083424.</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj-2024-083424</p>	January 2004 to September 2024	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvement in recorded quality at one year after incentive introduction Process indicators that were performing less well before QOF introduction showed larger improvements after incentives were applied. Largest changes seen for complex process indicators (e.g. diabetes retinal screening) <p>Unintended effects (withdrawal QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduction in recorded quality at one and three years after incentive withdrawal Improvements observed following incentivisation were not sustained, with post-withdrawal reductions in recorded quality generally equivalent to or greater than the initial gains. <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less consistent improvement in recorded quality at three years Smaller changes observed for simple process indicators (e.g. recording blood pressure), intermediate outcomes (e.g. achieving HbA1c targets), and treatment indicators (e.g. prescribing statins). 	Reviews the one- and three-year impact on quality of care of the introduction and withdrawal of financial incentives.
Database search	<p>Holdroyd et al. 2025</p> <p>The impact of primary care funding on health inequalities: an umbrella review. Primary Health Care Research and</p>	Inception to January 2024	Umbrella Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some narrowing of socioeconomic and age-related inequalities observed, particularly in England. <p>Unintended effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temporary widening of deprivation-related gaps following introduction. 	The review synthesised systematic reviews examining how primary care funding models, including capitation, pay-for-performance (such as QOF), fee-for-service, and choice or private provider reforms, affect health inequalities in high-income countries

	Development. 26(e24):1-10. https://doi.org/10.1017/S146342362500012X				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Scotland, socioeconomic inequalities did not narrow and in some cases widened. • Persistence or widening of sex-based inequalities in some settings. • Exception reporting²³ more common among older, deprived, and multi-morbid patients. <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No consistent pattern of change in ethnic inequalities. • Effects varied by indicator (e.g. diabetes, cardiovascular measures), subgroup (e.g. age, sex, deprivation), and country (e.g. England, Scotland). • No consistent evidence that QOF produced sustained reductions in health inequalities. 	
Database search	Langdown & Peckham 2013 The use of financial incentives to help improve health outcomes: is the quality and outcomes framework fit for purpose? A systematic review. Journal of Public Health. 36(2):251-258.	January 2004 to June 2012	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QOF initially improved health outcomes for a limited number of conditions, particularly diabetes, including improvements in blood pressure, cholesterol, and HbA1c control. <p>Unintended effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited impact on non-incentivised activities, with longer-term decline relative to pre-existing trends. 	This review examined evidence on the efficacy of QOF for improving health outcomes, its impact on non-incentivised activities and the robustness of its clinical targets.

²³ Exception reporting is the formal exclusion of specific patients from QOF performance indicators when applying the target would be inappropriate or unfeasible

	https://doi.org/10.1093/pubmed/fdt077				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Differential exception reporting²⁴ may have limited the extent to which certain sub-population groups benefited from incentivised care. Ceiling thresholds²⁵ and focus on process-based indicators limited incentives to improve outcomes beyond target levels. <p>Mixed/neutral effects (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvements fell to pre-existing trends 	
Database search	<p>Srai et al. 2025</p> <p>General practice characteristics associated with pay-for-performance in the UK: a systematic review. BJGP Open. 9(2)</p> <p>https://doi.org/10.3399/BJGPO.2024.0174</p>	2006 to 2022	Systematic Review	Published	<p>Positive associations (introduction QOF):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Group practices (versus single-handed practices) associated with better overall performance Higher numbers of FTE GPs associated with better overall performance Training practice status associated with better overall performance <p>Negative associations (introduction QOF)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Socioeconomic deprivation associated with poorer overall performance Higher proportion of patients aged >65 years associated with poorer performance Larger list size associated with poorer performance Increasing mean GP age associated with poorer performance APMS contracts associated with poorer performance <p>Inconsistent associations (introduction QOF):</p>	This review sought to understand which practice characteristics are associated with QOF performance.

²⁴ Exception reporting is the formal exclusion of specific patients from QOF performance indicators when applying the target would be inappropriate or unfeasible

²⁵ A “ceiling threshold” is the upper performance level beyond which additional improvement does not generate additional financial reward.

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inconsistent associations for most other population and organisational characteristics • Inconsistent findings for ethnicity, rurality, GP gender, and list size per GP • Limited recent evidence, with most studies using early QOF data 	
Other quality improvement schemes						
Organisational search Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System	<p>Bramwell et al. 2023 'Pay for Quality improvement' schemes: financially incentivising quality improvement activity in primary care.</p> <p>Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System. London. https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/pay-for-quality-improvement%E2%80%99-schemes-literature-review.pdf</p>	2000 to 2022	Literature Review	Published	<p>The Somerset Practice Quality Scheme</p> <p>The Staffordshire Quality Improvement Framework</p> <p>The North West England Scheme</p> <p>The Australian Primary Care Collaboratives Program</p> <p>The Australian Primary Care Collaboratives Program</p> <p>Swedish Quality Improvement Project</p> <p>See Table 1 of report for a brief description of the intervention and payment mechanisms</p>	<p>This review sought to synthesise the existing evidence on the effects of financially incentivised QI activities in general medical practice on targeted clinical activities, non-targeted activities (including potential spillover effects), overall quality of care, and practitioner and organisational outcomes, and to identify additional evidence relevant to NHS England policy development.</p> <p>Five out of the six interventions listed had been evaluated and were summarised</p> <p>Excluded studies evaluating pay-for-performance schemes that incentivised attainment or reporting of clinical outcomes rather than participation in quality improvement activities (e.g., QOF and similar schemes).</p>

Key

AMPS: alternative provider medical services; FTE: full time equivalent; GP: General Practitioner; HbA1c: Glycated Haemoglobin (blood test measuring blood sugar); NHS: National Health Service; QOF: quality outcomes framework; QI: quality incentives

Table 13: Summary of key organisational documents for incentive, quality, and performance frameworks

Citation	Content Summary
Quality outcomes framework	
<p>NHS England 2018</p> <p>Report of the review of the quality and outcomes framework in England. NHS England, London</p> <p>https://www.england.nhs.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/quality-outcome-framework-report-of-the-review.pdf</p>	<p>The purpose of this report was to present the findings of the review of QOF, with the aim of stimulating discussion about how the QOF can be developed to support good quality care into the future. It investigated how QOF and other incentive schemes operate in practice, determine future priorities for an incentive scheme for general practice, taking into account QOF's strengths and limitations and the changing environment, and develop proposals for reform or a successor to QOF</p>
<p>Nuffield Trust 2014</p> <p>The NHS payment system: evolving policy and emerging evidence: Research report. Nuffield Trust, London</p> <p>https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/research/the-nhs-payment-system-evolving-policy-and-emerging-evidence</p>	<p>This report provides an examination of the different approaches to paying for health care in NHS England and summarises the available evidence on recent payment initiatives. It aims to draw lessons from research in the UK and other countries for the scope and direction of a medium-term strategy for reforming provider payment systems, and to examine the role of the payment system in achieving the overarching objectives of the NHS.</p>
Quality assurance and improvement framework	
<p>Welsh Government 2020</p> <p>Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework: supplementary guidance for the GMS contract Wales 2020/21. Welsh Government, Cardiff.</p> <p>https://www.bma.org.uk/media/3339/wales-gov-quality-and-improvement-framework-2020-21.pdf</p>	<p>Supplementary Welsh Government guidance for the 2020–21 QAIF describing COVID-19–related adjustments to the GP contract, including revised indicators, cluster-based quality improvement projects (including a COVID-19 learning project), and updated reporting requirements for general practice in Wales.</p>
<p>Welsh Government 2021</p> <p>Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework: Guidance for the GMS contract Wales 2021/22. Welsh Government, Cardiff.</p> <p>https://sbuwb.nhs.wales/about-us/key-documents-folder/performance-and-finance-committee-papers/performance-and-finance-committee-march-2023/32-app-1-qaif-guidancepdf/</p>	<p>Welsh Government guidance describing the operation of the QAIF for the 2021–22 GMS contract in Wales, including quality indicators, cluster-based quality improvement projects, access standards, and collaborative working requirements for general practice.</p>

Key:

BMA: British Medical Association; NHS: National Health Service; QAIF: Quality Assurance and Improvement Framework, QOF: Quality Outcomes Framework

6. RAPID EVIDENCE SUMMARY METHODS

Searching was conducted in three stages. First, MEDLINE (Ovid), the Cochrane Library, and Google were searched to identify relevant review evidence within the broad topic area and to map key additional payment mechanisms and models (see Appendix 1).

Second, targeted searches of MEDLINE (Ovid) and Scopus were undertaken to identify further review evidence relating specifically to the identified mechanisms and models (see Appendix 2). These searches were not intended to be exhaustive, but rather to identify relevant literature to inform subsequent snowballing, including hand-searching the reference lists of included reviews.

The final stage involved searching relevant organisational websites (see Appendix 3), including site-specific searches using advanced Google search operators, alongside a broader advanced Google search to identify additional grey literature.

This review included a substantial number of organisational reports, in addition to systematic reviews. While our Rapid Evidence Summaries are usually based on information extracted from abstracts, in this case the relevant details were rarely reported at abstract level and were instead embedded within lengthy and complex reports. Therefore, in light of time constraints of this evidence summary, a single reviewer used artificial intelligence tools Microsoft Co-Pilot or ChatGPT 4.0 to extract the relevant key information included in these documents and then to assist in concisely summarising their content. All extracted and summarised data was subsequently checked for accuracy to ensure clarity, consistency, and reliability.

As secondary evidence relating to ARRS, DES and LES was limited, further targeted searches were conducted to identify primary studies. Findings from these studies are not synthesised in detail; however, an indication of the volume of literature across different aspects of the question is provided (see Table 11). For PCNs, primary research studies were identified via organisational website searches, and these were tabulated in Table 4.

7. EVIDENCE

The relevant review evidence from the initial searches is provided within Table 14 below.

Table 14: Summary of included review evidence used to identify financial mechanisms, contractual arrangements, and delivery models supporting services beyond core GMS contract

Resource	Citation	Recency (Search dates)	Evidence Type*	Status**	Approaches to organising, funding and contracting general practice services	Evaluations
Organisational search King's Fund	Baird et al. 2022 Levers for change in primary care: a review of the literature. https://assets.kingsfund.org.uk/f/256914/x/382aff840f/levers_for_change_primary_care_literature_review_2022.pdf	2010 to 2022 for work on English systems 2015 to 2022 for international literature	Literature review	Published	Financial incentives and pay for performance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality outcomes framework Locally enhanced services 	Research into the impact of QOF found little evidence to suggest that incentivised areas of focus improve at a faster rate than non-incentivised areas (Gillam 2015). Pay-for-performance financial incentives may influence the areas on which clinicians focus their efforts and can increase activity and quality in targeted areas. However, evidence of an overall effect on patient outcomes is limited, and there is some indication that such incentives may have adverse effects on non-targeted areas of care. Targeted contracts (for example, locally enhanced services) can support the development of new care pathways and services, although evidence on cost-effectiveness remains limited. Short-term funding arrangements can also hinder robust evaluation of benefits.
Organisational search	Bramwell et al. 2014 Moving Services out of hospital: Joining up	Not specified Studies date from 1970	Rapid review	Published	<u>Payment approaches</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Year of Care Bundled payments 	The review reports that no formal evaluations were identified for the approaches described at the time of publication; discussion is based on

<p>Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System</p>	<p>General Practice and community services? August 2014. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System</p> <p>https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/prucomm-moving-services-out-of-hospital-report-v8-final.pdf</p>	<p>In areas with extensive research evidence, the authors focused upon review articles</p>	<p>Grey literature (including reports and policy documents)</p>		<p><u>Contracting approaches</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alliance contracting • Prime contracting • Accountable care organisations 	<p>existing literature and policy documents rather than evaluative evidence</p>
<p>Organisational search</p>	<p>Rosen 2025b</p> <p>What can we learn from international examples of contracting for general practice services?, in The evolution of GP contracting: learning from history and other countries. Article series, Nuffield Trust</p> <p>https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/news-item/what-can-we-learn-from-international-examples-of-contracting-for-general-practice-services</p>	<p>1947 to present (2024?) and subsequently limited to 2000</p>	<p>Literature review</p>	<p>Published as Blog</p>	<p><u>International examples of organising and contracting general practice</u></p> <p>Netherlands – chronic disease management via care groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bundled payments for chronic disease management • Contracts between insurance companies and large operational support organisations (“care groups”) <p>Norway – general practice contract arrangements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fee-for-service payment reform • Revised blended payments in the GP contract to incentivise GP productivity <p>Massachusetts, USA – insurer-led contracting arrangements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted micro-incentives for quality and cost containment, with data and implementation support • The Massachusetts Blue Cross Blue Shield Alternative Quality Contract 	<p>International examples are discussed descriptively and comparatively; no formal evaluation or synthesis of outcomes is undertaken</p>

					<p>Estonia – group practice development</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estates development as a stimulus for a group practice contract • Contracts to incentivise the formation of group practice and multi-professional teams 	
<p>Organisational search</p> <p>Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System</p>	<p>Peckham & Gousia 2014</p> <p>GP payment schemes review. Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System. London. https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/assets/uploads/files/gp_paymentschemesreviewfinal.pdf</p>	<p>1998 to 2014</p> <p>Initially restricted to articles published after 1998 although relevant key older papers were also reviewed</p> <p>Studies before 1998 have been reviewed in Gosden et al. (1999), Gosden et al. (2000), and Gosden et al. (2001)</p>	<p>Literature review</p> <p>²⁶</p>	<p>Published</p>	<p>Fee for service</p> <p>Capitation</p> <p>Salary</p> <p>Blended payment methods</p> <p>i. partial capitation which combines FFS payments for a subset of services with capitation for services that are less amenable to piece-rate production</p> <p>ii. mixed models that blend elements of capitation payment, pay-for-performance incentives and FFS</p> <p>iii. bundled payments that pays the accountable provider organisation a fixed amount for the bundle of services required for treatment of an episode of care and</p> <p>iv. shared savings arrangements, which pay FFS to provider organisations but periodically share savings if total payments are less than a predetermined total healthcare cost (budget) target</p>	<p>The review does not address the impact of pay for performance incentive schemes. These may occur alongside any existing funding mechanism and discussions of the impact of such schemes has been extensively discussed and reviewed elsewhere (Flodgren et al. 2011, Gillam et al. 2012, Langdown and Peckham 2014, Scott et al. 2011)</p> <p>The review explored the impacts of different remuneration schemes in primary care, with particular attention to their influence on physicians' behaviour</p> <p>The literature focused on a limited set of outcomes, including service volume, referral patterns, supplier-induced demand, patient selection, and preventive activities, while other potential impacts, such as effects on organisational structures, were largely not examined</p>

²⁶ Grey literature (including documents and reports from the Department of Health, the King's Fund Information and Library Service, the Nuffield Trust, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, the Institute for Fiscal Studies, the World Bank and academic books specific to the subject matter)

Database search	Harris et al. 2025 General practice incentives: a review of the international literature. Br J Gen Pract. 2025 Nov 24:BJGP.2025.0143 https://doi.org/10.3399/bjgp.2025.0143	2020 to Nov 2023 17 SRs 2 URs 1 Narrative review	Umbrella review	Published	Pay for performance (n=20) Fee for service Capitation Bonus Payments Other models	The absence of detailed extraction tables and supplementary material means that schemes could not be reliably classified as core funding arrangements or additional payment models, limiting their use for detailed categorisation within this review Research Question 1: Impact on health care quality outcomes in multidisciplinary settings Research Question 2: Impact on preventive care for people with chronic conditions
Database search	Heider et al. 2020 Effects of Monetary Incentives in Physician Groups: A Systematic Review of Reviews. Appl Health Econ Health Policy. 2020 Oct;18(5):655-667 https://doi.org/10.1007/s40258-020-00572-x	No date restrictions Search conducted Jan 2020	Umbrella review	Published	Salary (n=2) Fee for service (n=5) Bonus payments (n=2) Bundled payments (n=3) Pay for Performance (n=10) Capitation (e.g. managed care, fund holding) (n=5) Accountable care organisations (n=3)	The review synthesised evidence from 21 reviews and reported mixed and heterogeneous findings. Positive effects were most consistently observed for process measures; outcome effects were variable and often inconclusive Some evidence suggests that performance-linked reimbursement systems may be associated with improvements in process or outcome quality in certain settings; however, findings were inconsistent across reviews, and the overall strength of evidence was weak
Advance Google Search	Kidd et al. 2024 Review of general practice incentives: International evidence and literature review. Faculty of Medicine	Jan 2010 to Nov 2023 26 SRs 2 URs	Rapid Review	Published	Pay for Performance (n=22) Fee for Service Capitation Bonus Payments	RQ 1 What is the evidence from the literature on the effectiveness of different payment models on quality outcomes in multidisciplinary settings?

	<p>and Health, UNSW Sydney.</p> <p>https://www.health.gov.au/resources/publications/review-of-general-practice-incentives-international-evidence-and-literature-review?language=en</p>	<p>1 narrative review 1 qualitative synthesis</p> <p>Additional searches identified 12 cohort and observational studies</p>			<p>Mixed and other models</p>	<p>RQ 2 What is the evidence from the literature on the effectiveness of different payment models on preventive care for people with complex chronic disease?</p> <p>RQ 3 What are the benefits of funding primary care using different payment models (e.g. block funding, FFS, outcomes based, incentives, salaried models and others), including the interactions between different funding models in blended systems and the outcomes they produce for people and the health system?</p> <p>RQ 4 What is the evidence on what drives behavioural change in primary care providers with regard to providing quality, patient-centred care?</p>
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Key FFS: Fee for service; RQ: research question; QOF: quality outcomes framework

8. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

8.1. Conflict of interest

The authors declare they have no conflicts of interest to report.

8.2. Acknowledgments

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9. APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Initial database searching audit

Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 20 Jan 2026
1	exp Reimbursement Mechanisms/	39352
2	exp Capitation Fee/	4259
3	exp Single-Payer System/	568
4	((financial or payment*) adj2 (incentive* or reward* or model* or scheme* or method* or reimburs* or program* or plan* or mechanism* or practice* or process* or framework*).ti	3890
5	(blended payment* or pay-for-performance or P4P).ti.	1231
6	(bonus adj2 (performance or payment or practice)).ti.	9
7	(fee-for-service* or paid-for-service* or FFS).ti.	1099
8	(capitation* or capitated financing).ti.	1288
9	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8	46458
10	exp Implementation Science/	1932
11	design*.ti.	216464
12	(implet* or commission* or contract* or admin* or mechanism* or develop).ti.	709590
13	10 or 11 or 12	924841
14	(review* or synthesis).tw.	4229375
15	9 and 13	1593
16	14 and 15	183
17	limit 16 to english language	178
18	limit 17 to yr="2004 -Current"	100

Appendix 2: Targeted searching audit

Year of Care / Accountable Care: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 27 Jan 2026
1	"year of care".ti.	98
2	limit 1 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	80
3	("accountable care" adj (organi#ation or model* or contract*)).ti.	196
4	limit 2 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	196
5	"year of care".tw.	742
6	("accountable care" adj (organi#ation or model* or contract*)).tw.	626
7	exp General Practice/	80,867
8	exp Primary Health Care/	211,710
9	exp General Practitioners/	12,308
10	exp Physicians, Family/	17,702
11	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,927
12	exp Group Practice/	23,705
13	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	12,945
14	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	37,394
15	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	109,896
16	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,646
17	7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14 or 15 or 16	536,071
18	5 and 17	184
19	6 and 17	247
20	limit 18 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	143
21	limit 19 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	246

Year of Care / Accountable Care: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 27 Jan 2026
1	TITLE ("year of care")	44
2	1 Limited to English Language and Publication Year 2004-2026	23
3	TITLE ("accountable care" PRE/0 (organi?ation OR model* OR contract*))	818
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((supplementary OR enhanced OR additional) PRE/0 service*)	4,929
5	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,241
6	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,932
7	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,529
8	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	402,444
9	OR 2-5	639,893
10	3 AND 9	179

Year of Care: Title

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	80
Scopus	23
Total	103
Duplicates	2
New Total	101

Accountable Care: Title

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	196
Scopus	179
Total	375
Duplicates	57
New Total	318

Supplementary Services: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 28 Jan 2026
1	((supplementary or enhanced or additional) adj service*).tw.	1,223
2	exp General Practice/	80,871
3	exp Primary Health Care/	211,742
4	exp General Practitioners/	12,312
5	exp Physicians, Family/	17,703
6	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,928
7	exp Group Practice/	23,705
8	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	12,950
9	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	37,398
10	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	109,912
11	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,710
12	2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11	536,166
13	1 and 12	277

Supplementary Services: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 28 Jan 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((supplementary OR enhanced OR additional) PRE/0 service*)	4,929
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,241
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,932
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,529
5	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	402,444
6	OR 2-5	639,893
7	1 AND 6	253

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	277
Scopus	253
Total	530
Duplicates Endnote	188
New Total	342

Alliance Contracting: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	(alliance adj2 (contract* or partnering or pure or project)).ti.	12
2	(alliance adj2 (contract* or partnering or pure or project)).tw.	81
3	exp General Practice/	80,886
4	exp Primary Health Care/	211,830
5	exp General Practitioners/	12,316
6	exp Physicians, Family/	17,708
7	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,933
8	exp Group Practice/	23,705
9	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	12,962
10	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	37,423
11	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	109,937

12	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,868
13	3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12	536,398
14	1 and 13	0
15	2 and 13	12

Alliance Contracting: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY (alliance W/1 (contract* OR partnering OR pure OR project))	968
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,241
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,970
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,675
5	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	402,932
6	OR 2-5	640,348
7	1 AND 6	31

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid) Title	12
Medline (Ovid) Tw	12
Scopus	31
Total	55
Duplicates Raayan	11
New Total	44

Prime / Lead Contracting: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	((prime or lead) adj2 contract*).ti.	34
2	((prime or lead) adj2 contract*).tw.	395
3	exp General Practice/	80,886
4	exp Primary Health Care/	211,830
5	exp General Practitioners/	12,316
6	exp Physicians, Family/	17,708
7	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,933
8	exp Group Practice/	23,705
9	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	12,962
10	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	37,423
11	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	109,937
12	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,868
13	3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12	536,398
14	2 and 13	4
15	1 OR 14	38
16	Limit 15 to (English Language and yr=2004 – Current)	18

Prime / Lead Contracting: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	TITLE ((prime OR lead) PRE/1 contract*)	81
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((prime OR lead) PRE/1 contract*)	2,620
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,302
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,970
5	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,675
6	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	402,932
7	OR 3-6	640,348
8	2 AND 7	5
9	1 OR 8	86
10	Limit 9 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	50

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	18
Scopus	50
Total	68
Duplicates	2
New Total	66

Multispeciality community providers: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	(multispeciality community provider* or multi-speciality community provider*).ti.	0
2	(multispeciality community provider* or multi-speciality community provider*).tw	0

Multispeciality community providers: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	TITLE ("multispeciality community provider*" or multi-speciality community provider*)	0
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("multispeciality community provider*" or multi-speciality community provider*)	0

Primary care networks: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	primary care network*.ti.	222
2	primary care network*.tw.	805
3	exp General Practice/	80,886
4	exp Primary Health Care/	211,830
5	exp General Practitioners/	12,316
6	exp Physicians, Family/	17,708
7	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,933
8	exp Group Practice/	23,705
9	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	12,962
10	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	37,423
11	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*)).tw.	109,937
12	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,868

13	3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12	536,398
14	2 and 13	805
15	review*.ti,pt	3982872
16	14 AND 15	27
17	Limit 16 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	25

Primary care networks Scopus

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	TITLE ("primary care network*")	247
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("primary care network*")	897
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,302
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,970
5	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,675
6	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	402,932
7	OR 3-6	640,348
8	2 AND 7	897
9	TITLE (review*)	1,584,836
10	8 AND 9	14
11	Limit 10 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	12

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	25
Scopus	12
Total	37
Duplicates	11
New Total	26

Bundled payments: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	((bundled or episode) adj3 payment*).tw.	1593
2	exp General Practice/	80,886
3	exp Primary Health Care/	211,830
4	exp General Practitioners/	12,316
5	exp Physicians, Family/	17,708
6	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,933
7	exp Group Practice/	23,705
8	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*).tw.	12,962
9	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*).tw.	37,423
10	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*).tw.	109,937
11	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,868
12	2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11	536,398
13	1 and 12	255
14	Limit 13 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	247

#	Query	Results from 03 Feb 2026
1	((bundled or episode) adj3 payment*).tw.	1593
2	review.ti,pt.	3969056
3	1 and 2	157
4	limit 3 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	152

Bundled payments: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((bundled OR episode) PRE/2 payment*)	1,835
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,302
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,970
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,675
5	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	402,932
6	OR 2-5	640,348
7	1 AND 6	87
8	Limit 7 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	85

#	Query	Results from 03 Feb 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((bundled OR episode) PRE/2 payment*)	1,835
2	TITLE (review*)	1,585,443
3	1 and 2	45
4	Limit 3 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	45

All publications:

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	247
Scopus	85
Total	333
Duplicates	61
New Total	272

Reviews:

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	152
Scopus	45
Total	197
Duplicates Endnote	41
New Total	156

Additional Roles Reimbursement Schemes: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	(additional role* reimbursement scheme* or additional capacity fund*).ti.	5
2	(additional role* reimbursement scheme* or additional capacity fund*).tw	12
3	Limit 2 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	12

Additional Roles Reimbursement Schemes Scopus

#	Query	Results from 02 Feb 2026
1	TITLE ("additional role* reimbursement scheme*" OR "additional capacity fund*")	6
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("additional role* reimbursement scheme*" OR "additional capacity fund*")	16
3	Limit 2 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	15

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	12
Scopus	15
Total	27
Duplicates Endnote	10
New Total	17

Outcome-based contracting: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 3 Feb 2026
1	(outcome-based adj (contract* or commission*).tw.	18
2	Limit 2 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	17

Outcome-based contracting: Scopus

#	Query	Results from 3 Feb 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,303
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,982
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,720
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	403,001
5	OR 1-4	640,464
6	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("outcome-based" PRE/0 (contract* OR commission*))	171
7	5 AND 6	4
8	TITLE (review*)	1,585,443
9	5 AND 8	4
10	7 OR 9	8
11	Limit 11 to (English Language and yr=2004-2026)	8

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	17
Scopus	8
Total	25
Duplicates Endnote	2
New Total	23

Quality Outcomes Framework: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 3 Feb 2026
1	exp General Practice/	80,898
2	exp Primary Health Care/	211,911
3	exp General Practitioners/	12,321
4	exp Physicians, Family/	17,709
5	exp Physicians, Primary Care/	4,937
6	exp Group Practice/	23,705
7	(community adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*).tw.	12,969
8	(family adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*).tw.	37,427
9	(general adj2 (doctor* or physician* or practice* or practitioner*).tw.	109,957
10	(family medicine or community medicine or primary care or primary health care or gp).tw.	246,930
11	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10	536,527
12	("quality outcome* framework*" or "quality and outcome* framework*" or QOF).tw.	653
13	review*.ti,pt.	3,984,031
14	11 and 12 and 13	45
15	limit 14 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	45

Quality Outcomes Framework Scopus

#	Query	Results from 3 Feb 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY (community W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	40,303
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY (family W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	112,982
3	TITLE-ABS-KEY (general W/1 (doctor* OR physician* OR practice* OR practitioner*))	253,720
4	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("family medicine" OR "community medicine" OR "primary care" OR "primary health care" OR GP)	403,001
5	OR 1-4	640,464
6	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("quality outcome* framework*" OR "quality and outcome* framework*" OR QOF)	919
7	TITLE (review*)	1,585,443
8	5 AND 6 AND 7	29
9	limit 14 to (english language and yr="2004 -Current")	29

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	45
Scopus	29
Total	74
Duplicates	23
New Total	51

Quality Incentive schemes: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 3 Feb 2026
1	("quality improvement scheme*" or "quality incentive* scheme*").tw.	16
2	review.ti.pt.	3,969,056
3	1 and 2	2

Quality Incentive schemes Scopus

#	Query	Results from 3 Feb 2026
1	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("quality improvement scheme*" OR "quality incentive* scheme*")	60
2	TITLE (review*)	1,585,443
3	1 and 2	1

Database	Results
Medline (Ovid)	2
Scopus	1
Total	3
Duplicates	0
New Total	3

Quality assurance and improvement framework: Ovid MEDLINE

#	Query	Results from 11 Feb 2026
1	"quality assurance and improvement framework".ti.	0
2	"quality assurance and improvement framework".tw.	1

Quality assurance and improvement framework

#	Query	Results from 25 Feb 2026
1	TITLE ("quality assurance and improvement framework")	0
2	TITLE-ABS-KEY ("quality assurance and improvement framework")	1

Appendix 3: Key organisational websites searched

Health Foundation - <https://www.health.org.uk/>

NHS England - <https://www.england.nhs.uk/>

Nuffield Trust - <https://www.nuffieldtrust.org.uk/>

King's Fund - <https://www.kingsfund.org.uk/>

NHS Confederation <https://www.nhsconfed.org/>

Policy Research Unit in Commissioning and the Healthcare System <https://pru.hssc.ac.uk/>

National Association of Primary Care <https://napc.co.uk/>

Year of Care <https://www.yearofcare.co.uk/>

Welsh Government <https://www.gov.wales/>

Health and Care
Research Wales
Evidence Centre

Canolfan Dystiolaeth
Ymchwil Iechyd a
Gofal Cymru

The Health and Care Research Wales Evidence Centre

Our dedicated team works together with Welsh Government, the NHS, social care, research institutions and the public to deliver vital research to tackle health and social care challenges facing Wales.

Funded by Welsh Government, through Health and Care Research Wales, the Evidence Centre answers key questions to improve health and social care policy and provision across Wales.

Along with our collaborating partners, we conduct reviews of existing evidence and new research, to inform policy and practice needs, with a focus on ensuring real-world impact and public benefit that reaches everyone.

Director: Professor Adrian Edwards

Associate Directors: Dr Alison Cooper, Dr Natalie Joseph-Williams, Dr Ruth Lewis

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